

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Adoption and Diffusion of Organic Farming

Discussion paper

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Adoption and Diffusion of Organic Farming

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Abstract

Organic farming is widely recognised as a key component of the transition to sustainable agriculture, contributing to the achievement of several Sustainable Development Goals. In line with these objectives, European policy frameworks call for a substantial expansion of agricultural land under organic management by 2030. Against this background, this study examines the diffusion and adoption of organic farming in two European Union (EU) Member States: the Czech Republic and Germany.

Using official statistics from the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic and Germany's Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, the study analyses the diffusion of organic farming and projects the share of agricultural land under organic management in 2030 using the Bass diffusion model. To further examine adoption behaviour, the study investigates farm-level determinants of organic farming adoption using data from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database for the period 2008–2021. Adoption patterns are analysed using a probit model specified as a within-between random-effects (WBRE) panel data model, complemented by cross-sectional and pooled probit models. Together, these approaches provide a comprehensive assessment of the determinants of organic farming adoption based on observed farm behaviour.

Despite ambitious national targets, projections based on the Bass diffusion model suggest that these targets are unlikely to be achieved in either country under current conditions. The results indicate that the Czech Republic and Germany are at different stages of the diffusion process, with innovation- and imitation-driven mechanisms playing distinct roles. While imitation effects are more pronounced in Germany, they remain limited in the Czech Republic.

Financial support is more strongly associated with conversion to organic farming than price premiums in both countries. Consumer demand also plays a key role in the diffusion of organic farming, with market-related effects being stronger in Germany, reflecting its more developed organic market. Conversion is further associated with farmers' pro-environmental orientations, as proxied by prior participation in agri-environment-climate measures and lower input intensity before conversion. Finally, organic farming adoption in both countries is negatively associated with economic size, production specialisation, and labour intensity, with the magnitude of these associations increasing over time, while being positively associated with location in mountainous and upland areas.

Overall, the findings highlight substantial heterogeneity across diffusion stages, indicating that early and late adopters represent structurally distinct types of farms. This heterogeneity suggests that effective policy support should be stage-specific and combine differentiated supply-side and demand-side measures. For modellers, the study provides projections of organic farming diffusion based on land conversion, as well as an identification of monetary and non-monetary drivers of conversion and their effects on adoption likelihood.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the urgent need to transform agri-food production systems towards greater sustainability. One key approach in the primary sector is organic agriculture, also referred to as ecological agriculture (Rizzo et al., 2024). It is a holistic production management system that prioritises locally adapted practices, minimises external inputs, and relies on agronomic, biological, and mechanical methods rather than synthetic inputs (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2025). Its core principles include diverse crop rotations, the maintenance of ecosystem dynamics, and the closing of nutrient cycles (International Federation of Organic Agricultural Movements, 2020).

Although the concept of organic agriculture emerged in the early twentieth century (Shi-ming & Sauerborn, 2006), it continues to represent an innovation in agricultural practice, as its adoption requires new management knowledge and skills (Rizzo et al., 2024; Gailhard et al., 2018). Today, organic farming is widely regarded as a modern production approach that combines traditional nature-friendly practices with contemporary technologies. It integrates advanced mechanization, improved crop varieties, soil and water conservation techniques, and innovations in livestock management (Reganold & Wachter, 2016), thereby contributing to sustainability goals such as improved soil health, enhanced biodiversity, climate resilience, social equity, and food safety (Giampieri et al., 2022; Meemken & Qaim, 2018; Bengtsson et al., 2005).

Organic systems generally exhibit lower yields than conventional systems (Meemken & Qaim, 2018), although this gap is expected to narrow with advances in management practices and crop varieties (Reganold & Wachter, 2016). Under drought conditions, organically managed farms may even outperform conventional systems due to higher soil water-holding capacity, suggesting greater resilience to climate change. Organic farming also offers potential benefits for food quality, including lower pesticide residues and nitrate levels, although nutritional advantages remain debated (Meemken & Qaim, 2018).

A substantial body of literature highlights the environmental benefits of organic farming. Reduced use of synthetic inputs lowers the risk of water pollution, while organic systems generally perform better in terms of nutrient leaching and greenhouse gas emissions per unit of land. However, these advantages are less pronounced—or may even reverse—when measured per unit of output due to lower land-use efficiency. Organic farming also enhances biodiversity, improves soil quality, and reduces soil erosion (Boschiero et al., 2023; Aulakh et al., 2022; Reganold & Wachter, 2016).

These benefits have led the European Union (EU) and other developed countries to actively promote organic farming (Möhring et al., 2024), raising important research questions regarding its adoption and diffusion. Adoption studies typically focus on farm and farmer characteristics and the factors influencing conversion decisions, while diffusion studies examine how adoption spreads over time and space.

The adoption of organic farming largely depends on its financial performance relative to conventional agriculture (Reganold & Wachter, 2016; Kuminoff & Wossink, 2010). Key determinants include yields, production costs, price premiums, income losses during the transition period (European Parliament, 2018), certification costs, and potential savings from reduced input use. Subsidies and price premiums can make organic farming competitive with conventional systems. However, decision-making is complex and shaped by additional factors, including risk perceptions, environmental conditions, market structures, social pressures, and institutional support (Silva-Cortés et al., 2025; Möhring et al., 2024; Haldar & Damodaran, 2022; Ambrosius et al., 2022; Meemken & Qaim, 2018; Läßle, 2013).

The diffusion of organic farming follows a typical S-shaped pattern (Padel, 2001). According to Rogers' diffusion theory (2003), early adopters differ systematically from later adopters. As diffusion is non-linear across time and space, the determinants of adoption may vary across stages of the diffusion process (Läpple & Rensburg, 2011). Understanding these dynamics is essential for designing effective, evidence-based policies.

However, a systematic review by Möhring et al. (2024) shows that temporal changes in adoption determinants are rarely addressed in the literature. This study seeks to fill this gap by analysing the diffusion and adoption of organic farming across time and space. Specifically, it aims to: (i) analyse the diffusion process in two European countries—the Czech Republic and Germany; (ii) identify the determinants of observed adoption decisions; and (iii) assess how these determinants vary across different stages of diffusion, using Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) data for 2008–2021.

While the initial research design considered NUTS2-level data, the final empirical strategy is based on country- and farm-level analyses. This enables the examination of long-term diffusion dynamics, since 1985 for Germany and 1990 for the Czech Republic, which cannot be consistently captured at the regional level. By applying the Bass diffusion model, the study provides new evidence on the expected future trajectory of organic farming adoption.

The study further contributes to the literature by offering a systematic assessment of heterogeneity in adoption determinants across time, space, and production specialisations. By focusing on the Czech Republic, it also addresses a gap in geographic coverage identified by Möhring et al. (2024), as existing research on organic farming adoption in this country remains limited (Malá & Malý, 2013).

The remainder of the study is structured as follows. The next chapter reviews methodological approaches used to analyse organic farming adoption and diffusion. The subsequent chapter describes the data and methods. The following chapter presents and interprets the results, which are then discussed. The final chapter summarises the main findings and limitations.

2. BACKGROUND

The adoption of organic farming represents a significant decision for agricultural producers. This decision involves a complex process in which farmers evaluate a range of socio-economic, agro-ecological, and institutional factors (Singh et al., 2023). The resulting outcome reflects not only these considerations but also the farm manager's individual characteristics, including psychological factors (Ambrosius et al., 2022).

To examine this process, researchers have employed a variety of methodological approaches, including binary choice models, fractional models, duration analysis, and structural equation modelling. A systematic review by Möhring et al. (2024) shows that binary choice models based on cross-sectional data from agricultural censuses or surveys were the most commonly used approach to study organic farming adoption between 2000 and 2021. These models provide a “snapshot in time” and enable the identification of key drivers of adoption based on observed farmer decisions.

Farmers' intentions to adopt organic farming are typically analysed using survey data combined with structural equation modelling. Duration analysis—also generally based on survey data—examines how adoption decisions evolve over time by measuring the interval between the moment a farmer becomes aware of the option to adopt organic farming and the moment adoption occurs. Event-history analysis can also be used to examine the duration until abandonment of organic farming, using agricultural census data for farms observed over the entire period (Heinze & Vogel, 2017; Läpple, 2010).

Binary choice models typically explain observed adoption decisions using socio-economic characteristics such as farm size, farmer age, gender, education, production orientation, and financial incentives (e.g., organic farming subsidies). Recent studies employing this approach include Singh et al. (2023), who analyse organic farming adoption in India using a logit model, and Halder and

Damodaran (2022), who use a probit model to examine how cooperatives, output prices, and price volatility influence adoption decisions in the United States.

In the European context, Chatzimichael et al. (2014) employed a probit model to evaluate the effects of social learning and financial incentives on farmers' adoption decisions. Using survey data from olive and cereal producers in Greece and Germany, they find that informational spillovers exert a stronger influence than conversion subsidies in promoting organic farming adoption.

Another notable European study is Jaime et al. (2016), which applies a binary choice model to examine the effects of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) on organic farming adoption in Sweden. Unlike most studies, this analysis relies on balanced panel data from 2000 to 2008 derived from FADN. However, the use of panel data introduces several challenges, including individual heterogeneity, state dependence, and the initial conditions problem. Because FADN data do not record the exact timing of adoption, the underlying stochastic process cannot be fully observed. Moreover, the transition to organic farming involves management changes and short-term income losses, implying that the probability of being an organic producer depends on past adoption status. This state dependence violates the assumption of strict exogeneity and, if not properly addressed, leads to inconsistent estimates.

To address these issues, Jaime et al. (2016) estimate a dynamic non-linear panel probit model in which current participation depends on past participation, using farm-level characteristics (production inputs, land tenure, specialisation, soil quality, and CAP payments) and regional characteristics (the share of organic farms and potential productivity) as explanatory variables. Their results highlight the importance of state dependence as well as agglomeration effects, suggesting that farmers located in close geographical proximity tend to exhibit similar behavioural patterns, likely due to information sharing. In addition, geographical and economic conditions also influence adoption patterns and may be spatially correlated. The study further shows that the impact of the CAP changed following the 2003 reform: while the pre-2003 market support system discouraged the adoption of organic farming, this effect was reversed after decoupling, which enabled farmers to respond to market signals while maintaining financial security, thereby reducing the opportunity costs of organic production.

Using FADN data to analyse the adoption of organic farming in French crop production, Latruffe and Nauges (2014) applied a different approach. Farms that converted to organic agriculture were included only in the year of conversion and excluded thereafter. To ensure consistency and avoid repeated observations, a random draw was conducted so that non-adopters also appeared only once in the final sample. Because the adoption decision is likely made at least one year prior to conversion, and to mitigate simultaneity bias, all explanatory variables were measured in the year preceding adoption. Incorporating a technical efficiency score, farm size, legal status, farmer education, indebtedness, the ratio of fertiliser expenditure to standard gross margin, price premiums, and subsidies as explanatory variables in the probit model, their results suggest an adverse selection effect: less efficient farms, particularly smaller ones, are more likely to adopt organic farming. Given their financial constraints and limited market power, small farms may view organic production as a means of producing higher-value commodities and obtaining price premiums, thereby making conversion a more attractive strategy.

FADN data have also been used to examine the adoption of organic farming by Cimino et al. (2025), who, using a logit model, found that Italian farmers' decisions to convert to organic production are closely linked to geographical location. Peri-urban farmers are more inclined to supply organic products than those in other areas, owing to their proximity to urban consumers who are willing to pay a premium. Similarly, Chmieliński et al. (2019), employing Polish FADN data to estimate logit models separately for each year between 2009 and 2015, concluded that the propensity to convert to organic farming is strongly conditioned by regional factors.

Research focusing on farmers' behavioural intentions to adopt organic farming has been built on different constructs from innovation theory. For example, Silva-Cortés et al. (2025) employed the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), a framework introduced by Davis (1989), to assess user acceptance of information technology. According to TAM, two fundamental determinants of technology acceptance are identified: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. The former refers to the degree to which farmers believe that using a new technology will improve their performance, while the latter reflects the degree to which farmers believe that using the technology will require minimal effort.

In the context of organic farming adoption, these determinants can be represented by perceived benefits, such as economic returns, improved product quality, and enhanced soil health (perceived usefulness), as well as by the effort required to implement and maintain organic farming systems, including additional labour for soil preparation and plant protection, and the time and effort needed to obtain certification (Silva-Cortés et al., 2025).

Current research acknowledges that farmers' behavioural intention to adopt organic farming is shaped not only by economic factors and structural enablers but also by socio-psychological influences (Rizzo et al., 2024; Dessart et al., 2019). This perspective aligns with Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003). According to TPB, the intention of farmers are determined by three components: attitude towards the behaviour, the degree to which a farmer evaluates organic farming favourably; subjective norms as in the perceived social pressure to adopt organic practices; and perceived behavioural control—the perceived ease or difficulty of adoption, reflecting both enabling factors and constraints.

Building on this framework, UTAUT extends the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by introducing additional constructs, including social influence and facilitating conditions. Social influence refers to perceived pressure from others, such as consumers, government authorities, other farmers, family members, and peers, to adopt organic farming. Facilitating conditions encompass external factors and resources that either support or hinder adoption, such as subsidies or bureaucratic complexity.

Empirical studies grounded in these theoretical frameworks aim to identify key predictors of farmers' behavioural intentions to adopt organic farming using survey data and structural equation modelling (e.g., Silva-Cortés et al., 2025) or fractional regression (Tran-Nam & Tiet, 2022¹). Their findings emphasize the importance of peer influence, observable evidence of benefits, and positive perceptions of both effort and outcomes in shaping farmers' decision-making processes. Despite the well-documented bureaucratic challenges associated with organic conversion, farmers with strong community support and clear knowledge of the benefits are more likely to adopt organic farming practices.

The importance of farmers' attitudes and preferences in adoption decisions is also highlighted in a duration analysis conducted by Kallas et al. (2010), who examined the adoption of organic practices in the vineyard sector in the Spanish region of Catalonia. Their results show that farmers who are more willing to take risks and who prioritise environmental preservation and local employment tend to adopt organic practices more quickly. Higher hazard rates are also observed for small farms located in less-favoured areas (LFAs) and for those with diversified production. Moreover, easy access to information sources and supportive policy frameworks further encourage adoption. Conversely, older farmers whose decisions are primarily driven by economic considerations, as well as those operating highly specialised and larger farms, exhibit a lower likelihood of adopting organic practices.

Duration analysis, although a less commonly used approach, makes it possible to identify not only the factors that drive farmers to adopt organic farming but also the timing of adoption and the

¹ Fractional logistic regression was employed because the dependent variable represents the percentage of investment in organic farming.

determinants of observed temporal patterns. This method is typically applied to survey data, as it requires information on the exact moment when a farm enters the organic agriculture regime, information that, for instance, FADN data do not fully provide.

Studies on the diffusion of organic farming examine cumulative adoption rates, typically measured either as the share of agricultural land under organic management relative to total agricultural land or as the proportion of organic farmers within the total farming population. At the regional level, these analyses often employ spatial regression methods to capture geographic patterns of organic farming adoption. The observed adoption rates are then modelled as a function of various explanatory factors. For example, Kitano (2025) investigates the impact of social capital on the diffusion of organic farming using a spatial Durbin model, with farm size, management type, and socio-economic characteristics included as control variables. The results, based on Japanese data, show that collaborative behaviour among community members and farmers is an important factor in the spread of organic agriculture. Moreover, prior environmentally friendly agricultural practices and a higher share of large farms facilitate the diffusion of organic farming.

Bjørkhaug and Blekesaune (2013) examined how the adoption rate of organic farming in Norway relates to population density, farm density, processing capacity, and farm size, and identified a significant neighbourhood effect: the share of organic farms in one municipality is positively associated with the share in adjacent municipalities. Their findings also highlight the importance of local markets, showing that a strong local consumer base with positive attitudes towards locally produced food contributes to a higher share of organic farms.

Another approach used to investigate the diffusion of organic farming is agent-based modelling. Ambrosius et al. (2022) employed this simulation method to study the diffusion of organic farming among pig producers in the Netherlands, incorporating social interaction mechanisms, market price dynamics, and heterogeneity in farming styles. Their findings indicate that demand for organic products is the most influential driver of organic farming diffusion. In an earlier study, Kaufmann et al. (2009) applied agent-based modelling to explore how organic farming spread in Latvia and Estonia and found that economic factors played a more significant role than social factors.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Data

This study focuses on the diffusion and adoption of organic farming in two Member States of the European Union (EU): the Czech Republic and Germany. According to Eurostat (2025) and FiBL (2025), the Czech Republic, with 16% of its total agricultural area under organic management, is a leader in organic farming adoption in Central Europe. However, its organic retail market share remains relatively low, at 1.7%. In contrast, Germany, with a more than 50-year tradition in organic farming and organic products accounting for 6.3% of retail sales, has a relatively smaller share of agricultural land under organic management (11%).

The description of organic farming diffusion in these two countries is based on official statistics from the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic and Germany's Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity. These data are presented in Table A1 in the Appendix. In addition, data on organic farmland for the period 1985–1993, obtained from the OrganicTargets4EU project, are used in the diffusion analysis (Willer et al., 2024).

Furthermore, this study uses data from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN), the only official source of harmonised and representative farm-level microeconomic data covering the entire EU. The database is based on annual farm surveys conducted in EU Member States and collects physical,

structural, economic, and financial information on commercial agricultural holdings. FADN is specifically designed to ensure representativeness at the national level through a stratified sampling framework that accounts for region, type of farming, and economic size class. Expansion weights are applied to align the sample aggregates with national Farm Structure Survey (FSS) benchmarks (European Commission, 2020). This approach ensures that FADN accurately reflects the structure of agriculture in each Member State in terms of farm numbers, utilised agricultural area (UAA), and livestock units (LU) (European Commission, 2025).

Within the FADN database, organic farming is captured by a categorical variable with three categories: conventional production, partial organic production, and full organic production. For partially organic production, FADN records the sector in which organic farming is practiced.

The dataset used in this study covers the period 2008–2021 and comprises 18,718 observations from 2,919 Czech agricultural holdings and 121,656 observations from 18,346 German farms. Table A2 in the Appendix presents the development of organic farming adoption as recorded in the FADN database and compares it with trends observed in the full population. Furthermore, Table A3 shows how the FADN database captures both conversion to and reversion from organic farming, as well as the number of farms that had adopted organic farming prior to their first observation in the FADN database. Descriptive statistics for farms in the three organic status categories (conventional, partly organic, and fully organic) for the first year (2008), the midpoint (2015), and the final year (2021) of the analysed period are presented in Tables A4 and A5 in the Appendix.

The panel data–based analysis utilises an unbalanced panel sample. To account for unobserved heterogeneity and potential endogeneity, farms with fewer than three consecutive observations, as well as farms with missing information, are excluded. This results in an unbalanced sample of 1,998 farms, comprising a total of 16,569 observations for the Czech Republic. The structure of this sample for the binary choice model is presented in Table A5 in the Appendix, while Table A8 provides descriptions of the selected variables. In the German sample, this procedure results in an unbalanced dataset of 106,297 observations from 14,029 farms. The structure of the German sample for the binary choice model is presented in Table A6 in the Appendix, with descriptions of the selected variables reported in Table A9.

3.2. Methods

3.2.1. Bass model

The diffusion of organic farming is described using the Bass model (Bass, 1969). The model is based on the premise that a subset of adopters decides to adopt an innovation independently of others. These innovators base their adoption decisions on the expected future utility of the innovation. Such adoption is characteristic of the early stage of the diffusion process, when the number of adopters remains limited. As the adoption rate increases, subsequent adopters are increasingly influenced by the decisions and observed experiences of previous adopters. Consequently, imitative forces become more prominent, leading to an acceleration of the adoption rate. The diffusion trajectory described by the Bass model is therefore S-shaped (Bass, 1969; Mahler & Rodgers, 1999).

The Bass model thus assumes that the probability of adopting an innovation at time t depends on two forces: one that is independent of the number of previous adopters and another that is positively influenced by them. In the model, the first force, often referred to as external influence, is captured by the coefficient of innovation, denoted by p , while the second force, known as internal influence, is captured by the coefficient of imitation, denoted by q . In hazard function notation, the model is expressed as follows (Bass, 1969):

$$\frac{f(t)}{1-F(t)} = p + qF(t), \quad (1)$$

where $f(t)$ is the density function of adoption at time t and $F(t)$ is the corresponding cumulative function. Assuming $F(0) = 0$ integration over time yields the cumulative adoption function:

$$F(t) = \frac{1 - e^{-(p+q)t}}{1 + \frac{q}{p}e^{-(p+q)t}}. \quad (2)$$

Bass et al. (1994) provide a generalized version of the Bass model which allows to include variables that play an important role in adoption, such as prices or subsidies. This Generalized Bass model is defined as:

$$\frac{f(t)}{1 - F(t)} = [p + qF(t)]x(t), \quad (3)$$

where $x(t)$ is called market effort.

Alternatively, the Bass model can be expressed in the cumulative adoption domain. In this study, the following notation is employed (Simpson et al., 2019):

$$n_t = p(M - N_t) + q \frac{N_t}{M}(M - N_t), \quad (4)$$

where n_t is the newly converted agriculture area to organic farming at time t , N_t is the cumulative agricultural area under organic farming at time t , M is the maximum potential agricultural area that can be converted to organic farming, p is the coefficient of innovation and q is the coefficient of imitation.

The cumulative agricultural area under organic farming can be obtained as (Simpson et al., 2019):

$$N_t = M \left(\frac{1 - e^{-(p+q)t}}{1 + \frac{q}{p}e^{-(p+q)t}} \right). \quad (5)$$

The model in Eq. (4) can also be extended to the Generalized Bass model:

$$n_t = \left\{ p(M - N_t) + q \frac{N_t}{M}(M - N_t) \right\} (1 + \beta \mathbf{X}_t), \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{X}_t is a vector of external influencing variables and β is a vector of parameters.

The Bass model is thus a special case of the Generalized Bass model. When no external influencing variables are included, or when these variables remain constant over time, the Generalized Bass model reduces to the standard Bass model (Bass et al., 1994; Simpson et al., 2019). Model parameters are estimated using nonlinear least squares (NLS), with positivity ensured through exponential reparameterization. Two alternative specifications are considered, in which M is treated as either exogenous or endogenous (Massiani & Gohs, 2015). All estimations are performed using Stata 18.

3.2.2. Binary choice models

Although the Bass model is widely used to describe and forecast the diffusion of innovations, it provides only limited insights into the microeconomic processes underlying organic farming adoption. This study, therefore, also employs binary choice modelling², following the widespread research on agricultural technology adoption.

The binary panel-data choice model describing the probability of farming under the organic agriculture regime can be specified as follows:

$$\Pr(Y_{it} = 1 | \mathbf{X}_{it}, c_i, \beta) = \Phi(\mathbf{X}'_{it}\beta + c_i). \quad (7)$$

² An ordered probit specification was initially considered. However, due to the highly unbalanced distribution of the dependent variable, with only about 2.4% of observations falling into the partly organic category in the Czech sample and 1.5% in the German sample, the model does not achieve convergence.

where Y_{it} is a dummy variable indicating whether the i -th farm ($i = 1, \dots, N$) operates under organic farming ($Y_{it} = 1$) at time t ($t = 1, \dots, T$), \mathbf{X}_{it} is a vector of determinants of the production under organic agriculture regime, c_i represents unobserved farm-specific effect, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is a vector of the parameters to be estimated, and $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function (Cruz-Gonzalez et al., 2017).

To capture heterogeneity in panel data, this study employs the within-between random effects (WBRE) model proposed by Bell and Jones (2015). The WBRE specification extends Mundlak's approach, which addresses the correlation between regressors and individual effects in random-effects models. Mundlak (1978) augmented the random-effects specification by including pseudo-fixed effects (the group means of the time-varying variables). Building on this idea, Bell and Jones (2015) replace the original time-varying variables (x_{it}) with their group-mean centring ($\tilde{x}_{it} = x_{it} - \bar{x}_i$), where \bar{x}_i denotes the group mean of x_{it} computed over the time periods with a complete set of data. More specifically, $\bar{x}_i = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T s_{it} x_{it}}{T_i}$, where $s_{it} = 1$ if, and only if, both the regressors and the regressand are fully observed (Wooldridge, 2019).

This approach allows the within and between effects to be clearly separated, in contrast to Mundlak's device, where the contextual effect represents the difference between within and between effects. Moreover, it provides more stable estimates by mitigating collinearity between the original variables and their group means through group-mean centring³.

The employed WBRE probit model is specified as follows:

$$\Pr(Y_{it} = 1 | \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_{it}, \bar{\mathbf{X}}_i, \mathbf{Z}_i, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}) = \Phi(\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_{it}' \boldsymbol{\beta}_W + \bar{\mathbf{X}}_i' \boldsymbol{\beta}_B + \mathbf{Z}_i' \boldsymbol{\gamma} + a_i), \quad (8)$$

where a_i is a time-invariant unobservable component $a_i \sim N(0, \sigma_a^2)$, \mathbf{Z}_i is a vector of time-invariant variables, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ are vectors of parameters. The vectors $\boldsymbol{\beta}_W$ represents within effects (identical to the coefficients in fixed effects models), while $\boldsymbol{\beta}_B$ captures between effects. That is, in the WBRE model, the within and between effects are explicitly and clearly separated, in contrast to Mundlak's specification.

Table 1 provides a detailed description of the variables and their alternative specifications considered in the panel data probit models. Descriptive statistics for these variables are presented in Tables A10–A13 in the Appendix. Given the presence of outliers in the data, the variables were winsorised at the 1st and 99th percentiles. The dependent variable is constructed based on the definition of an organic farmer as one who allocates at least a portion of their inputs to organic production (Jaime et al., 2016, p. 1121). In the FADN dataset for the period 2008–2021, the conversion period is already considered part of organic production⁴.

The selection of variables is informed by previous research, including Bojnec and Fertő (2025), Kremmydas et al. (2023), Jaime et al. (2016), and Latruffe and Nauges (2014). Following these studies, additional variables are also considered, including utilised agricultural area; differences in wheat and milk yields between organic and conventional farms; differences in fertiliser and pesticide expenditure per hectare between organic and conventional farms; expected subsidy gains; and price premium variables, computed from the FADN dataset as price differences between organic and conventional farms for wheat and milk. However, the coefficients of these variables did not reach statistical significance in any of the model specifications, either in the Czech Republic or in Germany.

The model in Eq. (8) is estimated using the maximum likelihood (ML) method with robust standard errors. A Wald test is employed to examine the joint significance of the regression coefficients, thereby

³ The advantages of the WBRE model over the fixed-effects model, the random-effects model, and Mundlak's random-effects specification are summarised in Bell et al. (2019) and Schmid et al. (2023).

⁴ FADN introduced a more detailed indicator that distinguishes the conversion period from the subsequent regime in 2014.

providing validation of the estimation results. In the context of Mundlak’s device, the Wald test serves as an alternative to the Hausman test (Wooldridge, 2019). To address potential endogeneity in the explanatory variables, a control-function approach is applied, using two-period lags and year dummies as instruments in the first-stage regression (Slijper et al., 2021).

Table 1 Variables employed in the prediction of the likelihood to convert to organic farming

Variable	Type	Description
Farm level		
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	B	1 for organic farming management, 0 otherwise
x_ECONOMIC_SIZE	C	Economic size (SE005)
x_CEREALS_ARABLE	C	Share of cereals on total arable land (SE035/SE025)
x_COWS_TLU	C	Share of cows on total livestock unit (SE085/SE080)
x_RENTED_LAND	C	Share of rented land (SE030/SE025)
x_RENTAL_PRICE	C	Rental price of agricultural land (SE485/SE436)
x_LABOUR_INTENSITY	C	Labour input per 100 hectares (SE010/(SE025/100))
x_FIXED_ASSETS	C	Fixed assets per hectare (deflated SE441/SE025), ipi_fix.assets (2010=100)
x_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	C	Debt to assets ratio (SE485/SE436)
x_OA_SHARE	C	Share of other (non-agricultural) output on total output (SE256/SE131)
z_ALTITUDE	B	Dummies for 2 categories: 300 to 600m a.s.l.; above 600m a.s.l.
z_CONSTRAINED_AREA	B	Dummies for 2 categories: natural and other specific constrains (ANC) and mountain less-favoured areas (LFA)
z_FAMILY_FARM	B	1 for family farm (SE015/SE010 = 1), 0 otherwise
z_FARMING_TYPE	B	Dummies for FADN classes of type of farming (TF14)
z_PP_2014–2021	B	1 for the Common Agricultural Policy programming period 2014–2020
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE	B	Dummies for FADN’s ES6 categories: 3 represents Standard Output (SO) 25,000–<50,000 EUR; 4: 50,000–<100,000 EUR; 5: 100,000–<500,000 EUR; and 6: ≥ 500,000 EUR.
Regional level		
x_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	C	Number of organic farms in NUTS2 regions
Country level		
x_MARKET_SHARE	C	Organic share of total retail sales based on FIBL

Source: own processing

Note: B is a binary variable, C is a continuous variable

Based on the estimated model, average partial effects (APEs) are computed with respect to the random effects by integrating over their distribution (Bland & Cook, 2018). The APE captures the average change in the probability of adopting organic farming resulting from a one-unit change in a continuous explanatory variable, or from a discrete shift from the reference category in the case of categorical variables.

To examine whether the determinants of organic farming adoption vary across different stages of the diffusion process, the probit model is also estimated using cross-sectional data for the years 2008, 2015, and 2021. The models are estimated by ML with robust standard errors and evaluated using the Wald test. In addition, the analysis examines whether these determinants differ between field crop and livestock production systems. Field crop production is defined using the FADN TF14 classification and includes the following farm types: TF15 (specialist cereals, oilseeds, and protein crops), TF16 (specialist other field crops), TF60 (mixed crops), and TF80 (mixed crops and livestock). Livestock production comprises TF45 (specialist milk), TF48 (specialist sheep and goats), TF49 (specialist cattle), and TF70 (mixed livestock).

A robustness check employs the strategy proposed by Wooldridge (2019) for unbalanced panels, in which unobserved heterogeneity is modelled as a function of the number of time periods (yearly observations) for each farm and its interactions with the group means of the time-varying variables:

$$E(c_i|\mathbf{w}_i) = \sum_{r=1}^T \psi_r 1[T_i = r] + \sum_{r=1}^T 1[T_i = r] \cdot \bar{\mathbf{X}}_i \xi_r, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{w}_i is a vector of known functions of $\{(s_{it}, s_{it} \mathbf{X}_{it}) : t = 1, \dots, T\}$, r denotes the number of periods (years) observed for the i -th farm in the dataset.

Given that the literature employs different approaches to analyse the likelihood of conversion to organic farming using FADN data, this study also follows the approach of Latruffe and Nauges (2014) as part of a robustness check. In their adoption model, a farm that converts to organic farming is included in the sample only once. Assuming that the conversion decision is made at least one year prior to adoption, and to mitigate reverse causality, the selected observation corresponds to the year preceding conversion. For consistency, and to avoid repeated observations over time, non-adopting farms are also included only once in the final sample, based on a random draw.

This approach reduces the dataset to 637 observations for the Czech Republic, of which 79 correspond to organic farms. In Germany, the resulting sample consists of 2,658 farms, including 324 organic farms. At the same time, this approach allows for the inclusion of variables that are clearly influenced by organic farming practices; these variables are described in Table 2⁵.

Table 2 Variables employed in the prediction of the likelihood to convert to organic farming

Variable	Type	Description
x_FERTILISERS_HA	C	Expenditure per hectare in fertilisers (SE295/SE025)
x_PESTICIDES_HA	C	Expenditure per hectare in pesticides (SE300/SE025)
x_LIVESTOCK_DENSITY	C	Livestock units per hectare (SE080/SE025)
x_MFP	C	Multifactor productivity measured as total output divided total input (SE131/SE270)
x_ENVI_SUBSIDY_SHARE	C	Share of environmental payments in total subsidies excluding on investment (SE621/SE605)
x_EXPEC_SUBSIDY_GAINS	C	Expected subsidy gains from conversion to organic farming, calculated as the difference between total subsidies excluding investment subsidies per hectare (SE605/SE025) in organic farms and total subsidies per hectare in conventional farms
x_EXPECTED_WHEAT_PRICE_PREMIUM	C	Difference in wheat price between organic and conventional farm

Source: own processing

Note: C is a continuous variable

The pooled probit model of conversion to organic farming is estimated using the maximum likelihood method with robust standard errors. All statistical analyses are conducted using Stata 18.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Organic farming in the Czech Republic

The development of organic farming in the Czech Republic began in the 1990s, when the first three farms, covering a total area of 480 hectares, started operating under organic management, inspired by the ideas of traditional organic practitioners from Western Europe. Prior to 1989, the development of organic farming was constrained by social, political, and economic conditions associated with the Soviet system (Zagata, 2010).

As a result of broader societal changes and the introduction of financial incentives, a further 129 farms adopted organic farming as early as 1991, increasing the area of agricultural land under organic management to 17,507 hectares (0.4% of agricultural land in the Czech Republic) (see Figure 1 and

⁵ The descriptive statistics of these variables are presented in Tables A14–A17 in the Appendix.

Table A1 in the Appendix). However, subsidies were discontinued by the new liberal government at the end of 1992. In the absence of policy support and sufficient consumer awareness, the official organic label was unfamiliar to most consumers leading to the stagnation of the Czech organic sector until 1998. In that year, a targeted subsidy scheme in the form of area-based payments for organic farmers was reintroduced, alongside the establishment of a national inspection and certification agency (Urban, 2012; Zagata, 2010). This support for renewed policy was associated with a more than threefold increase in organically managed agricultural land, which reached 71,621 hectares (1.7% of agricultural land in the Czech Republic) and was managed by 348 organic farms.

Figure 1 Number of organic farms and share of agricultural land under organic management in the Czech Republic

Source: Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic (2025)

Growing interest in organic farming was among the factors contributing to the adoption of the Act on Organic Farming (Act No. 242/2000 Coll.) in 1999, which replaced the existing Methodological Instruction from 1993 (Moschitz & Stolze, 2010). Policymakers also sought to modify the structure of land use under organic management, which had been dominated by permanent grassland (86.7%). From 1999 onward, area-based payments were differentiated in favour of arable land and, in particular, permanent crops, with vegetables and specialised herbs included from 2001 (Šejnohová et al., 2015).

In 2004, the Action Plan of the Czech Republic for the Development of Organic Farming until 2010 was approved, setting a target of achieving approximately a 10% share of organically farmed land by 2010 (Moschitz & Stolze, 2010). At the same time, organic farming began to be supported through agri-environmental measures under the Horizontal Rural Development Plan, resulting in a substantial increase in subsidy payment rates, ranging from approximately 10% for permanent grassland to up to 250% for permanent crops (Šejnohová et al., 2015). For farmers, this represented an average increase in support of about 24%, as shown in Figure 2. Organic farmers were also granted bonus points when applying for funding under the Operational Programme Agriculture.

Figure 2 Average subsidies payment for organic farming

Source: Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic (2025)

Note: The average subsidy per hectare is calculated based on the volume of subsidies disbursed until 2003 and the volume of subsidies requested from 2004 onwards. Since subsidies are paid in Czech koruna (CZK), the average level is also presented in CZK. The average subsidy rate, therefore, also reflects the exchange rate applied.

During the first decade of the 21st century, organic farming expanded considerably in the Czech Republic, both in terms of land area and the number of farms. By 2010, organically managed land accounted for 10.6% of total agricultural land, and the number of organic farms had reached 3,517. By contrast, the structure of land use changed only marginally. Permanent grassland remained dominant, accounting for 82.4% of organically managed land, followed by arable land (12.2%). Cereals and fodder crops were the primary crops grown on arable land, while cattle farming dominated livestock production. Organic farming was primarily concentrated in mountainous and upland areas.

Despite an increase in the number of processors, which rose to 404 by 2010 (Figure 3), a substantial proportion of organic output continued to be sold through conventional markets or exported abroad (Hrabalová et al., 2011), and organic products accounted for only 0.6% of total retail sales (FiBL, 2025). To support domestic consumption, which amounted to EUR 5.7 per capita per year in 2010, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic launched an information campaign aimed at promoting organic products and organic farming to the public (FiBL, 2025; Zagata, 2010).

At the end of 2010, the Czech government adopted the Action Plan of the Czech Republic for the Development of Organic Farming for the period 2011–2015, which set a target of achieving a 15% share of total agricultural land under organic management, alongside increasing the market share of organic food to 3%. During this period, organic farming was supported through agri-environmental measures under the Rural Development Programme 2007–2013, prepared in accordance with Council Regulation (EC) No. 1698/2005 on support for rural development from the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). This programme resulted in increases in per-hectare subsidy payment rates of 21% for arable land, 78% for permanent grassland, and 91% for permanent crops. Organic farmers were also granted bonus points in the evaluation of project applications under several other measures of the Rural Development Programme, including support for young farmers, the modernization of agricultural holdings, the processing of agricultural and food products, diversification into non-agricultural activities, and support for rural tourism (Šejniová et al., 2015).

Figure 3 Number of organic processors and organic products share of total retail sales

Source: FiBL (2025)

Despite considerable expansions in agriculture, during the period 2011–2015, stagnation was observed in both the number of organic farms and the area of agricultural land under organic management (Figure 1). In 2015, a total of 4,115 farms operated under organic farming practices, accounting for 11.7% of agricultural land. The market share of organic products increased only marginally, to 0.8%.

The subsequent programme document, the Rural Development Programme 2014–2020, adopted pursuant to Article 29 of Regulation (EU) No. 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council on support for rural development by the EAFRD, separated support for organic farming from agri-environmental measures and introduced differentiated payment rates for the conversion period and the period of full organic management. The programme also increased differentiation across crop types and restricted eligibility for support to closed organic farms (i.e., those without concurrent conventional crop production). As shown in Figure 2, these changes did not result in a substantial change in the average subsidy level. Building on previous programmes, preferential treatment of organic farms in the scoring of applications continued under the investment measures of the Rural Development Programme.

In addition to subsidies, governmental support also focused on research, knowledge transfer, consultancy, education, and promotion within the framework of the Czech Action Plan for the Development of Organic Farming 2016–2020, approved in 2015. This Action Plan aimed to enhance the viability of organic farms, increase the consumption of organic products, and strengthen functional cooperation across the entire supply chain (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2016). Building consumer trust and improving consumer awareness of organic farming were identified as key prerequisites for the further development of the organic food market. In 2019, the project Support for Organic Food and Organic Farming Products was launched with the objective of expanding general knowledge and public awareness of organic food and organic farming (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2021).

This policy framework contributed to achieving the targeted 15% share of agricultural land under organic management, increasing the number of organic processors to 852 (representing a 52.7% increase compared to 2015), and raising the market share of organic products to 1.8% in 2020 (Figure 3). However, permanent grassland remained dominant, accounting for 82.1% of organically managed

land, while arable land represented 16.7% of the land-use structure. On arable land, cereal production, particularly wheat, prevailed. In organic livestock production, beef cattle farming remained dominant, followed by sheep farming (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2021).

In 2020, a new Action Plan was approved, setting the objective of achieving a 22% share of agricultural land under organic management in the Czech Republic by 2027, with arable land accounting for 30% and organic food representing 4% of total food and beverage consumption. These targets are to be pursued through continued support for research, knowledge transfer, market development (including public procurement and public catering), promotion of organic products, and education. Since 2023, organic farming has been supported under the CAP Strategic Plan. The new programming period for 2023–2027 has reintroduced support for the coexistence of organic and conventional farming, subject to the conditions laid down in Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council, and has increased subsidy support for most crops, with some exceptions (e.g., grass seed production). The average subsidy level increased by 10% in 2023 compared with 2022 and continued to grow in the following year by a further 6.8% (see Figure 2). The Strategic Plan also maintains preferential treatment for organic farmers in the evaluation of applications under investment measures (Hlaváčková et al., 2025a).

Interest in organic farming in the Czech Republic has continued to grow, accompanied by gradual, albeit modest, changes in the structure of production. In 2024, a total of 5,565 organic farms operated on 604,803 hectares of agricultural land, representing 17.1% of total agricultural land. Organic farming remained primarily concentrated in mountainous and upland areas. However, the share of permanent grassland declined slightly to 78.9% of organically managed land, while arable land accounted for 20.1%, with cereals and fodder crops predominating. In livestock production, cattle farming dominated, followed by poultry farming. Demand for organic products has been increasing; however, more than 50% of this demand has been met by imported organic food. For Czech organic farms, marketing therefore remains a challenge, and a large share of products continues to be sold through conventional markets (Hlaváčková et al., 2025a; Hlaváčková et al., 2025b).

4.1.1. Diffusion of organic farming in the Czech Republic

The diffusion of organic farming can be characterized using several indicators, including the number of organic farms, the area of organic farmland, and organic output. This study focuses on the area of organic farmland and employs the Bass model to predict annual new adoptions, measured as land converted to organic farming.

Tables 3 and 4 present the results of the Bass model estimation, with exogenous adoption potential defined as the share of total agricultural land that can be converted to organic farming. The results are sensitive to the a priori assumed level of adoption potential. While the innovation coefficient (p) is consistently positive and statistically significant, the imitation coefficient (q) is statistically significant only at low levels of adoption potential. At higher levels of adoption potential, the models do not exhibit a statistically significant imitation effect, suggesting that farmers convert to organic farming independently of previous adopters. Only under the assumption of a 25% adoption potential does the Bass model indicate that, following a relatively slow initial adoption phase, diffusion accelerates due to imitation effects.

Table 3 Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990)

A.potential	25%			30%			40%			50%		
	Coef.	Std.err	P> t									
p	0.019	0.008	0.015	0.017	0.006	0.009	0.013	0.005	0.006	0.011	0.004	0.005
q	0.050	0.023	0.025	0.032	0.020	0.108	0.016	0.018	0.357	0.009	0.017	0.573
R2	0.512			0.504			0.493			0.490		
Adj.R2	0.287			0.473			0.462			0.458		
RMSE	18.315			18.571			18.760			18.824		

A.potential	60%			70%			80%			90%		
	Coef.	Std.err	P> t									
p	0.009	0.003	0.004	0.008	0.003	0.004	0.007	0.002	0.003	0.006	0.002	0.003
q	0.005	0.016	0.730	0.003	0.016	0.842	0.002	0.016	0.924	0.000	0.016	0.987
R2	0.488			0.488			0.487			0.487		
Adj.R2	0.456			0.456			0.455			0.455		
RMSE	18.852			18.866			18.874			18.878		

Source: own processing

Note: UAA is assumed to remain constant at the 2024 level.

The results suggest limited evidence of word-of-mouth effects or experience spillovers from neighbouring farms in driving conversion to organic farming in the Czech Republic. This interpretation is supported by a comparison of coefficients of variation at the national and NUTS2 levels over the period 2007–2024, which indicates that conversion occurred across regions without strong regional concentration. While the nationwide coefficient of variation is 0.63, NUTS2 values range from 0.19 (Central Moravia) to 0.43 (Central Bohemia).

Table 4 Bass model with adoption potential as 100% UAA – the Czech Republic (data from 1990)

	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	Coef.
p	0.006	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.010
q	0.000	0.016	0.999	-0.030	0.030
R2	0.487				
Adj.R2	0.455				
RMSE	18.878				

Generalized Bass Model					
	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	Coef.
p	0.004	0.001	0.000	0.003	0.005
β_In_OF_SUBSIDY	0.127	0.009	0.000	0.107	0.146
R2	0.214				
Adj.R2	0.188				
RMSE	17.033				

Source: own processing

Note: UAA is assumed to remain constant at the 2024 level. The generalized Bass model is based on data from 1993 to 2022 due to the unavailability of data on organic farming subsidies in earlier periods. Ln_OF_SUBSIDY represents the logarithm of the average organic farming subsidy per hectare (CZK/ha).

Figures 4–5 and Tables B1–B10 in the Appendix present a simulation of organic farming adoption up to 2030. While Figure 4 presents a simulation based on a plausible conversion potential of 25% of agricultural land, Figure 5 illustrates a theoretical maximum scenario, assuming full conversion of agricultural land at its 2024 level.

Regardless of the assumed level of adoption potential, the simulations indicate that the target of converting 25% of agricultural land will not be achieved by 2030, ceteris paribus. By that year, adoption is projected to reach between 702,039 and 720,178 hectares, corresponding to approximately 20% of agricultural land. The root mean squared errors (RMSEs), presented in Tables 3–4, indicate that the prediction error increases with higher assumed levels of adoption potential⁶.

⁶ Table B11 and Figure B1 in the Appendix present additional results of the Bass model with endogenous adoption potential. However, the estimated adoption potential is close to the cumulative adoption observed in the final year, as noted in previous research (Massiani & Gohs, 2015).

Figure 4 Cumulative adoption of organic farming according to Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 25% of agricultural area)

Source: own processing

Figure 5 Cumulative adoption of organic farming according to Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 100% of agricultural area)

Source: own processing

Furthermore, the results of the Generalized Bass model indicate that subsidy payments accelerate the diffusion of organic farming by strengthening the innovation-driven component of the adoption process. At the same time, the inclusion of subsidies eliminates the imitation effect.

Compared with the standard Bass model, the Generalized Bass model exhibits the lowest root mean squared error. Projections based on this specification suggest that organically managed land will reach 720,178 hectares by 2030, corresponding to approximately 20.4% of total agricultural land—the highest predicted value among the alternative model specifications. However, this projection assumes

that the average subsidy rate remains constant at its 2024 level and does not account for potential changes in subsidy schemes, shifts in land-use structure, or exchange rate fluctuations.

4.1.2. Organic farming adoption in the Czech Republic

The analysis of organic farming adoption rests on the assumption that adoption decisions precede observed adoption by at least one year. Accordingly, the probit model includes market share and the number of organic farms in the NUTS2 region with a one-period lag. This specification assumes that agricultural producers base their decisions on observed demand for organic products and the observed behaviour of neighbouring farms.

Table 5 reports the estimation results of the panel data probit model using the within-between random-effects (WBRE) specification. Among the higher-level variables (regional and country-level variables), which are presented first, only the coefficient for market share is reported, as the coefficient for the number of organic farms at the NUTS2 level is not statistically significant, even at the 10% level. Within-farm effects for continuous variables are then presented, followed by between-farm effects and coefficients for binary variables. Finally, Table 5 reports the random-effects statistics and the results of the Wald test.

The results indicate substantial unobserved heterogeneity among Czech farms, supporting the use of a panel data specification over a pooled model. The joint significance test of Mundlak's device (group means) rejects the null hypothesis that the group means are statistically insignificant in the corrected random-effects specification. This result indicates that the WBRE specification is appropriate.

The Wald test further confirms the overall statistical significance of the model at the conventional significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. In addition, the Wald test for endogeneity fails to reject the null hypothesis of exogeneity ($\alpha = 0.05$), supporting the use of the model estimates without instrumental variables. As shown in Table 5, the model correctly classifies 90% of observations (using a 0.5 probability threshold) as organic or conventional farms⁷.

⁷ Tables B12–B13 in the Appendix B report additional estimates based on non-winsorised data. The results are qualitatively similar to those obtained from the winsorised samples.

Table 5 Probit model estimates – the Czech Republic

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_In_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.678	0.307	0.027	0.076	1.280
Within					
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.177	0.336	0.599	-0.836	0.483
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.029	0.044	0.505	-0.114	0.056
x_In_COWS_TLU	-0.198	0.102	0.053	-0.398	0.003
x_In_RENTED_LAND	0.173	0.083	0.038	0.010	0.336
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.357	0.310	0.250	-0.964	0.251
Between					
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.652	0.281	0.020	-1.202	-0.103
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE	-1.469	0.202	0.000	-1.864	-1.074
x_In_COWS_TLU	-0.161	0.192	0.401	-0.538	0.215
x_In_RENTED_LAND	0.351	0.187	0.061	-0.016	0.718
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-2.211	0.548	0.000	-3.285	-1.138
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	1.661	0.635	0.009	0.417	2.905
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	3.068	0.888	0.001	1.327	4.809
z_TF14_16	1.016	0.590	0.085	-0.141	2.173
z_TF14_20	0.592	2.106	0.779	-3.535	4.719
z_TF14_35	0.036	1.935	0.985	-3.756	3.829
z_TF14_36	3.684	1.233	0.003	1.267	6.100
z_TF14_45	2.584	0.831	0.002	0.955	4.212
z_TF14_48	4.317	0.988	0.000	2.379	6.254
z_TF14_49	3.649	0.767	0.000	2.146	5.152
z_TF14_50	2.824	1.147	0.014	0.576	5.073
z_TF14_60	3.604	1.126	0.001	1.397	5.810
z_TF14_70	3.226	0.946	0.001	1.373	5.080
z_TF14_80	2.628	0.736	0.000	1.185	4.072
YEAR_2009	-0.305	0.208	0.141	-0.712	0.101
YEAR_2010	1.198	0.267	0.000	0.674	1.722
YEAR_2011	1.491	0.298	0.000	0.908	2.075
YEAR_2012	1.400	0.291	0.000	0.830	1.970
YEAR_2013	1.369	0.290	0.000	0.801	1.936
YEAR_2014	1.328	0.280	0.000	0.780	1.876
YEAR_2015	0.939	0.285	0.001	0.381	1.498
YEAR_2016	0.401	0.252	0.112	-0.094	0.895
YEAR_2017	0.246	0.218	0.259	-0.181	0.672
YEAR_2018	0.189	0.205	0.355	-0.212	0.591
YEAR_2020	0.121	0.055	0.027	0.014	0.229
_const.	-4.046	2.985	0.175	-9.897	1.806
Insig2u	3.416	0.101		3.218	3.614
sigma_u	5.519	0.279		4.998	6.093
Rho	0.968	0.003		0.962	0.974
Wald chi2(35)	156.170		0.000		
Log likelihood	-1577.299				
Wald ch2(5): Mundlak devices	63.710		0.000		
Wald chi2(2): LABOUR_INTENSITY_res, ESIZE_res	0.360		0.837		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	89.565				
Number of observations	16,569				
Number of farms	1,998				

Source: own processing

Note: The coefficient of x_In_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1) was not statistically significant at 10% level (p-value = 0.214).

Table 6 reports the average partial effects. The positive effect of market share, statistically significant at the 5% level, is consistent with the notion that growing demand supports conversion to organic farming in the Czech Republic (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2021). Market share exhibits a strong correlation with the number of processors (correlation coefficient of 0.94), suggesting that marketing opportunities may play an important role in the conversion to organic farming. The between-farm effects, which capture time-invariant differences across farms, indicate that, at the 10%

significance level, conversion to organic farming is significantly influenced by economic size, specialisation, land ownership, and labour intensity. In addition, farm location plays an important role.

Table 6 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit model – the Czech Republic

	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.021	0.010	0.033	0.002	0.041
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.006	0.011	0.601	-0.026	0.015
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.001	0.001	0.504	-0.004	0.002
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.006	0.003	0.057	-0.013	0.000
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.005	0.003	0.051	0.000	0.011
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.011	0.010	0.261	-0.031	0.008
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.020	0.008	0.013	-0.036	-0.004
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.046	0.005	0.000	-0.056	-0.036
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.005	0.006	0.385	-0.016	0.006
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.011	0.006	0.048	0.000	0.022
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.069	0.015	0.000	-0.099	-0.040
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.049	0.019	0.010	0.012	0.086
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.104	0.033	0.002	0.039	0.168
z_TF14_16	0.028	0.016	0.076	-0.003	0.058
z_TF14_20	0.016	0.058	0.787	-0.098	0.129
z_TF14_35	0.001	0.049	0.985	-0.095	0.097
z_TF14_36	0.118	0.044	0.008	0.031	0.205
z_TF14_45	0.077	0.024	0.002	0.029	0.125
z_TF14_48	0.145	0.037	0.000	0.072	0.218
z_TF14_49	0.117	0.025	0.000	0.067	0.167
z_TF14_50	0.085	0.037	0.022	0.012	0.159
z_TF14_60	0.115	0.041	0.005	0.035	0.195
z_TF14_70	0.100	0.030	0.001	0.041	0.160
z_TF14_80	0.079	0.021	0.000	0.038	0.119

Source: own processing

Note: The partial effects for z-variables represent a discrete change from the baseline level (dummy variable=0).

The average partial effect of economic size is negative (–2 percentage points, p.p.), indicating that larger farms have a lower probability of converting to organic farming. This pattern is consistent with national statistics based on utilised agricultural area, which show that organic farms are predominantly represented among holdings smaller than 500 hectares, accounting for 59% in 2021 and 88% in 2008 (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2025). It is also worth noting that economic size and land area are strongly correlated (correlation coefficient: 0.84).

Farms with a high share of cereals on arable land are less likely to convert to organic farming, likely due to greater exposure to yield risk and a stronger dependence on intensive input use, both of which reduce the relative attractiveness of organic production. Higher labour intensity is likewise associated with a lower likelihood of conversion, reducing the probability by approximately 6.9 p.p., ceteris paribus. Consistent with this finding, the average labour intensity of conventional farms is 20.8 AWU per hectare, compared with 4.8 AWU per hectare among organic farms, although labour intensity varies substantially across production types.

The results further indicate that farm location in higher-altitude areas increases the likelihood of conversion. Farms situated at altitudes between 300 and 600 meters above sea level exhibit an approximately 4.9 p.p. higher probability of conversion, while those located above 600 meters show an increase of about 10.4 p.p., compared with farms below 300 meters.

Within-farm effect estimates, capturing temporal dynamics, indicate that changes in the share of cows in total livestock units and in the share of rented land are significantly associated with the likelihood of adopting organic farming at the 10% significance level. These findings suggest that conversion is linked to structural changes within farms over time. In particular, a higher degree of specialisation in dairy production is associated with an approximately 0.6 p.p. lower probability of conversion. Although organic farming in the Czech Republic is more prevalent in livestock production, it is primarily oriented towards beef cattle rather than dairy farming. In contrast, the probability of conversion increases with a higher share of rented land, suggesting that farms may be transitioning towards more extensive production systems requiring larger utilised agricultural areas, facilitated through land rental arrangements. This pattern may reflect land market rigidities or uncertainty.

While descriptive FADN statistics indicate a higher prevalence of organic farming among family farms—with family farms accounting for 45% to 61% of organic holdings over the period 2008–2021—the econometric results provide no statistical evidence supporting this pattern. The model also does not support the hypothesis that organic farms exhibit a lower debt-to-assets ratio (0.17 on average) compared with conventional farms (0.20 on average). Finally, no statistically significant effect of capital intensity on the adoption of organic farming is identified, despite capital intensity being substantially lower among organic producers, as documented in Table A8 in Appendix A.

The WBRE probit model further reveals heterogeneity in the probability of organic farming adoption over time and across types of farming. Potential changes in the effects of the analysed variables over the study period are examined by estimating probit models using cross-sectional data for the years 2008, 2015, and 2021. The estimation results are presented in Table 7. The Wald test confirms the overall statistical significance of the models, and the proportion of correctly predicted observations ranges between 89.8% and 91.6%, slightly exceeding the predictive accuracy of the WBRE model.

The average partial effects of the cross-sectional models are presented in Table 8. The effect of economic size is statistically significant only in 2015 and 2021, with the magnitude of the negative effect increasing over time from approximately 3.1 to 4.6 p.p. This suggests that, over time, farms with larger economic size are less likely to convert to organic farming.

The cross-sectional models further identify a negative association between the share of cereals in arable land and the probability of conversion to organic farming, consistent with the panel data results. An increase in the share of cereals is associated with a reduction in the probability of conversion of approximately 1.1 to 2.2 p.p., with the magnitude of this effect strengthening over time. A similar pattern is observed for the share of dairy cows in total livestock units, although this effect does not reach conventional levels of statistical significance in 2021. Overall, the findings indicate that a higher degree of farm specialisation is associated with a lower likelihood of conversion to organic farming. This relationship is consistent with the principles of organic agriculture, which emphasize diversified production systems, crop rotations, and the integration of crop and livestock activities as key mechanisms for maintaining soil fertility, reducing reliance on external inputs, and enhancing agroecological resilience.

Table 7 Probit model estimates for 2008, 2015, and 2021 – the Czech Republic

Variable	2008			2015			2021		
	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE				-0.209	0.051	0.000	-0.373	0.059	0.000
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.098	0.030	0.001	-0.097	0.024	0.000	-0.176	0.030	0.000
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.112	0.033	0.001	-0.107	0.038	0.005			
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.223	0.096	0.020						
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.129	0.058	0.027	0.036	0.020	0.073	0.060	0.024	0.013
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.318	0.118	0.007	-0.276	0.084	0.001	-0.586	0.112	0.000
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-0.083	0.039	0.036						
x_ln_OA_SHARE				0.056	0.024	0.021	0.100	0.031	0.001
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.364	0.155	0.019						
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.				0.452	0.168	0.007	0.403	0.235	0.087
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.				0.719	0.225	0.001	0.599	0.291	0.040
z_ANC_other	0.466	0.153	0.002						
z_ANC_mountain	0.603	0.193	0.002						
z_TF14_16	-0.415	0.415	0.317	1.026	0.216	0.000	1.680	0.414	0.000
z_TF14_20	1.170	0.614	0.057	0.544	0.640	0.395			
z_TF14_35	0.318	0.597	0.594	1.075	0.388	0.006	3.127	0.627	0.000
z_TF14_36				1.302	0.310	0.000	2.404	0.545	0.000
z_TF14_45	0.802	0.342	0.019	1.537	0.293	0.000	2.017	0.420	0.000
z_TF14_48	1.313	0.441	0.003	2.371	0.355	0.000	2.512	0.542	0.000
z_TF14_49	1.198	0.252	0.000	1.827	0.190	0.000	2.666	0.378	0.000
z_TF14_50	0.462	0.598	0.440				2.084	0.712	0.003
z_TF14_60	0.891	0.581	0.125	0.789	0.537	0.142	1.862	0.560	0.001
z_TF14_70	0.804	0.361	0.026	1.141	0.329	0.001			
z_TF14_80	0.660	0.224	0.003	0.777	0.193	0.000	1.652	0.376	0.000
_const.	-2.188	0.331	0.000	-1.548	0.548	0.005	-0.803	0.618	0.194
Wald chi2(19/18/16)	200.68		0.000	333.94		0.000	274.61		0.000
Log likelihood	-251.83			-372.18			-249.83		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	91.197			89.824			91.600		
Number of observations	1,271			1,366			1,119		
Number of organic farms	110			255			222		

Source: own processing

The effect of the share of rented land is statistically significant only in 2008, indicating that a greater reliance on rented land is associated with an approximately 2.4 p.p. increase in the probability of conversion to organic farming. Compared with the panel data model, the cross-sectional models also reveal a statistically significant effect of land rental prices. While this effect is negative in 2008, it becomes positive in 2015 and 2021. Since land rent reflects soil quality, these results may suggest that, over time, farms with higher-quality land are increasingly converting to organic farming. This pattern may also reflect changes in land-use structure observed in national statistics, which indicate a shift from permanent grassland towards arable land (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2025).

Consistent with the panel probit model, labour intensity is negatively associated with the probability of conversion to organic farming, with the magnitude of this association increasing over time. In contrast to the panel data model, the cross-sectional analysis reveals a statistically significant effect of the share of other output in total output. Specifically, a higher share of other activities is positively associated with conversion to organic farming. This finding is consistent with descriptive evidence showing that such activities account for a larger proportion of total output among organic farms (8.8%) than among conventional farms (6.0%). These activities encompass a broad range of non-core farm operations, including the processing of farm products (other than milk), contract work, agritourism, renewable energy production, and forestry. The share of these activities in total output serves as a proxy for diversification, which may help mitigate short-term economic risks and thereby facilitate conversion to organic farming (Bojnek & Fertö, 2025).

Table 8 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit models for 2008, 2015, and 2021 – the Czech Republic

Variable	2008			2015			2021		
	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE				-0.031	0.008	0.000	-0.046	0.007	0.000
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.011	0.003	0.001	-0.015	0.003	0.000	-0.022	0.003	0.000
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.012	0.004	0.001	-0.016	0.006	0.004			
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.024	0.010	0.021						
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.014	0.006	0.027	0.005	0.003	0.072	0.007	0.003	0.013
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.034	0.012	0.006	-0.041	0.013	0.001	-0.072	0.013	0.000
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-0.009	0.004	0.039						
x_ln_OA_SHARE				0.008	0.004	0.021	0.012	0.004	0.001
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.039	0.016	0.017						
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.				0.067	0.024	0.005	0.048	0.027	0.070
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.				0.118	0.041	0.004	0.075	0.037	0.042
z_ANC_other	0.052	0.019	0.005						
z_ANC_mountain	0.073	0.028	0.010						
z_TF14_16	-0.037	0.030	0.217	0.195	0.047	0.000	0.207	0.051	0.000
z_TF14_20	0.212	0.159	0.181	0.096	0.130	0.460			
z_TF14_35	0.040	0.086	0.643	0.216	0.095	0.023	0.385	0.075	0.000
z_TF14_36				0.280	0.082	0.001	0.296	0.066	0.000
z_TF14_45	0.116	0.063	0.064	0.314	0.068	0.000	0.248	0.051	0.000
z_TF14_48	0.261	0.128	0.042	0.594	0.086	0.000	0.309	0.066	0.000
z_TF14_49	0.224	0.066	0.001	0.476	0.057	0.000	0.328	0.045	0.000
z_TF14_50	0.062	0.098	0.527				0.257	0.088	0.003
z_TF14_60	0.147	0.132	0.268	0.151	0.124	0.224	0.229	0.067	0.001
z_TF14_70	0.124	0.073	0.089	0.236	0.083	0.004			
z_TF14_80	0.083	0.032	0.009	0.130	0.035	0.000	0.203	0.046	0.000

Source: own processing

The effect of the share of other output is not statistically significant in 2008 but becomes significant in later years, with increasing magnitude. This pattern may suggest that farms with more diversified production structures are better positioned to cope with marketing challenges in the organic market. By contrast, the effect of indebtedness is negative in 2008 but becomes statistically insignificant in subsequent years, a pattern that is also observed for family-farm status.

The statistical significance of the location effect differs across years. While a positive effect of farm location in less-favoured areas (LFAs) is observed in 2008, the influence of location in 2015 and 2021 is instead captured by altitude, with the magnitude of the location-related effect declining over time. This pattern may indicate a gradual shift in the adoption of organic farming towards more productive regions, reflecting the expanding role of organic crop production.

Overall, these findings suggest that the impact of key determinants is not stable over the diffusion process of organic farming, which complicates predictions based on historical data and has important implications for policymakers. In particular, the results highlight the need for flexible and diffusion phase specific policy instruments.

The average partial effects of the type-of-farming dummies further indicate that, across individual years, farms of different production types exhibit varying propensities to convert to organic farming. In particular, farms classified as Type of Farming (TF) 48—specialised sheep and goat farms—and TF 49—specialised cattle farms—show a higher probability of conversion. Over time, however, the probability of adoption also increases among wine producers (TF 35) and fruit producers (TF 36). Indeed, over the observed period, the area under orchards increased by 60%, while the area under vineyards almost tripled (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2025).

The heterogeneity across different types of farming is further reflected in the estimation of separate models for livestock and field crop production. The estimates of these production-specific models in the WBRE specification are presented in Table 9. For both production types, overall model significance is confirmed by the Wald test at the 5% level.

Table 9 Probit model estimates – livestock and field crops production in the Czech Republic

Variable	Livestock production			Field crops production		
	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)				0.695	0.338	0.040
Within						
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE				-0.815	0.322	0.011
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	0.316	0.356	0.375			
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE				-0.001	0.060	0.982
x_ln_COW_TLU	-0.311	0.113	0.006			
x_ln_RENTED_LAND				0.413	0.191	0.030
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY				-0.506	0.460	0.271
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS	0.151	0.069	0.029			
x_ln_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-0.350	0.115	0.002			
Between						
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE				-0.565	0.124	0.000
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	-1.556	0.742	0.036			
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE				-0.727	0.180	0.000
x_ln_COW_TLU	-2.067	0.460	0.000			
x_ln_RENTED_LAND				0.415	0.191	0.030
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY				-0.690	0.254	0.007
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS	0.181	0.229	0.430			
x_ln_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	0.063	0.180	0.726			
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	6.230	2.305	0.007	0.358	0.388	0.356
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	6.646	2.399	0.006	2.313	0.702	0.001
z_ANC_other	0.162	0.481	0.737			
z_ANC_mountain	1.902	0.991	0.055			
z_TF14_48/z_TF14_16				-0.690	0.254	0.007
z_TF14_49/ z_TF14_60				0.358	0.388	0.356
z_TF14_70/ z_TF14_80				2.313	0.702	0.001
YEAR_2009	0.207	0.296	0.485			
YEAR_2010	1.814	0.427	0.000	1.065	0.271	0.000
YEAR_2011	2.594	0.504	0.000	0.605	0.372	0.104
YEAR_2012	2.444	0.502	0.000	0.491	0.423	0.246
YEAR_2013	2.515	0.503	0.000	0.433	0.438	0.323
YEAR_2014	2.317	0.489	0.000	0.406	0.443	0.359
YEAR_2015	2.384	0.513	0.000	-0.129	0.475	0.787
YEAR_2016	1.974	0.469	0.000	-0.995	0.462	0.031
YEAR_2017	1.801	0.468	0.000	-1.202	0.411	0.003
YEAR_2018	1.915	0.464	0.000	-1.130	0.451	0.012
YEAR_2019	2.030	0.467	0.000	-1.048	0.473	0.027
YEAR_2020	2.105	0.478	0.000	-0.813	0.465	0.080
YEAR_2021	1.777	0.472	0.000	-0.822	0.506	0.104
_const.	-6.243	4.907	0.203	-5.889	1.017	0.000
Insig2u	4.024	0.157		2.504	0.224	
sigma_u	7.480	0.586		3.498	0.392	
Rho	0.982	0.003		0.924	0.016	
Wald chi2(25/26)	60.170		0.000	129.170		0.000
Log likelihood	-745.317			-613.904		
Wald chi2(4/4): Mundlak's devices	8.260		0.083	16.920		0.002
Wald chi2(0/2): LABOUR_INTENSITY_res, ESIZE_res				0.190		0.911
Percent. of correctly predicted v.	79.371			89.993		
Number of observations	5,216			9,002		
Number of farms	775			1,216		

Source: own processing

In the field crop production model, the Wald test fails to reject the exogeneity assumption. This test is not performed for the livestock production model, as the potentially endogenous variables, namely economic size and labour intensity, are not statistically significant at the 10% level. Economic size is

also insignificant when specified using categorical variables; none of the dummy variables representing the four considered size classes is significant at the 10% level. Moreover, alternative measures of size, such as the number of workers measured in annual working units (AWU) and utilised agricultural area, are not statistically significant at the 10% level.

In terms of predictive performance, the field crop production model exhibits higher accuracy, correctly predicting 90% of the dependent binary outcomes using a 0.5 threshold, compared with 79% for the livestock production model. However, in contrast to the livestock model, the coefficients of the dummy variables representing the type of farming are statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating differences in the probability of organic farming adoption between specialised and mixed farms.

The determinants of conversion to organic farming differ substantially between livestock and field crop production, as shown in Table 9, not only with respect to production-specific variables such as the share of dairy cows in total livestock units and the share of cereals in arable land. While, in livestock production, the statistically significant determinants (at the 10% level) include fixed assets per UAA, the share of unpaid labour, the debt-to-assets ratio, and location in less-favoured areas (LFAs), in field crop production the significant factors are economic size, the share of rented land, labour intensity, farm location in mountainous areas, and the number of organic farms in the NUTS2 region. This finding suggests that production-specific modelling approaches may be more appropriate than a single common specification when analysing conversion to organic farming, particularly as the prevalence of organic farming increases across different types of production.

Table 10 presents the average partial effects of both models. Focusing on livestock production, specialisation in dairy production, which is measured by the share of dairy cows in total livestock units, is associated with an approximately 7.7 p.p. lower probability of conversion. Farms with a higher level of capital endowment, measured as fixed assets per UAA, also exhibit a lower probability of conversion to organic farming, suggesting that more capital-intensive production structures may face greater barriers to adopting organic practices. By contrast, farms located in LFAs have an approximately 6.5 p.p. higher probability of conversion to organic farming compared with farms situated in more production-favourable areas. This pattern is consistent with the structure of the Czech organic sector, where extensive cattle and sheep production predominates in LFAs (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2025), and indicates a comparative advantage of extensive production systems in these areas.

The within-effects indicate that an increase in the farm debt-to-assets ratio is associated with a slight increase in the probability of conversion to organic farming (0.6 p.p.). This relationship may reflect financial pressure, whereby more indebted farms seek alternative production strategies to stabilize revenues, reduce input intensity, or improve access to agri-environmental support schemes. Conversely, a higher share of dairy cows in total livestock units reduces the probability of conversion, indicating that increasing specialisation in dairy production over time lowers the likelihood of adopting organic farming. The results further suggest that farms facing shortages of external labour—and consequent adjustments in labour structure—exhibit a lower propensity to convert.

In field crop production, the likelihood of conversion is influenced by the presence of organic farms in the surrounding area, measured at the NUTS2 level. Farms located in regions with a higher number of organic producers exhibit an approximately 2 p.p. higher probability of conversion. In contrast to livestock production, this indicates a neighbourhood effect in field crop systems, suggesting that adoption is influenced by the behaviour of nearby producers.

Table 10 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit models – livestock and field crops production in the Czech Republic

Variable	Livestock production			Field crops production		
	APE	Std.err.	P> z	APE	Std.err.	P> z
x_In_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)				0.020	0.009	0.023
Within						
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE				-0.024	0.009	0.012
x_In_FIXED_ASSETS	0.012	0.013	0.376			
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE				0.000	0.002	0.982
x_In_COW_TLU	-0.012	0.004	0.010			
x_In_RENTED_LAND				0.012	0.006	0.039
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY				-0.015	0.013	0.279
x_In_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS	0.006	0.003	0.033			
x_In_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-0.013	0.004	0.002			
Between						
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE				-0.016	0.002	0.000
x_In_FIXED_ASSETS	-0.058	0.024	0.017			
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE				-0.021	0.004	0.000
x_In_COW_TLU	-0.077	0.017	0.000			
x_In_RENTED_LAND				0.012	0.005	0.028
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY				-0.020	0.007	0.004
x_In_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS	0.007	0.009	0.428			
x_In_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	0.002	0.007	0.726			
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.211	0.047	0.000	0.010	0.010	0.308
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.226	0.051	0.000	0.095	0.035	0.007
z_ANC_other	0.008	0.024	0.742			
z_ANC_mountain	0.065	0.033	0.046			

Source: own processing

Consistent with the common model, farms with larger economic size exhibit a lower probability of conversion, and increases in economic size over time further reduce this likelihood. Conversion is also less likely among farms specialising in cereal production, compared with those maintaining more diversified cropping structures. Higher labour intensity similarly reduces the probability of adoption by approximately 2 p.p., *ceteris paribus*. By contrast, farms located at altitudes above 600 meters above sea level exhibit a higher probability of conversion.

Estimates from cross-sectional probit models for livestock and field crop production in 2008 and 2021 (Tables B14–B15 in Appendix B) further indicate that the determinants of organic farming adoption vary over the diffusion process. Across both production types, a consistent pattern is observed only in the strengthening negative effect of economic size.

Taken together, these findings are consistent with national statistics, which indicate that organic farming adoption in the Czech Republic is less prevalent among large farms but more common among farms specialising in cattle and sheep production and located in mountainous and upland areas.

Building on these results, it can be concluded that, within the livestock sector, farms more inclined towards organic farming tend to exhibit lower capital intensity and are more frequently located in less-favoured areas (LFAs). Capital-constrained farms face limited ability to compete with highly intensive conventional production systems. In this context, organic livestock farming—based on extensive grazing—represents a viable alternative, as it relies less on capital-intensive inputs and enables farms to shift away from price-based competition towards differentiated market segments. Moreover, farms in LFAs often face structural disadvantages, such as lower land productivity and limited alternative production opportunities, which further increase the relative attractiveness of organic farming as a strategy for income stabilization.

In field crop production, the number of organic farms within a NUTS2 region appears to be a key determinant. A higher density of organic farms facilitates both formal and informal knowledge exchange, reducing information barriers and transaction costs associated with conversion. It also provides observable evidence of the economic viability of organic production, thereby lowering perceived risks—particularly for more risk-averse farmers. In addition, a higher concentration of organic producers supports the development of specialised infrastructure, including certification services, advisory systems, and processing capacities.

From a policy perspective, these findings highlight the importance of knowledge transfer mechanisms, including formal training programmes, advisory services, and demonstration farms that allow potential adopters to observe organic practices under real production conditions. At the same time, enhancing the productive potential of organic farming through targeted support for research and innovation—particularly in productivity, input efficiency, and adaptation to local agro-climatic conditions—is essential.

Given that limited market access remains a key constraint for the expansion of organic farming in the Czech Republic, policy measures should also focus on strengthening downstream segments of the value chain. In particular, support for the establishment and expansion of processing capacities, including on-farm processing, can increase value added, reduce marketing bottlenecks, and improve the economic viability of organic production.

Demand for organic products is a critical driver of organic farming development. Although subsidies have a strong motivational effect, insufficient demand results in a substantial share of organic production being sold through conventional markets. In the Czech Republic, demand remains relatively low, with organic products accounting for less than 2% of total retail sales, compared with approximately 11% in neighbouring Austria (FiBL, 2025), despite public awareness campaigns. One potential policy response is to expand the provision of organic food in public institutions, such as school catering, as proposed in the Czech Action Plan for the Development of Organic Agriculture 2021–2027 (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2021).

4.1.3. Robustness check of Czech organic farming adoption models

Wooldridge's (2019) corrected random-effects model is estimated as a robustness check of the WBRE model results⁸. The probit model estimates incorporating Wooldridge's (2019) devices are presented in Table 11. Following previous studies (e.g., Slijper et al., 2021), the coefficients on the dummy variables capturing the number of observations and their interactions with group means are not reported. The joint statistical significance of these coefficients is assessed using a Wald test.

Failure to reject the null hypothesis in this regression-based Hausman test at the conventional 5% significance level provides no evidence that the random effects are correlated with the regressors. Moreover, the statistical insignificance of Wooldridge's devices indicates that omitting the unbalanced-panel corrections may yield efficiency gains, thereby supporting the results of the WBRE model.

⁸ As a robustness check, the logit model was also estimated. The results reported in Tables B16–B17 are qualitatively consistent with those obtained from the probit model.

Table 11 Probit model estimates with Wooldridge's (2019) devices – the Czech Republic

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_In_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.694	0.218	0.001	0.267	1.121
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.371	0.240	0.122	-0.841	0.100
x_In_COWS_TLU	-0.140	0.088	0.113	-0.312	0.033
x_In_RENTED_LAND	0.156	0.088	0.075	-0.016	0.329
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.198	0.274	0.470	-0.736	0.339
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	2.030	0.764	0.008	0.533	3.527
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	3.228	0.917	0.000	1.431	5.026
z_ANC_mountain	4.467	0.719	0.000	3.057	5.877
YEAR_2009	-0.346	0.178	0.052	-0.694	0.002
YEAR_2010	1.037	0.189	0.000	0.666	1.408
YEAR_2011	1.326	0.211	0.000	0.913	1.740
YEAR_2012	1.285	0.200	0.000	0.893	1.677
YEAR_2013	1.315	0.203	0.000	0.918	1.712
YEAR_2014	1.243	0.193	0.000	0.865	1.621
YEAR_2015	0.887	0.180	0.000	0.535	1.239
YEAR_2016	0.377	0.152	0.013	0.080	0.674
YEAR_2017	0.250	0.121	0.039	0.013	0.488
_const.	-1.240	5.564	0.824	-12.144	9.665
Insig2u	3.374	0.057		3.263	3.486
sigma_u	5.404	0.154		5.111	5.714
Rho	0.967	0.002		0.963	0.970
Wald chi2(76)	258.760		0.000		
Log likelihood	-1759.317				
Wald chi2(71): CRE parameters – Ti_means	69.990		0.155		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	86.239				
Number of observations	16,569				
Number of farms	1,998				

Source: own processing

Comparing the results of the WBRE probit model (Table 5) with those of the probit model incorporating Wooldridge's correction devices shows that the latter correctly predicts 86% of the dependent variable outcomes, slightly below the predictive accuracy of the WBRE model. Table 12 reports the corresponding average partial effects from Wooldridge's (2019) corrected random-effects model. As in the WBRE specification, market share has a statistically significant effect at the 5% level, although its magnitude is slightly larger in this model.

A statistically significant effect at the 10% level is also identified for the share of rented land, with an average partial effect of approximately 0.6 p.p., closely corresponding to the within effect estimated in the WBRE model. Farms located at higher altitudes similarly exhibit a higher likelihood of organic production. Relative to the WBRE specification, the altitude effect is stronger, amounting to 6.5 and 11.7 p.p., respectively, compared with 4.9 and 10.4 p.p. in the WBRE model. In addition, farms operating in less-favoured areas (LFAs) are more likely to convert to organic farming, although this effect was not statistically significant in the WBRE specification (Table 5).

The average partial effects of economic size, the share of cereals in arable land, and labour intensity exhibit the same signs as in the WBRE model but are not statistically significant at the 10% level, consistent with the within effects estimated in the WBRE specification. Moreover, the Wooldridge model does not yield statistically significant coefficients for the farming-type dummy variables, suggesting that between-farm variation associated with production specialisation is largely absorbed by the model.

Table 12 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit model with Wooldrige's (2019) devices – the Czech Republic

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.025	0.008	0.002	0.009	0.040
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.013	0.009	0.129	-0.030	0.004
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.005	0.003	0.108	-0.011	0.001
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.006	0.003	0.085	-0.001	0.012
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.007	0.010	0.471	-0.026	0.012
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.065	0.028	0.021	0.010	0.120
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.117	0.039	0.002	0.042	0.193
z_ANC_mountain	0.159	0.023	0.000	0.113	0.204

Source: own processing

Table 13 presents the probit model estimates based on the approach of Latruffe and Nauges (2014). Under this framework, observations for organic farms are limited to a single period—the year prior to their identification as organic producers in the FADN database—while observations for conventional farms are likewise restricted to one year. This data structure enables the inclusion of variables that may be subject to reverse causality. The joint significance of the model and its covariates is confirmed by a Wald test at the 5% significance level. The model correctly predicts 90.9% of the dependent variable outcomes.

Table 14 reports the corresponding average partial effects. Expected subsidy gains, defined as the change in total operating subsidies between periods t and $t-1$, are statistically significant at the 5% level. The estimates suggest that a 1% increase in the subsidy premium is associated with an increase of approximately 1.6 p.p. in the probability of conversion to organic farming. Consistent with the Generalized Bass model, subsidies targeted at organic producers increase farmers' incentives to adopt organic practices.

The probability of conversion also increases with a higher share of environmental subsidies in total operating subsidies. These payments are conditional on the adoption of environmentally friendly production practices, including reduced fertiliser and pesticide use, adjustments in livestock intensity, conversion of arable land to permanent grassland, crop rotation measures, and biodiversity-supporting actions⁹. As such, they compensate for additional costs and income foregone associated with environmentally and climate-conscious farming.

Because the analysis considers subsidies received prior to the observed organic status in the FADN database, where farms in the conversion period are already classified as organic, this variable may capture a broader orientation towards environmentally friendly farming practices.

⁹ Payments to LFA are not included.

Table 13 Pooled probit model estimates – the Czech Republic

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_In_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	0.122	0.018	0.000	0.086	0.157
x_In_ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY_SHARE	0.139	0.041	0.001	0.060	0.219
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.063	0.040	0.110	-0.141	0.014
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.281	0.130	0.030	-0.535	-0.027
x_In_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-0.126	0.043	0.003	-0.210	-0.042
x_In_FIXED_ASSETS	0.149	0.092	0.104	-0.031	0.330
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_3	0.115	0.294	0.695	-0.462	0.693
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.149	0.307	0.629	-0.751	0.454
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.433	0.329	0.189	-1.079	0.213
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-1.129	0.402	0.005	-1.917	-0.342
z_TF14_16	-0.091	0.404	0.822	-0.883	0.701
z_TF14_20	0.265	0.642	0.680	-0.994	1.523
z_TF14_35	-0.044	0.568	0.938	-1.157	1.069
z_TF14_36	-0.462	0.763	0.545	-1.958	1.034
z_TF14_45	0.838	0.433	0.053	-0.011	1.688
z_TF14_48	0.055	0.906	0.952	-1.722	1.831
z_TF14_49	0.988	0.398	0.013	0.208	1.768
z_TF14_50	-0.996	0.863	0.249	-2.688	0.696
z_TF14_70	0.662	0.512	0.196	-0.342	1.666
z_TF14_80	0.186	0.366	0.611	-0.531	0.903
YEAR_2009	0.250	0.276	0.366	-0.292	0.791
YEAR_2010	-0.173	0.318	0.587	-0.796	0.450
YEAR_2012	-0.641	0.690	0.353	-1.994	0.712
YEAR_2013	-0.784	0.547	0.152	-1.856	0.288
YEAR_2014	-0.083	1.015	0.935	-2.073	1.907
YEAR_2015	-0.863	0.498	0.083	-1.840	0.114
YEAR_2016	-0.087	0.701	0.902	-1.460	1.287
YEAR_2017	-0.556	0.655	0.396	-1.839	0.727
YEAR_2018	-0.056	0.394	0.888	-0.828	0.717
YEAR_2020	-1.017	0.481	0.034	-1.959	-0.075
_const.	-1.149	0.853	0.178	-2.821	0.524
Wald chi2(30)	198.240		0.000		
Log likelihood	-147.450				
Percentage of correctly predicted values	90.895				
Number of observations	637				
Number of organic farms	79				

Source: own processing

Consistent with the WBRE model, labour intensity is negatively associated with the probability of conversion to organic farming, with the estimates indicating a reduction of approximately 3.6 p.p. In addition, the pooled model identifies a significant effect of labour composition, with a higher share of unpaid labour associated with a reduction in the probability of conversion of about 12.6 p.p. Indeed, in this dataset, the share of unpaid labour is lower among organic farms than among conventional farms, as reported in Table A14 in the Appendix.

Economic size, captured by dummy variables for size categories, confirms that larger farms are less inclined to convert to organic farming, consistent with the findings of the WBRE model. As shown in Table 14, however, only the largest size category, farms with standard output exceeding EUR 500,000, is statistically significant at the 5% level. Farms in this group exhibit a 14.2 p.p. lower probability of conversion compared with farms in the smallest size category (EUR 25,000–50,000 in standard output).

Table 14 Average partial effects (APEs) of pooled probit model – the Czech Republic

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_In_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	0.016	0.002	0.000	0.011	0.020
x_In_ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY_SHARE	0.018	0.005	0.001	0.007	0.028
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.008	0.005	0.110	-0.018	0.002
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.036	0.016	0.028	-0.068	-0.004
x_In_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-0.016	0.005	0.003	-0.027	-0.005
x_In_FIXED_ASSETS	0.019	0.012	0.104	-0.004	0.042
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_3	0.021	0.054	0.695	-0.085	0.128
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.026	0.053	0.631	-0.130	0.079
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.068	0.054	0.207	-0.175	0.038
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-0.142	0.055	0.010	-0.250	-0.034

Source: own processing

Model estimates for livestock production and field crop production based on the approach of Latruffe and Nauges (2014) are presented in Table 15, with the corresponding average partial effects reported in Table 16.

Table 15 Pooled probit model estimates – livestock and field crops production in the Czech Republic

Variable	Livestock production			Field crops production		
	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z
x_In_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	0.152	0.036	0.000	0.206	0.035	0.000
x_In_ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY_SHARE				0.340	0.069	0.000
x_In_EXPECTED_WHEAT_PRICE_Premium				0.074	0.032	0.021
x_In_LIVESTOCK_DENSITY	-0.913	0.466	0.050			
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-1.123	0.461	0.015	-0.868	0.304	0.004
x_In_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-0.417	0.153	0.007			
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.971	0.497	0.051			
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.209	0.790	0.791			
z_ANC_other				0.376	0.269	0.162
z_ANC_mountain				0.592	0.515	0.250
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_3	-0.053	0.695	0.939	-0.645	0.691	0.351
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-1.139	1.041	0.274	-1.043	0.517	0.044
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-1.759	1.058	0.096	-2.111	0.627	0.001
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-4.647	1.460	0.001	-1.255	0.559	0.025
z_TF14_48/ z_TF14_16	-0.657	1.248	0.599	0.272	0.535	0.611
z_TF14_49/ z_TF14_80	-0.553	0.712	0.438	-0.162	0.503	0.748
z_TF14_70	0.301	0.714	0.673			
YEAR_2009	1.141	0.449	0.011	-0.076	0.384	0.842
YEAR_2012	-1.157	0.617	0.061			
YEAR_2014/2013	-0.069	1.009	0.946	-1.575	0.669	0.018
YEAR_2015	1.869	0.742	0.012	-1.323	0.723	0.067
YEAR_2016/2017	0.048	0.852	0.955	-1.346	0.786	0.087
YEAR_2018/2020	-1.488	0.575	0.010	-1.775	0.573	0.002
_const.	1.119	1.594	0.483	2.736	0.854	0.001
Wald chi2(19/17)	63.580		0.000	82.330		
Log likelihood	-31.721			-50.034		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	79.787			94.172		
Number of observations	94			326		
Number of organic farms	40			29		

Source: own processing

Table 16 Average partial effects (APEs) of pooled probit model estimates – livestock and field crops production in the Czech Republic

Variable	Livestock production			Field crops production		
	APE	Std.err.	P> z	APE	Std.err.	P> z
x_In_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	0.029	0.006	0.000	0.017	0.003	0.000
x_In_ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY_SHARE				0.029	0.007	0.000
x_In_EXPECTED_WHEAT_PRICE_PREMIUM				0.006	0.003	0.017
x_In_LIVESTOCK_DENSITY	-0.171	0.084	0.041			
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.210	0.079	0.008	-0.073	0.025	0.004
x_In_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-0.078	0.025	0.002			
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.165	0.083	0.046			
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.032	0.125	0.797			
z_ANC_other				0.033	0.024	0.182
z_ANC_mountain				0.056	0.057	0.327
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_3	-0.007	0.089	0.938	-0.096	0.100	0.333
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.168	0.146	0.249	-0.143	0.080	0.074
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.270	0.128	0.035	-0.219	0.081	0.007
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-0.633	0.089	0.000	-0.163	0.083	0.051

Source: own processing

Across both production specialisations, a positive association is observed between expected subsidy gains and the likelihood of conversion to organic farming. This relationship is more pronounced in livestock production than in field crop production. While the share of environmental subsidies does not reach conventional levels of statistical significance in livestock production, it is positively associated with the probability of conversion in field crop production. Overall, these results suggest that financial incentives play an important, albeit heterogeneous, role in organic farming adoption across different production systems.

In field crop production, the data also allow for the inclusion of a price premium variable. A higher price differential between organic and conventional wheat is positively associated with the likelihood of conversion to organic farming. In livestock production, the FADN database makes it possible to construct an indicator of the milk price premium; however, due to the predominance of beef-cattle specialisation, this variable is available for only a limited number of farms and its estimated effect does not reach conventional levels of statistical significance. By contrast, for livestock production it is possible to include a measure of livestock density, whose average partial effect indicates a negative association with the probability of conversion to organic farming.

In both production types, labour intensity is associated with a lower probability of conversion to organic farming, consistent with the results of the WBRE model. However, the share of unpaid labour is statistically significant only in livestock production, with an average partial effect of -7.8 p.p. In contrast to the WBRE models, farm location plays a significant role exclusively in livestock production, particularly for farms located at altitudes between 300 and 600 meters above sea level. Finally, the probability of conversion declines with increasing economic size, consistent with the WBRE results. In livestock production, the magnitude of this association increases with farm size. In field crop production, farms in the largest size category (i.e., farms exceeding EUR 500,000 in standard output) exhibit a 16.3 p.p. lower probability of conversion, while farms in the EUR 100,000–500,000 standard output category exhibit an even lower probability of conversion (by 21.9 p.p.) relative to the reference group, i.e., farms with standard output below EUR 25,000.

Consistent with the WBRE models, the results indicate that the determinants of organic farming adoption are production-specific. The observed changes in key determinants over time make prediction based on historical data and revealed adoption behaviour challenging when attempting to identify which farms are likely to convert to organic farming in the future. For this purpose, an

alternative approach based on survey data capturing farmers' intentions to adopt organic farming may be more appropriate, as it allows for a forward-looking assessment of potential adopters.

4.2 Organic farming in Germany

The development of organic agriculture in Germany dates back to the 1920s, when biodynamic and organic-biological movements laid its foundations, giving the sector a considerably longer tradition than in the Czech Republic. Despite these early origins, institutional consolidation and large-scale expansion did not occur until the late twentieth century. Common production standards were introduced in 1984, followed by the establishment of the Federation for Organic Farming (AGOEL) in 1988. A decisive regulatory milestone was Council Regulation (EC) No. 2092/91, which came into force in 1992 and was complemented by national legislation (Willer & Youssefi, 2006).

Financial support further stimulated growth. Public funding was introduced in 1989 through the EU extensification scheme, and from 1994 onward, support for the introduction and maintenance of organic farming was incorporated into the rural development framework, subsequently governed by successive EU rural development regulations (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2025).

Following German reunification in 1990, organic farming also expanded rapidly in eastern Germany, where it had previously been officially prohibited under the former regime (Willer & Youssefi, 2006). According to official statistics, at the beginning of the 1990s, 5,866 farms operated under organic management on 272,139 hectares, accounting for approximately 1.6% of total agricultural land (Figure 6) (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2025).

The expansion of organic farming after 2000 was driven by the introduction of a comprehensive policy framework aimed at supporting the sector. This framework included enhanced financial support for organic farms and the establishment of the national organic label (Bio-Siegel) in 2002 (Willer & Youssefi, 2006; Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2025). Under the Federal Organic Farming Scheme (BÖL), the number of organic farms in Germany increased by 49% between 2000 and 2010, while organically managed land expanded by 81%, reaching 990,702 hectares.

Figure 6 Number of organic farms and share of agricultural land under organic management in Germany

Source: Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity (2025).

As the policy measures also targeted processing and marketing activities, growth extended beyond primary production. The number of organic processors more than doubled from 3,850 to 8,511 (a 2.2-fold increase), and the organic market share rose from 1.4% to 3.7% (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Number of organic processors and organic products share of total retail sales

Source: FiBL (2025)

Institutional consolidation further strengthened the sector. Most organic farms in Germany were members of producer associations. In 2002, representatives of organic farming associations, organic food processors and organic trade established the Bund Ökologischer Lebensmittelwirtschaft (BÖLW, Organic Food Industry Federation) as the umbrella organization of the entire organic sector. Notably, some standards set by German organic associations are stricter than those defined in EU organic farming legislation, reinforcing the credibility and differentiation of the sector.

During the period 2010–2020, the expansion of organic farming in Germany continued at a substantial pace. The number of farms increased by 61% to 35,396, managing 1,702,240 hectares, equivalent to 10.2% of total agricultural land. Over the same period, the number of organic processors doubled and the organic market share rose to 6.8%. This development was likely facilitated by several complementary policy instruments introduced at both EU and national levels.

At the EU level, the 2014–2020 programming period marked an important institutional shift, as organic farming was granted a distinct policy identity under Article 29 (Measure 11) of the Rural Development Regulation (EU Regulation No 1305/2013). Maintenance payments were increased and continued to be provided on a per-hectare basis, differentiated by land use, with the clear objective of compensating for income foregone and additional costs associated with organic production (Lampkin & Sander, 2022).

At the national level, the Federal Government adopted an action plan for 2017–2022 aimed at raising the share of agricultural land under organic management to 20%. The strategy combined enhanced production support with measures to strengthen cooperative supply chain management and expand public procurement of organic products, supported by targeted information campaigns. It also included advisory services to promote the use of organic products in out-of-home catering and continued consumer information activities under the Federal Organic Farming Scheme (BÖL). Additional components comprised expanded conversion advisory services, the establishment of a herbage legume demonstration network, the development of training programmes (including regulatory adjustments), and increased research funding (Willer et al., 2024). Despite this comprehensive policy framework, the 20% target was not achieved (Figure 6).

In the subsequent programming period, the emphasis on agricultural sustainability was further strengthened, resulting in additional increases in support payments. In vegetable production, continuation payments rose by up to 35%, reaching €485 per hectare, whereas payments for maintaining grassland under organic management increased only marginally, by 4%, to €219 per hectare. The highest levels of support were directed towards permanent crops, amounting to €1,210 per hectare during the conversion period and €987 per hectare for maintenance, reflecting differences in cost structures and income foregone across production systems (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2025).

A new action plan for the period 2023–2030 was subsequently introduced, setting a more ambitious target of 30% of agricultural land under organic management. The strategy seeks to achieve this objective through improved remuneration of public goods delivered by organic farming, support for processing, input markets and plant breeding, and the further development of supply chains. It also aims to expand public procurement and the share of organic products in public catering, strengthen business advisory services, and reduce administrative burdens. Complementary measures include public information campaigns, the provision of technical information on crop yields, livestock production and biodiversity, the development of regional conversion strategies, enhanced knowledge transfer, expanded training across the entire value chain, and increased availability of research and data (Willer et al., 2024).

By 2023, 36,680 farms were operating under organic management, covering 1,888,999 hectares, equivalent to 11.4% of total agricultural land. More than half of the organically managed area consists of permanent pasture, reflecting the traditional dominance of ruminant livestock in organic animal husbandry. In 2020, over 25% of German suckler cows were kept on organic holdings, while sheep and goat production also plays a relatively important role within the sector (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2024).

At the same time, organic fruit and vegetable production has gained increasing prominence in plant production. Between 2000 and 2021, the area under organic vegetables expanded by approximately 180%, rising from 6,500 to 18,220 hectares. Consequently, organic vegetable production now accounts for around 14% of total vegetable output, substantially exceeding the overall share of agricultural land under organic management (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2024).

Demand-side dynamics have further reinforced this structural transformation. Annual per capita expenditure on organic products reached €190.6 (almost three times the level recorded in 2010) thereby attracting new processors and increasing their number to 22,382. This development suggests that organic production is increasingly perceived not only as an environmental strategy but also as a viable business model, enabling firms to position themselves as sustainable, diversified, and attractive to both younger employees and consumers (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2025).

4.2.1 Diffusion of organic farming in Germany

Tables 17–18 present the results of the Bass model estimations, where the exogenous adoption potential is defined as the share of total agricultural land in Germany that can be converted to organic farming. To ensure consistency with the results for Czech agriculture, the assumed adoption potential is specified to range from 25% to 100%, despite Germany's policy objective of placing at least 30% of agricultural land under organic management by 2030. All models show a moderately strong fit, with R^2 values between 70.5% and 70.7% and RMSE values ranging from 34.3 to 34.4. These measures remain highly stable across alternative assumptions regarding adoption potential.

The innovation coefficient is relatively stable (ranging from 0.002 to 0.005) and statistically significant at the 1% level. However, since the diffusion process had already begun prior to the observation period, the estimated innovation coefficient should be interpreted as conditional on an ongoing adoption trajectory rather than as a measure of early-stage uptake. The imitation coefficient (q) is statistically significant at the 1% level across all assumed adoption potentials, although its magnitude decreases from 0.060 to 0.037. This suggests that the diffusion of organic agriculture in Germany is primarily driven by imitation effects.

Table 17 Bass model with exogenous M - Germany (data from 1985)

A.potential	25%			30%			40%			50%		
	Coef.	Std.err	P> t									
p	0.005	0.002	0.004	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.001
q	0.060	0.015	0.000	0.053	0.014	0.000	0.047	0.013	0.000	0.043	0.012	0.000
R2	0.705			0.706			0.707			0.707		
Adj.R2	0.688			0.690			0.690			0.690		
RMSE	34.396			34.323			34.287			34.283		

A.potential	60%			70%			80%			90%		
	Coef.	Std.err	P> t									
p	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.000
q	0.041	0.012	0.001	0.039	0.012	0.001	0.038	0.012	0.001	0.037	0.011	0.001
R2	0.707			0.707			0.707			0.706		
Adj.R2	0.690			0.690			0.690			0.690		
RMSE	34.285			34.288			34.290			34.293		

Source: own processing

Note: UAA is assumed to remain constant at the 2023 level.

Table 18 Bass model with adoption potential as 100% UAA – Germany (data from 1985)

	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	Coef.
p	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.002
q	0.037	0.011	0.001	0.014	0.059
R2	0.706				
Adj.R2	0.690				
RMSE	34.295				

Source: own processing

Note: UAA is assumed to remain constant at the 2023 level.

This result suggests that the prevailing behaviour of German farmers adopting organic farming is driven more by imitation and the tendency to follow others than by fully independent decision-making. By imitating farms that have already converted to organic production, potential adopters can acquire knowledge and experience more rapidly. Such knowledge spillovers reduce uncertainty about potential risks and, in turn, increase farmers' confidence in converting to organic farming. However, imitation behaviour may reflect not only a neighbourhood effect, whereby adoption intentions arise from observing nearby farms that have already transitioned to organic farming, but also the influence of broader social pressures through which society shapes and reinforces particular patterns of behaviour.

Figure 8 and Table B18 in the Appendix present a simulation of the adoption of organic farming in Germany, based on the assumption of a 30% adoption potential, which reflects the current target set by the Federal Government (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2024). Under current conditions, the model projects that organic farming would expand to 2,247,386 hectares, representing 14.6% of Germany's agricultural land (assuming the 2023 level of UAA).

Figure 8 Cumulative adoption of organic farming according to Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 30% of agricultural area)

Source: own processing

Simulations based on higher adoption potential are reported in Tables B19–B25. In addition, Figure 9 illustrates the simulation under a hypothetical adoption potential of 100% of agricultural land. The projections are highly similar across scenarios, indicating that increases in the assumed adoption potential lead only to marginal improvements in predictive precision.

Figure 9 Cumulative adoption of organic farming according to Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 100% of agricultural area)

Source: own processing

4.2.2 Adoption of organic farming in Germany

Similarly to the analysis for the Czech Republic, the adoption of organic farming in Germany is examined using a WBRE model, with the corresponding estimates reported in Table 19. The model specification is assessed through a series of Wald tests, which evaluate the joint significance of the estimated parameters, the relevance of Mundlak's devices, and the exogeneity of potentially endogenous variables, namely economic size and labour intensity.

Table 19 Probit model estimates – Germany

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	1.613	0.308	0.000	1.008	2.217
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	3.969	0.579	0.000	2.834	5.104
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-1.137	0.227	0.000	-1.582	-0.692
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.045	0.027	0.094	-0.097	0.008
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.059	0.056	0.292	-0.050	0.168
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	0.002	0.019	0.916	-0.036	0.040
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.148	0.198	0.456	-0.536	0.240
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-2.210	0.630	0.000	-3.445	-0.974
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.463	0.140	0.001	-0.737	-0.189
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	1.562	0.514	0.002	0.555	2.569
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.675	0.224	0.003	-1.115	-0.235
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-1.413	0.494	0.004	-2.381	-0.445
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.538	0.158	0.001	-0.848	-0.227
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	1.537	0.648	0.018	0.267	2.807
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	1.494	0.771	0.053	-0.018	3.006
z_TF14_16	0.240	0.289	0.406	-0.326	0.806
z_TF14_20	3.977	1.705	0.020	0.634	7.319
z_TF14_35	2.739	1.782	0.124	-0.753	6.231
z_TF14_36	2.466	1.592	0.121	-0.654	5.587
z_TF14_38	3.349	0.789	0.000	1.802	4.895
z_TF14_45	1.321	0.539	0.014	0.265	2.378
z_TF14_48	1.600	0.515	0.002	0.590	2.610
z_TF14_49	1.552	0.417	0.000	0.735	2.370
z_TF14_50	0.845	0.723	0.243	-0.573	2.262
z_TF14_60	1.578	0.615	0.010	0.372	2.783
z_TF14_70	1.228	0.484	0.011	0.279	2.176
z_TF14_80	0.825	0.358	0.021	0.122	1.527
z_PP_2014_2020	0.066	0.090	0.461	-0.110	0.242
YEAR_2021	-0.393	0.172	0.022	-0.730	-0.056
_const.	11.753	3.254	0.000	5.375	18.131
Insig2u	3.982	0.169		3.651	4.312
sigma_u	7.322	0.617		6.207	8.638
Rho	0.982	0.003		0.975	0.987
Wald chi2(29)	167.400		0.000		
Log likelihood	-5946.511				
Wald chi2(5): Mundlak's devices	12.200		0.032		
Wald chi2(2): LABOUR_INTENSITY_res, ESIZE_res	1.920		0.383		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	87.160				
Number of observations	99,064				
Number of farms	14,028				

Source: own processing

Regarding exogeneity, the failure to reject the null hypothesis of a non-significant effect of the residuals from these variables on the dependent variable suggests that the assumption of exogeneity is not violated. By contrast, the Wald test rejects the null hypothesis of non-significance of the group means, thereby favouring the WBRE model over the standard random effects model. The Wald test also rejects the null hypothesis of joint non-significance of the estimated parameters. All these conclusions hold at the 5% significance level. The estimates are based on winsorised data. However, the magnitude and sign of the estimated coefficients remain largely unchanged when non-winsorised data are used (Tables B26–B27 in Appendix B)¹⁰.

Table 19 first presents the coefficients of variables measured at the regional level (the number of organic farms) and at the national level (market share). These are followed by estimates of the within effects of time-varying variables, and subsequently by the between effects and dummy variables. The corresponding average partial effects are reported in Table 20.

Table 20 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit model – Germany

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	0.028	0.005	0.000	0.018	0.038
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.069	0.019	0.000	0.032	0.106
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.020	0.005	0.000	-0.030	-0.009
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.001	0.001	0.128	-0.002	0.000
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.001	0.001	0.308	-0.001	0.003
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	0.000	0.000	0.916	-0.001	0.001
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.003	0.004	0.468	-0.010	0.004
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.039	0.005	0.000	-0.049	-0.028
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.008	0.002	0.000	-0.011	-0.005
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.027	0.005	0.000	0.017	0.037
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.012	0.002	0.000	-0.017	-0.007
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.025	0.006	0.000	-0.037	-0.012
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.009	0.004	0.015	-0.017	-0.002
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.028	0.009	0.001	0.011	0.045
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.027	0.013	0.035	0.002	0.053
z_TF14_16	0.003	0.004	0.436	-0.005	0.012
z_TF14_20	0.078	0.043	0.070	-0.006	0.163
z_TF14_35	0.049	0.032	0.127	-0.014	0.111
z_TF14_36	0.043	0.033	0.194	-0.022	0.107
z_TF14_38	0.063	0.020	0.002	0.023	0.102
z_TF14_45	0.021	0.009	0.016	0.004	0.037
z_TF14_48	0.026	0.010	0.012	0.006	0.045
z_TF14_49	0.025	0.008	0.004	0.008	0.041
z_TF14_50	0.013	0.012	0.295	-0.011	0.036
z_TF14_60	0.025	0.011	0.027	0.003	0.047
z_TF14_70	0.019	0.009	0.035	0.001	0.036
z_TF14_80	0.012	0.006	0.044	0.000	0.024
z_PP_2014_2020	0.001	0.002	0.455	-0.002	0.004

Source: own processing

Consistent with the results of the Bass model, a statistically significant neighbourhood effect is identified. Farms located in areas with a higher presence of organic producers exhibit an approximately 2.8 percentage point (p.p.) higher probability of conversion to organic farming. This finding suggests the existence of knowledge spillovers and learning effects, whereby experience and information are transmitted between neighbouring farms.

¹⁰ A specification including year dummies was also estimated, with the results presented in Tables B28–B29 in the Appendix.

An even stronger effect is observed for the market share of organic products, highlighting the key role of market demand in shaping farmers' adoption decisions. Compared with the Czech Republic, the effect of market share is stronger in Germany, which likely reflects a more developed organic market, stronger demand from processors, and higher final consumer demand. As in the Czech Republic, market share is strongly correlated with the number of processors (correlation coefficient of 0.94). However, while in the Czech Republic there were on average 0.14 organic processors per organic farm over the period 2008–2021, the corresponding figure in Germany was 0.46. Moreover, per capita consumption of organic products is almost nine times higher in Germany than in the Czech Republic.

Focusing on farm characteristics, the between-effects results are consistent with the findings for the Czech Republic, indicating a lower probability of conversion among farms with larger economic size, a higher degree of specialisation, and greater labour intensity. A lower probability of conversion is also observed for farms operating on higher-quality land, as reflected in higher rental prices. By contrast, farms with a higher share of rented land and those located at altitudes above 300 meters above sea level exhibit a higher probability of conversion. The effect of altitude (approximately 2.7–2.8 p.p.) is weaker than that observed in the Czech Republic. Furthermore, the probability of conversion to organic farming is lower for family farms. Indeed, the proportion of family farms is lower among organic farms (48%) than among conventional farms (52%) in the FADN dataset.

Among the within effects, economic size is the only determinant that reaches statistical significance at the 5% level, with increases in economic size associated with a lower probability of conversion to organic farming. Finally, the results indicate that the likelihood of conversion differs across farming types.

To investigate the stability of these effects over the diffusion process, probit models are estimated using cross-sectional data from the first, middle, and final years of the FADN dataset. The results are reported in Table 21. According to the Wald test, the estimated coefficients are jointly statistically significant in each specification, and the proportion of correctly predicted observations ranges from 90.4% to 95.4%, exceeding the predictive accuracy of the WBRE model.

Table 21 Probit model estimates for 2008, 2015, and 2021 – Germany

Variable	2008			2015			2021		
	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	0.289	0.046	0.000	0.327	0.040	0.000	0.045	0.005	0.000
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.347	0.037	0.000	-0.376	0.038	0.000	-0.068	0.005	0.000
x_ln_FIXED_ASSESTS	-0.157	0.027	0.000	-0.118	0.032	0.000			
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.042	0.014	0.002	-0.054	0.011	0.000	-0.011	0.001	0.000
x_ln_COWS_TLU				-0.033	0.016	0.041			
x_ln_RENTED_LAND				0.064	0.035	0.065	0.025	0.004	0.000
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE				-0.034	0.016	0.031	-0.007	0.002	0.000
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.202	0.052	0.000	-0.092	0.047	0.051	-0.025	0.007	0.000
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS				0.031	0.014	0.026	0.011	0.002	0.000
x_ln_OA_SHARE	0.036	0.017	0.031				0.008	0.002	0.000
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.537	0.064	0.000	-0.588	0.058	0.000	-0.067	0.008	0.000
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.055	0.067	0.410				0.022	0.008	0.004
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.296	0.144	0.040				0.041	0.019	0.032
z_ANC_other	0.267	0.066	0.000	0.267	0.053	0.000	0.026	0.007	0.001
z_ANC_mountain	0.356	0.212	0.093	0.564	0.138	0.000	0.044	0.016	0.005
z_TF14_16	0.316	0.131	0.016	0.432	0.113	0.000	0.028	0.010	0.007
z_TF14_20	1.104	0.273	0.000	0.699	0.261	0.007	0.160	0.063	0.011
z_TF14_35	0.475	0.203	0.019	0.307	0.171	0.074	0.008	0.018	0.671
z_TF14_36	0.478	0.263	0.070	0.474	0.235	0.044	0.141	0.055	0.010
z_TF14_38				0.671	0.360	0.063	0.024	0.064	0.710
z_TF14_45	0.383	0.122	0.002	0.764	0.138	0.000	0.066	0.012	0.000
z_TF14_48	0.312	0.243	0.199	0.342	0.171	0.045	0.049	0.025	0.048
z_TF14_49	0.458	0.129	0.000	0.636	0.110	0.000	0.069	0.012	0.000
z_TF14_50	0.167	0.152	0.275	0.259	0.147	0.078	0.053	0.018	0.003
z_TF14_60	-0.261	0.313	0.404	0.341	0.212	0.108	0.043	0.028	0.129
z_TF14_70	0.373	0.156	0.017	0.500	0.176	0.004	0.105	0.030	0.001
z_TF14_80	0.313	0.115	0.007	0.601	0.102	0.000	0.057	0.012	0.000
_const.	0.882	0.344	0.010	0.335	0.354	0.344	0.025	0.004	0.000
Wald chi2(22/24/25)	328.20		0.000	504.39		0.000	624.79		0.000
Log likelihood	-1276.2			-1814.2			-2068.7		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	95.356			93.512			90.350		
Number of observations	7,838			8,878			7,741		
Number of organic farms	364			571			765		

Source: own processing

Similarly to the Czech Republic, the determinants of adoption are found to vary across selected years. In all years, a statistically significant effect of the number of organically managed farms in the NUTS2 region in which a farm is located is observed. Moreover, the magnitude of this effect increases over time, rising from approximately 2.5 percentage points to 4.5 p.p. (Table 22). This pattern suggests that the expanding presence of organic farms, providing observable evidence and practical experience of organic conversion, increasingly encourages conventionally managed farms to adopt organic practices.

The negative effect of economic size increases in magnitude over time, rising from approximately 3.1 p.p. to 6.8 p.p. Large farms thus appear to become less inclined to convert to organic farming over time, a pattern also observed for farms specialising in cereal production. The magnitude of the effect of specialisation, measured by the share of cereals in arable land, increases from about 0.4 p.p. to 1.1 p.p.

Moreover, a negative effect of labour intensity and family-farm status is observed in all years, consistent with the results of the WBRE model. Farms with higher capital intensity also exhibit a lower probability of conversion to organic farming; however, the effect of capital intensity is statistically significant only in 2008 and 2015. By contrast, in 2015 and 2021, the average partial effect of the debt-to-assets ratio is positive and statistically significant at the 5% level, suggesting that more highly leveraged farms are increasingly likely to convert to organic farming over time. In 2008 and 2021, a positive effect of diversification, proxied by the share of other output in total output, is also observed. This effect is not identified in the WBRE model.

Table 22 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit models for 2008, 2015, and 2021 – Germany

Variable	2008			2015			2021		
	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z
x_In_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	0.025	0.004	0.000	0.036	0.004	0.000	0.045	0.005	0.000
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.030	0.003	0.000	-0.041	0.004	0.000	-0.068	0.005	0.000
x_In_FIXED_ASSETS	-0.013	0.002	0.000	-0.013	0.003	0.000			
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.004	0.001	0.002	-0.006	0.001	0.000	-0.011	0.001	0.000
x_In_COWS_TLU				-0.004	0.002	0.041			
x_In_RENTED_LAND				0.007	0.004	0.065	0.025	0.004	0.000
x_In_RENTAL_PRICE				-0.004	0.002	0.031	-0.007	0.002	0.000
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.017	0.004	0.000	-0.010	0.005	0.051	-0.025	0.007	0.000
x_In_DEBT_TO_ASSETS				0.003	0.002	0.026	0.011	0.002	0.000
x_In_OA_SHARE	0.003	0.001	0.031				0.008	0.002	0.000
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.046	0.006	0.000	-0.064	0.006	0.000	-0.067	0.008	0.000
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.005	0.006	0.415				0.022	0.008	0.004
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.030	0.017	0.082				0.041	0.019	0.032
z_ANC_other	0.023	0.006	0.000	0.030	0.006	0.000	0.026	0.007	0.001
z_ANC_mountain	0.034	0.025	0.178	0.076	0.025	0.002	0.044	0.016	0.005
z_TF14_16	0.027	0.011	0.016	0.031	0.009	0.000	0.028	0.010	0.007
z_TF14_20	0.094	0.023	0.000	0.063	0.032	0.051	0.160	0.063	0.011
z_TF14_35	0.041	0.017	0.020	0.020	0.012	0.103	0.008	0.018	0.671
z_TF14_36	0.041	0.023	0.070	0.035	0.022	0.112	0.141	0.055	0.010
z_TF14_38				0.059	0.046	0.206	0.024	0.064	0.710
z_TF14_45	0.033	0.010	0.002	0.072	0.014	0.000	0.066	0.012	0.000
z_TF14_48	0.027	0.021	0.199	0.023	0.014	0.091	0.049	0.025	0.048
z_TF14_49	0.039	0.011	0.000	0.054	0.010	0.000	0.069	0.012	0.000
z_TF14_50	0.014	0.013	0.274	0.016	0.010	0.104	0.053	0.018	0.003
z_TF14_60	-0.022	0.027	0.404	0.023	0.017	0.185	0.043	0.028	0.129
z_TF14_70	0.032	0.013	0.016	0.038	0.017	0.023	0.105	0.030	0.001
z_TF14_80	0.027	0.010	0.006	0.050	0.008	0.000	0.057	0.012	0.000

Source: own processing

Consistent with the WBRE model, the probability of conversion to organic farming is higher for farms located at higher altitudes and in areas with natural constraints (ANC). However, both the statistical significance and the magnitude of these location-specific effects vary across years. Similarly to the Czech Republic, the type of farming dummy variables indicate heterogeneous adoption probabilities across different production specialisations.

The estimates of the WBRE probit models for livestock and field-crop production are presented in Table 23. For both models, the Wald test confirms the overall statistical significance of the estimated specification at the 5% level. At the same significance level, the null hypothesis of exogeneity of economic size and labour intensity is not rejected in the livestock production model. In the field-crop production model, this test is not conducted because the coefficients of these variables do not reach statistical significance at the 10% level.

Table 23 Probit model estimates – livestock and field crops production in Germany

Variable	Livestock production			Field crops production		
	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z
x_In_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	0.864	0.253	0.001			
Within						
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-1.328	0.299	0.000			
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE				-0.128	0.054	0.017
x_In_RENTAL_PRICE				0.020	0.033	0.545
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.870	0.239	0.000			
x_In_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS	0.047	0.054	0.378	0.007	0.047	0.889
Between						
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-2.377	0.441	0.000			
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE				-0.075	0.036	0.036
x_In_RENTAL_PRICE				-0.081	0.018	0.000
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-1.919	0.528	0.000			
x_In_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS	0.465	0.169	0.006	0.105	0.044	0.016
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.626	0.166	0.000	-0.263	0.108	0.015
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.348	0.489	0.477	0.548	0.117	0.000
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	1.583	0.658	0.016	0.042	0.460	0.928
z_TF14_48/z_TF14_16	0.077	0.569	0.893	0.104	0.104	0.317
z_TF14_49/z_TF14_60	-0.035	0.330	0.915	0.167	0.208	0.421
z_TF14_70/z_TF14_80	-0.120	0.488	0.806	0.060	0.128	0.641
YEAR_2009				0.079	0.090	0.379
YEAR_2010	0.003	0.114	0.976	0.075	0.111	0.498
YEAR_2011	0.152	0.156	0.330	0.181	0.155	0.241
YEAR_2012	0.197	0.194	0.310	0.171	0.173	0.322
YEAR_2013	0.174	0.188	0.355	-0.026	0.168	0.879
YEAR_2014	0.253	0.227	0.265	-0.077	0.183	0.675
YEAR_2015	0.527	0.238	0.027	0.076	0.206	0.712
YEAR_2016	1.325	0.286	0.000	0.556	0.243	0.022
YEAR_2017	1.477	0.344	0.000	0.626	0.257	0.015
YEAR_2018	1.650	0.353	0.000	0.954	0.267	0.000
YEAR_2019	1.582	0.380	0.000	1.096	0.272	0.000
YEAR_2020	1.709	0.394	0.000	1.208	0.276	0.000
YEAR_2021	1.908	0.405	0.000	1.267	0.281	0.000
_const.	3.283	2.280	0.150	-5.934	0.246	0.000
Insig2u	3.711	0.090		2.596	0.075	
sigma_u	6.395	0.289		3.662	0.137	
Rho	0.976	0.002		0.931	0.005	
Wald chi2(25/25)	163.240		0.000	80.590		0.000
Log likelihood	-3018.554			-2051.622		
Wald chi2(3/3): Mundlak's devices	12.030		0.007	9.410		0.024
Wald chi2(2/0): LABOUR_INTENSITY_res, ESIZE_res	0.100		0.952			
Percentage of correctly predicted values	84.917			94.806		
Number of observations	37,634			37,716		
Number of farms	5,811			5,277		

Source: own processing

Furthermore, the Wald test rejects the null hypothesis of the joint statistical insignificance of Mundlak's devices at the 5% significance level, indicating potential inconsistency in the standard random effects model without correction. Finally, the percentage of correctly predicted observations reaches 84.9% for livestock production and 94.8% for field-crop production.

Tables 23 and 24, which present the estimation results and the corresponding average partial effects, indicate that the determinants of organic farming adoption differ between livestock and field-crop production. For instance, the effect of the number of organic farms is not statistically significant for field crop production, even at the 10% level. By contrast, in livestock production this variable has a

statistically significant positive effect on the probability of conversion to organic farming, with an average partial effect of approximately 2.4 p.p.

Similarly, labour intensity is not statistically significant in the field crop production model, whereas in livestock production both the between- and within-effects are negative and statistically significant at the 5% level. In contrast, land rental prices are statistically significant at the 5% level only in field crop production: farms facing higher rental costs exhibit a lower probability of conversion to organic farming, which is consistent with the common model. A negative effect is also observed for a high share of cereals in arable land.

Table 24 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit model – livestock and field crops production in Germany

Variable	Livestock production			Field crops production		
	APE	Std.err.	P> z	APE	Std.err.	P> z
x_In_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	0.024	0.008	0.002			
Within						
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.038	0.009	0.000			
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE				-0.004	0.002	0.020
x_In_RENTAL_PRICE				0.001	0.001	0.547
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.025	0.007	0.001			
x_In_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS	0.001	0.002	0.378	0.000	0.001	0.889
Between						
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.067	0.009	0.000			
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE				-0.002	0.001	0.028
x_In_RENTAL_PRICE				-0.003	0.000	0.000
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.054	0.014	0.000			
x_In_DEBT_TO_ASSESTS	0.013	0.005	0.004	0.003	0.001	0.005
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.018	0.005	0.001	-0.008	0.003	0.016
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.010	0.015	0.489	0.019	0.003	0.000
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.049	0.021	0.019	0.001	0.014	0.929

Source: own processing

Both models further reveal that farms with a higher debt-to-assets ratio are more inclined to convert to organic farming. Indeed, in field crop production, the average debt-to-assets ratio in organic farms is 1.12 higher than in conventional farms. In livestock production, this ratio is, on average, 1.05 higher in organic farms.

Family farms display a lower probability of conversion to organic farming in both livestock and field crop production, in line with the common model presented in Tables 19–20. Farm location also plays a statistically significant role: in livestock production, farms situated at altitudes above 600 meters above sea level exhibit an approximately 4.9 p.p. higher probability of conversion, while in field crop production this effect is observed for farms located at altitudes between 300 and 600 meters above sea level.

Similarly to the results based on Czech data, the determinants of organic farming adoption in livestock and field crop production differ across stages of the diffusion process, as shown in Tables B30–B31 in Appendix B. In both production specialisations, a strengthening negative effect of economic size can be observed over time. In livestock production, a particularly noteworthy finding is the declining influence of farm location in LFAs.

The results reflect the structure of the German organic sector as reported in national statistics. Organic farming in Germany is predominantly located on lower-quality sites with lower yield potential and a high share of permanent grassland. More than half of the organically farmed area consists of permanent pasture, reflecting the dominance of ruminant species in organic livestock production.

Compared with the Czech Republic, organic farming in Germany shows a markedly higher representation of dairy cows. In Germany, more than 25 % of suckler cows are kept under organic standards, whereas in the Czech Republic only 1.2 % of dairy cows are managed organically (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2024; Hlaváčková et al., 2025a; Vona & Kopáček, 2025). Similarly to the Czech Republic, sheep and goat husbandry plays a relatively important role within the German organic sector. Moreover, the number of organic farms in the poultry sector has also been increasing, which is reflected in the rising average partial effects of the TF–50 dummy. In crop production, cereals and legumes are key components of organic farming systems. Legumes occupy a substantial share of organically farmed land and are integrated into cereal-based crop rotations primarily to supply biologically fixed nitrogen, improve soil fertility, and support the stability of subsequent cereal yields.

Consistent with the identified negative effect of economic size, organic farming is predominantly practiced by small and medium-sized farms. The average organic farm operates on just under 50 hectares of agricultural land, although considerable heterogeneity in farm size is observed (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2024). The model results further reveal a significant neighbourhood effect in the adoption of organic farming. The presence of organic farms in proximity, together with formal and informal linkages, appears to facilitate the conversion process by providing observable signals of the economic performance of organic production and by reducing information asymmetries and perceived uncertainty associated with conversion. Consistent with this mechanism, evidence reported by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity (2024) shows that organic farms tended to outperform comparable conventional holdings in terms of profitability during 2014–2021. These observable economic outcomes provide concrete signals to neighbouring farmers, who can directly assess the realised benefits of organic production and adjust their conversion decisions accordingly. Conversely, as this profitability advantage weakened in 2022 and 2023, conversion to organic farming in Germany stagnated in 2023 and 2024 (Kuhnert & Offermann, 2025), consistent with farmers revising their expectations based on peers' experiences.

Demand for organic products, similarly to the Czech Republic, represents a key determinant of the development of organic farming (Kuhnert, 2025). With a market share of organic products of 6.3 %, Germany ranks among the most developed organic food markets in the European Union (FiBL, 2025). In contrast to the Czech Republic, a substantial share of organic production in Germany is marketed through public catering channels, including preschools, schools, workplace canteens, and nursing homes. This strategy is explicitly aimed at achieving a 30% share of organic food in public catering, supported by dedicated subsidy programmes (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, 2024). This approach may serve as an inspiration for Czech policymakers.

From a policy perspective, further development of organic farming requires a coordinated approach combining demand-side support, expansion of processing capacities, targeted research and innovation, and effective knowledge transfer mechanisms. These measures are essential to reduce conversion risks, enhance production efficiency, and ensure the long-term economic viability of organic farming systems.

4.2.3 ROBUSTNESS CHECK OF GERMAN ORGANIC FARMING ADOPTION MODELS

The robustness check is based on alternative model specifications. Table 25 reports the estimates from a corrected random-effects probit model incorporating Wooldridge's correction devices. However, the relevance of these correction terms is not supported by the Wald test at the 5% significance level. This result indicates that the model without correction is both consistent and more efficient. The model correctly predicts 87 % of observations, which is comparable to the performance of the WBRE model.

Table 25 Probit model estimates with Wooldrige's (2019) devices – Germany

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	1.463	0.264	0.000	0.945	1.981
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	4.006	0.561	0.000	2.906	5.106
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-1.128	0.218	0.000	-1.554	-0.701
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.043	0.026	0.100	-0.094	0.008
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.059	0.055	0.281	-0.048	0.166
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	0.002	0.019	0.932	-0.035	0.038
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.151	0.194	0.436	-0.532	0.229
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.517	0.151	0.001	-0.813	-0.220
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	1.205	0.547	0.027	0.134	2.277
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	1.580	0.698	0.024	0.212	2.949
z_TF14_16	0.181	0.272	0.506	-0.352	0.713
z_TF14_20	3.864	1.580	0.014	0.767	6.962
z_TF14_35	2.529	1.662	0.128	-0.729	5.787
z_TF14_36	2.464	1.353	0.069	-0.188	5.117
z_TF14_38	3.176	0.743	0.000	1.720	4.632
z_TF14_45	1.293	0.507	0.011	0.299	2.287
z_TF14_48	1.574	0.497	0.002	0.599	2.548
z_TF14_49	1.502	0.387	0.000	0.744	2.261
z_TF14_50	0.786	0.688	0.253	-0.562	2.134
z_TF14_60	1.562	0.592	0.008	0.402	2.722
z_TF14_70	1.117	0.462	0.016	0.212	2.023
z_TF14_80	0.765	0.338	0.024	0.103	1.426
z_PP_2014_2020	0.068	0.086	0.427	-0.100	0.236
YEAR_2021	-0.418	0.163	0.011	-0.738	-0.097
_const.	12.930	4.933	0.009	3.262	22.598
lnsig2u	3.902	0.150		3.608	4.197
sigma_u	7.037	0.529		6.073	8.154
Rho	0.980	0.003		0.974	0.985
Wald chi2(95)	190.620		0.000		
Log likelihood	-5915.485				
Wald chi2(71): CRE parameters – Ti_means	19.540		1.000		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	87.173				
Number of observations	99,064				
Number of farms	14,028				

Source: own processing

Average partial effects reported in Table 26 are largely consistent with those obtained from the WBRE model. In particular, the estimated effects of the number of organic farms at the NUTS2 level and market share closely align with the WBRE results. Only minor differences are observed in the average partial effects of dummy variables, while the effects of time-varying covariates are consistent with the estimated within-effects.

Overall, in line with the WBRE model results, the likelihood of conversion to organic farming is influenced by neighbourhood effects and driven by market demand. Farms located at higher altitudes also exhibit a higher probability of conversion. In addition, substantial differences in conversion probabilities are observed across different farm types, indicating heterogeneity in adoption behaviour.

Table 26 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit model with Wooldrige’s (2019) devices – Germany

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	0.026	0.005	0.000	0.016	0.035
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.070	0.019	0.000	0.034	0.107
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.020	0.005	0.000	-0.030	-0.009
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.001	0.000	0.127	-0.002	0.000
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.001	0.001	0.299	-0.001	0.003
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	0.000	0.000	0.932	-0.001	0.001
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.003	0.004	0.450	-0.010	0.004
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.009	0.004	0.014	-0.016	-0.002
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.022	0.008	0.009	0.005	0.038
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.029	0.012	0.015	0.006	0.053
z_TF14_16	0.003	0.004	0.526	-0.005	0.010
z_TF14_20	0.077	0.041	0.056	-0.002	0.157
z_TF14_35	0.045	0.031	0.142	-0.015	0.105
z_TF14_36	0.044	0.028	0.121	-0.011	0.099
z_TF14_38	0.060	0.020	0.003	0.021	0.099
z_TF14_45	0.020	0.008	0.015	0.004	0.037
z_TF14_48	0.025	0.010	0.011	0.006	0.045
z_TF14_49	0.024	0.008	0.004	0.008	0.041
z_TF14_50	0.012	0.011	0.308	-0.011	0.034
z_TF14_60	0.025	0.011	0.023	0.003	0.047
z_TF14_70	0.017	0.009	0.046	0.000	0.034
z_TF14_80	0.011	0.006	0.049	0.000	0.023
z_PP_2014_2020	0.001	0.002	0.426	-0.002	0.004

Source: own processing

Table 27 reports probit estimates following the identification strategy proposed by Latruffe and Nauges (2014). The overall validity of the specification is supported by a Wald test, which confirms the joint significance of the model and its covariates at the 5 % significance level. The model correctly classifies 93.3 % of observed outcomes.

Average partial effects derived from the model are reported in Table 28. Consistent with the WBRE results, farms located in regions with a higher number of organic producers exhibit a higher probability of converting to organic farming; however, this effect is statistically significant only at the 10 % level. A higher share of cereals in arable land is also associated with a lower probability of conversion to organic farming, with an estimated average partial effect of approximately (-0.6) p.p. In line with the WBRE model, labour intensity is negatively associated with conversion, with an average partial effect of approximately (-3.1) p.p.

The effect of farm location is likewise comparable to the WBRE results. The probability of adopting organic farming is approximately 3.3 p.p. higher for farms located at altitudes between 300 and 600 meters above sea level and about 10.5 p.p. higher for farms situated above 600 meters. Consistent with the conclusions drawn from the WBRE model, the probability of conversion decreases with increasing economic size. In particular, farms exceeding EUR 500,000 in standard output exhibit an 8.9 p.p. lower probability of converting to organic farming.

Table 27 Pooled probit model estimates – Germany

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARM_NUTS	0.102	0.057	0.076	-0.011	0.214
x_ln_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	0.145	0.010	0.000	0.125	0.164
x_ln_ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY_SHARE	0.104	0.019	0.000	0.067	0.141
x_ln_MFP	-0.304	0.130	0.020	-0.560	-0.049
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.051	0.019	0.007	-0.088	-0.014
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.272	0.083	0.001	-0.434	-0.109
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.278	0.098	0.004	0.086	0.469
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.734	0.227	0.001	0.288	1.180
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.133	0.141	0.344	-0.409	0.143
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.242	0.139	0.082	-0.515	0.031
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-0.862	0.193	0.000	-1.239	-0.484
z_TF14_16	-0.320	0.202	0.113	-0.715	0.076
z_TF14_20	0.344	0.600	0.567	-0.833	1.520
z_TF14_35	0.694	0.303	0.022	0.099	1.288
z_TF14_36	-0.518	0.430	0.228	-1.360	0.324
z_TF14_38	-0.180	0.631	0.775	-1.417	1.056
z_TF14_45	0.319	0.172	0.063	-0.018	0.655
z_TF14_48	-0.760	0.343	0.027	-1.433	-0.087
z_TF14_49	0.492	0.170	0.004	0.159	0.825
z_TF14_50	-0.128	0.244	0.599	-0.606	0.350
z_TF14_60	-1.247	0.453	0.006	-2.136	-0.358
z_TF14_70	-0.118	0.320	0.714	-0.746	0.510
z_TF14_80	0.145	0.172	0.400	-0.192	0.482
YEAR_2009	0.281	0.238	0.238	-0.185	0.746
YEAR_2010	0.207	0.244	0.397	-0.271	0.684
YEAR_2011	-0.270	0.291	0.354	-0.841	0.301
YEAR_2012	-0.372	0.376	0.322	-1.108	0.364
YEAR_2013	0.347	0.270	0.199	-0.182	0.876
YEAR_2014	0.533	0.247	0.031	0.049	1.018
YEAR_2015	1.674	0.229	0.000	1.225	2.124
YEAR_2016	0.998	0.229	0.000	0.548	1.448
YEAR_2017	1.257	0.219	0.000	0.828	1.685
YEAR_2018	1.191	0.239	0.000	0.723	1.658
YEAR_2019	0.364	0.242	0.133	-0.111	0.839
YEAR_2020	-0.307	0.264	0.246	-0.825	0.212
_const.	-0.880	0.292	0.003	-1.451	-0.308
Wald chi2(35)	477.420		0.000		
Log likelihood	-541.504				
Percentage of correctly predicted values	93.303				
Number of observations	2,658				
Number of organic farms	324				

Source: own processing

The coefficients of additional variables not included in the WBRE model that are statistically significant at the 5 % level include expected subsidy gains, the share of environmental subsidies, and multifactor productivity. Comparable to the findings for the Czech Republic, expected subsidy gains increase the probability of conversion. Farms already operating under environmental constraints or regulatory requirements, as captured by a higher share of environmental subsidies in total subsidies, exhibit a greater propensity to adopt organic farming. As the FADN database does not allow for a detailed decomposition of environmental subsidies by specific measures, it can only be inferred that environmentally friendly agricultural practices may serve as a precursor to organic farming (Kitano, 2025).

Table 28 Average partial effects (APEs) of pooled probit model – Germany

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_In_ORGANIC_FARM_NUTS	0.012	0.007	0.076	-0.001	0.025
x_In_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	0.017	0.001	0.000	0.015	0.018
x_In_ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY_SHARE	0.012	0.002	0.000	0.008	0.016
x_In_MFP	-0.035	0.015	0.020	-0.064	-0.005
x_In_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.006	0.002	0.007	-0.010	-0.002
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.031	0.009	0.001	-0.050	-0.013
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.033	0.012	0.007	0.009	0.058
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.105	0.041	0.010	0.025	0.185
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.018	0.019	0.348	-0.056	0.020
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.031	0.019	0.098	-0.069	0.006
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-0.089	0.020	0.000	-0.129	-0.049

Source: own processing

Furthermore, farms with lower multifactor productivity are more likely to convert to organic farming. Farms lagging behind their competitors may perceive organic farming as an alternative development pathway, offering opportunities to improve economic viability through price premia, public support, or a strategic reorientation away from highly competitive conventional production systems.

Subsidies targeted at organic farmers are particularly important during the transition phase, as conversion to organic farming is time-consuming and risky. It requires training and advisory support and is often associated with yield losses due to changes in crop rotation and the abandonment of conventional inputs such as mineral nitrogen fertilisers and pesticides. Moreover, during conversion farmers typically lack access to full organic price premiums, as in-conversion products cannot be marketed as organic or receive only reduced premiums (Lampkin & Sander, 2022).

The coefficients of the farm type dummy variables reveal that the probability of conversion to organic farming varies across farm types. Accordingly, and consistent with the panel data analysis, pooled models are also estimated separately for livestock and field crop production. These estimates are presented in Table 29, with the corresponding average partial effects reported in Table 30.

Expected subsidy gains exert a statistically significant effect at the 5 % level in both production types. The magnitude of the expected subsidy premium is larger in livestock production (2.3 p.p.) than in field crop production (1.1 p.p.). At the same time, both production systems exhibit a positive effect of farm location at higher altitudes, with a markedly higher probability of conversion for farms situated in mountainous areas above 600 meters above sea level.

In livestock production, the effect of environmental subsidies is statistically significant at the 5 % level, increasing the probability of conversion by approximately 1.4 p.p. In contrast, in field-crop production, a negative association is identified between the likelihood of conversion to organic farming and both fertiliser and pesticide intensity. Similar to the case of environmental subsidies, this pattern may indicate that more environmentally friendly management practices often precede conversion to organic farming. At the same time, it may reflect underlying farmer values and attitudes towards environmental stewardship, whereby producers who already limit the use of chemical inputs are more inclined to consider organic production as a natural extension of their existing practices.

Table 29 Pooled probit model estimates – livestock production and field crops production in the Germany

Variable	Livestock production			Field crops production		
	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z
x_In_ORGANIC_FARM_NUTS				0.251	0.125	0.045
x_In_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	0.163	0.015	0.000	0.135	0.020	0.000
x_In_ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY_SHARE	0.102	0.027	0.000			
x_In_EXPECTED_WHEAT_PRICE_PREMIUM				0.058	0.021	0.007
x_In_LIVESTOCK_DENSITY	-0.257	0.136	0.059			
x_In_MFP				-1.265	0.276	0.000
x_In_RENTED_LAND_SHARE				-0.225	0.077	0.003
x_In_RENTAL_PRICE				0.185	0.062	0.003
x_In_FERTILISERS_HA				-0.061	0.033	0.067
x_In_PESTICIDES_HA				-0.087	0.020	0.000
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.259	0.167	0.121			
x_In_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	0.079	0.047	0.091			
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.337	0.137	0.014	0.484	0.179	0.007
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.923	0.264	0.000	1.799	0.643	0.005
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.211	0.231	0.362	0.198	0.245	0.418
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.269	0.249	0.279	0.341	0.236	0.149
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-0.676	0.360	0.060	-0.303	0.292	0.299
z_TF14_48/ z_TF14_16	-1.074	0.358	0.003	-0.382	0.217	0.078
z_TF14_49	0.327	0.165	0.047			
z_TF14_70/ z_TF14_80	-0.255	0.308	0.407	-0.009	0.214	0.966
YEAR_2012				-1.143	0.439	0.009
YEAR_2014	0.547	0.222	0.014			
YEAR_2015	1.863	0.226	0.000	1.958	0.307	0.000
YEAR_2016	0.858	0.237	0.000	1.548	0.323	0.000
YEAR_2017	0.933	0.185	0.000	1.687	0.280	0.000
YEAR_2018	1.007	0.233	0.000			
YEAR_2019				1.373	0.326	0.000
YEAR_2020	-0.956	0.388	0.014			
_const.	0.106	0.350	0.762	-2.801	0.645	0.000
Wald chi2(19/20)	232.400		0.000	147.730		0.000
Log likelihood	-242.544			-133.917		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	91.003			95.028		
Number of observations	967			905		
Number of organic farms	184			89		

Source: own processing

Furthermore, in field-crop production, a positive association is observed between the wheat price premium and the probability of conversion, with higher expected prices for organic wheat associated with an approximately 0.5 p.p. increase in the probability of conversion. In line with the evidence for the Czech Republic, this suggests that subsidies are more strongly associated with organic farming adoption than price premiums.

A negative effect of multifactor productivity is also observed, indicating that farms with lower productivity levels are more likely to convert to organic farming. This pattern suggests that less productive farms may perceive organic farming as a strategic alternative to intensive conventional production, benefiting from income-stabilizing support payments and lower reliance on productivity-enhancing external inputs, thereby improving their relative economic performance.

Table 30 Average partial effects (APEs) of pooled probit model estimates – livestock production and field crops production in the Germany

Variable	Livestock production			Field crops production		
	APE	Std.err.	P> z	APE	Std.err.	P> z
x_In_ORGANIC_FARM_NUTS				0.021	0.010	0.044
x_In_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	0.023	0.001	0.000	0.011	0.001	0.000
x_In_ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY_SHARE	0.014	0.004	0.000			
x_In_EXPECTED_WHEAT_PRICE_PREMIUM				0.005	0.002	0.004
x_In_LIVESTOCK_DENSITY	-0.036	0.019	0.062			
x_In_MFP				-0.105	0.022	0.000
x_In_RENTED_LAND_SHARE				-0.019	0.006	0.002
x_In_RENTAL_PRICE				0.015	0.005	0.001
x_In_FERTILISERS_HA				-0.005	0.003	0.064
x_In_PESTICIDES_HA				-0.007	0.002	0.000
x_In_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.037	0.023	0.117			
x_In_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	0.011	0.007	0.093			
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.049	0.020	0.016	0.044	0.017	0.012
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.161	0.057	0.004	0.254	0.135	0.060
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.033	0.038	0.378	0.016	0.020	0.418
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.042	0.041	0.304	0.029	0.020	0.145
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-0.093	0.050	0.063	-0.020	0.019	0.294

Source: own processing

Similarly to the case of the Czech Republic, the results indicate that the determinants of adoption vary both across different types of agricultural production and over the course of the diffusion process. It is therefore recommended that adoption behaviour be analysed using farming-type-specific models, as these allow for a more accurate identification of heterogeneous drivers of adoption and their evolution over time.

5. DISCUSSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The decision to adopt organic farming practices is influenced by a range of factors. Previous studies show that farmers' intentions to convert to organic farming depend on their perceptions of both economic and non-economic benefits, the costs and complexity of the conversion process (Läpple & Kelley, 2013), socio-psychological factors (Silva-Cortés et al., 2025), social pressure (Van et al., 2023), and institutional conditions (Pietola & Lansink, 2001).

This study identifies a significant neighbourhood effect in German agriculture. According to Sun (2013), previous adopters can trigger imitation, particularly under conditions of uncertainty. When farmers perceive their own information as insufficient, they rely more heavily on the observed behaviour of others. Through this process, initial beliefs are revised based on the experiences of prior adopters, and these updated beliefs become a key determinant of adoption intentions. Important mechanisms underlying this effect include the demonstrability of results, referring to farmers' ability to observe and verify the benefits of adopting organic practices on other farms (Silva-Cortés et al., 2025), and social learning, which enables farmers to share knowledge and provide support (Tran-Nam & Tiet, 2022).

In the Czech Republic, however, a neighbourhood effect has been identified only in field crop production. This finding suggests that policymakers could support the diffusion of organic farming by fostering networks of demonstration farms, where farmers can directly observe and learn from the experiences of successful organic producers.

Proximity to other organic producers may also facilitate participation in cooperatives, which can mitigate risks and enhance market power. By reducing exposure to price volatility and lowering transaction and marketing costs, cooperatives may contribute to more stable farm incomes and improved access to organic markets. In this way, cooperative participation may increase the propensity

to adopt organic and other environmentally sustainable production practices (Haldar & Damodaran, 2022). These findings therefore point to the potential benefits of policy support aimed at fostering cooperative structures and collective action among farmers, for example through targeted support for producer organizations and marketing cooperatives.

Naturally, there are also factors that may discourage farmers from converting to organic farming. These include, in particular, the time and financial costs associated with certification and compliance controls. Reducing administrative burdens and improving the efficiency of control systems is therefore important. In this regard, the digitalization of the agricultural sector and the use of smart technologies may represent effective tools.

Numerous studies have highlighted the role of social and personal norms in shaping farmers' decisions (Silva-Cortés et al., 2025; Tran-Nam & Tiet, 2022; Blaće et al., 2020). Farmers who are more concerned about environmental impacts, feel responsible for the consequences of their actions, and place greater emphasis on food safety are more likely to convert to organic farming. In our results, this pattern is partly reflected in the positive association between the share of environmental subsidies in total support, capturing prior participation in agri-environment-climate schemes, and the likelihood of conversion to organic farming. It is further consistent with the lower fertiliser and pesticide intensity observed in field crop production, indicating that environmentally oriented management practices often precede the transition to organic farming. From a policy perspective, these findings highlight the importance of fostering farmers' pro-environmental attitudes. Through education and extension services, improving farmers' awareness of the role of organic agriculture in ecosystem health, food security, and rural development may support higher rates of conversion.

Socio-economic factors also play a considerable role; however, many of these characteristics cannot be analysed using the FADN database. One such factor is the age of the farmer. Research shows that younger farmers tend to be more open-minded, less risk-averse, and more likely to possess better knowledge of organic farming, which makes them faster adopters (Tran-Nam & Tiet, 2022; Malá & Malý, 2013). Bojnec and Fertó (2025) further find that education is crucial for participation in agri-environmental and climate measures, of which organic farming is an integral part. Farmers with higher educational attainment are more likely to understand and value the benefits associated with organic agriculture (Latruffe & Nauges, 2014). From a policy perspective, many studies therefore emphasize the need for investments in education, training, extension services, capacity-building workshops, and peer-to-peer learning networks (Silva-Cortés et al., 2025).

Economic factors are also important. As shown in this study, farms with lower multifactor productivity are more likely to adopt organic farming. According to Xu et al. (2018), conversion to organic farming is often associated with dissatisfaction with the current production system and a perceived need for more fundamental change, whereas farmers who view their current situation as satisfactory are less inclined to undertake such substantial adjustments. Building on this reasoning, it can be argued that the most productive farms are less likely to convert to organic farming. Xu et al. (2018) further associate high productivity with farm size, concluding that larger farms tend to be less sensitive to external shocks and therefore less likely to experience dissatisfaction with the status quo. Consequently, large farms appear to be less likely to convert to organic farming (Latruffe & Nauges, 2014; Malá & Malý, 2013), a finding that is also supported by the results of this study. For large farms to convert, their economic conditions would therefore need to change substantially, for example through stricter environmental regulations or restrictions on the use of harmful inputs.

The economic situation of farms is strongly influenced by subsidies. Numerous studies have shown that financial incentives have significantly supported the expansion of organic farming (Jaime et al., 2016; Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Malá & Malý, 2013; Pietola & Lansink, 2001). Organic farming payments compensate farmers for income losses related to organic management practices, thereby making organic farming more attractive, particularly in areas with lower soil quality (Gailhard et al., 2015). Empirical evidence further indicates that, in both the Czech Republic and Germany, producers

located in mountainous, upland, and LFAs are more likely to engage in organic farming. This pattern is likely related to higher opportunity costs in more fertile regions, where conventional production systems tend to be more profitable (Schmidtner et al., 2012).

However, the findings of Chatzimichael et al. (2014) suggest that subsidy policies alone are less effective in promoting the diffusion of organic farming than information dissemination. Rather, subsidies appear to play a complementary role by accelerating the adoption process as information spreads and the number of adopters increases. As diffusion progresses, the remaining non-adopters tend to be more sceptical and therefore harder to convince. In this context, subsidies may help offset such scepticism by reducing perceived risks. Early adopters, who are typically more innovative and willing to take risks, are less dependent on financial support than later adopters, who are generally more cautious. These insights underscore that the timing of adoption is an important dimension in the analysis of adoption determinants. Decisions made at different stages of the diffusion process are associated with different sets of drivers and therefore require differentiated policy support (Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Läpple & Van Rensburg, 2011).

However, supply-side incentives alone are unlikely to be sufficient, as market factors play a crucial role in the development of organic farming (Alonso-Adame et al., 2025; Ambrosius et al., 2022; Smith & Marsden, 2004). In particular, growth in consumer demand represents a key driver of diffusion. According to Verburg et al. (2022) and Aschemann-Witzel and Zielke (2017), observed price differentials and limited consumer willingness to pay a premium constrain the growth of the organic sector. While higher prices are typically associated with higher quality in conventional products, organic products are more often perceived as involving additional costs rather than superior quality (Marian et al., 2014).

From a policy perspective, these challenges could be addressed by improving consumer information on price differences, the costs of organic production, and the environmental and social benefits of organic food. Enhancing consumers' knowledge, experience, and trust may help reduce misperceptions surrounding organic price premiums (Aschemann-Witzel & Zielke, 2017). In addition, increasing the availability of organic food in public institutions could support demand, provided that such initiatives are accompanied by adequate supply-chain and logistical infrastructure enabling farmers to deliver products that meet organic quality standards.

6. CONCLUSION

This study examines the diffusion and adoption of organic farming in two European Union Member States: the Czech Republic, a leading adopter of organic farming in Central Europe, and Germany, one of the largest organic farming markets in the EU. Specifically, the study analyses the diffusion process in both countries, identifies the determinants of observed adoption decisions, and examines how these determinants vary across different stages of the diffusion process. To achieve these objectives, the study employs the Bass diffusion model, estimated using official statistics from the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic and Germany's Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity, alongside probit modelling based on Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) data covering the period 2008–2021.

Although the expansion of organic farming constitutes a central policy objective in both countries, with national targets of 25% of agricultural land under organic management in the Czech Republic and 30% in Germany by 2030, projections based on the Bass diffusion model indicate that these targets are unlikely to be achieved under current conditions. This finding highlights the need for a more detailed understanding of adoption determinants and for policy measures that are better aligned with the underlying diffusion dynamics.

The results suggest that the Czech Republic and Germany are at different stages of the organic farming diffusion process, with innovation- and imitation-driven mechanisms exerting distinct influences across these stages. While imitation effects are more pronounced in Germany, they appear to be limited in the Czech Republic, where neighbourhood effects are observed mainly in field crop production. These differences point to variations in market maturity, institutional environments, and knowledge networks between the two countries.

Financial support schemes are positively associated with conversion to organic farming in both countries and appear to play a more prominent role than price premiums. At the same time, consumer demand emerges as a key driver, with market-related effects being stronger in Germany, reflecting the more advanced development of its organic food market. The findings further suggest that conversion is closely linked to farmers' pro-environmental orientations, as proxied by prior participation in agri-environment-climate measures and lower input intensity prior to conversion.

Finally, organic farming adoption in both countries is negatively associated with economic size, production specialisation, and labour intensity, with the magnitude of these associations increasing over time. This pattern underscores the heterogeneity of adopters across different stages of the diffusion process and suggests that late adopters face structurally different constraints than early adopters.

Overall, the results imply that policies aimed at accelerating the diffusion of organic farming should be stage-specific, combining financial incentives with information-based instruments and demand-side measures. Such an approach is likely to be more effective than uniform policy support in addressing the diverse barriers faced by farmers at different points in the adoption process.

The study makes three main contributions. First, it contributes to the existing literature by jointly analysing diffusion dynamics and farm-level adoption behaviour. Second, it provides novel comparative evidence for two EU Member States situated at different stages of the diffusion process. Third, it advances the literature by explicitly examining the stability and evolution of adoption determinants over time.

For policymakers, this study offers a comprehensive assessment of the current state of organic farming, projections of its future development, and a set of policy-relevant insights that can support the expansion of organic agriculture. However, further research is required to enable more precise targeting of policy instruments. For modellers, the study provides projections of organic farming diffusion based on land conversion, as well as an identification of monetary (e.g., subsidies, price

premiums) and non-monetary (e.g., farm structural characteristics, attitudes) drivers of conversion and their effects on adoption likelihood. Nevertheless, this exogenous approach does not fully capture the role of profitability in shaping farmers' decisions and should therefore be complemented by endogenous modelling approaches (Kremmydas et al., 2023).

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. First, the farm-level analysis relies on observable variables from FADN. Although FADN is representative of agricultural holdings in the EU, its representativeness does not specifically extend to organic farms, which may limit the generalisability of the results. Consequently, the relationships identified in this study should be interpreted as associations rather than causal effects.

Second, the analysis is limited to variables available in FADN and national statistics. Important drivers of organic conversion, such as farmers' age, education, knowledge of organic practices, and certification costs, are not captured and should be incorporated in future research when suitable data become available.

Third, neighbourhood effects are proxied using the number of organic farms at the NUTS2 level. While this indicator captures broad spatial patterns, a more precise assessment would require information on the physical distance between farms. Such spatially explicit analysis is not feasible within the FADN framework, as the dataset does not provide detailed location data.

A fourth limitation concerns the omission of state dependence effects. Conversion to organic farming represents a knowledge-intensive and potentially risky transformation, requiring not only changes in production management and employee training but also adjustments in supplier–buyer relationships associated with entry into new markets. As a result, it is relatively uncommon for producers to abandon organic farming shortly after adoption. However, identifying state dependence in panel data with unobserved heterogeneity is challenging, as unobserved farm-specific differences may generate spurious state dependence. While approaches proposed by Wooldridge (2005) and extended by Rabe-Hesketh and Skrondal (2013) offer potential solutions to the initial conditions problem, these methods require balanced panel data. Enforcing panel balance in the FADN dataset would lead to a substantial loss of observations¹¹. Alternative bias-corrected fixed-effects estimators (Fernández-Val and Weidner, 2016) address the incidental parameters problem but rely on within-farm variation, implying that farms with no change in organic status over the observation period cannot be included in the estimation (Arroyabe and Schumann, 2022). In the context of the FADN dataset, this would again result in the exclusion of a large number of potentially informative observations¹². For these reasons, state dependence is not explicitly modelled in this study.

Given the important role of research in supporting the development of organic farming, this study highlights the need for improved farm-level data collection. Developing more detailed data on organic farms, for example, as a dedicated sub-sample within the FADN framework, would strengthen future analyses and provide a more robust empirical basis for evidence-based policy design.

¹¹ In the Czech sample, the balanced panel consists of 4,455 observations for 495 farms (including 81 organic farms), with only 20 observed status changes. In the German sample, it comprises 16,137 observations for 1,793 farms (including 151 organic farms), with 64 changes in organic farming status over time. Even in the unbalanced dataset, only 1% of observations show a status change in the Czech sample and 0.5% in the German sample.

¹² For Germany, observations for 13,594 farms (including 767 organic farms) would be lost, while for the Czech Republic the corresponding figures are 1,889 farms (including 292 organic farms).

7. REFERENCES

- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 50(2): 179-211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Ambrosius, F. H. W., Kramer, M. R., Spiegel, A., Bokkers, E. A. M., Bock, B. B., & Hofstede, G. J. (2022). Diffusion of organic farming among Dutch pig farmers: An agent-based model. *Agricultural Systems* 197: 103336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2021.103336>
- Alonso-Adame, A., Farahbakhsh, S., Meensel, J. V., Marchand, F., & Passel, S. V. (2025). Factors to scale out innovative organic farming systems: A case study in Flanders region, Belgium. *Agricultural Systems* 224: 104219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2024.104219>
- Arroyabe, M. F., & Schumann, M. (2022). On the Estimation of True State Dependence in the Persistence of Innovation. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics* 84: 850–893. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obes.12482>
- Aschemann-Witzel, J., & Zielke, S. (2017). Can't Buy Me Green? A Review of Consumer Perceptions of and Behavior Toward the Price of Organic Food. *Journal of Consumer Affairs* 51: 211–251. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joca.12092>
- Aulakh, C. S., Sharma, S., Thakur, M., & Kaur, P. (2022). A review of the influences of organic farming on soil quality, crop productivity and produce quality. *Journal of Plant Nutrition* 45(12): 1884–1905. <https://doi-org.infozdroje.czu.cz/10.1080/01904167.2022.2027976>
- Bass, F. M. (1969). A New Product Growth for Model Consumer Durables. *Management Science* 15(5): 215–227. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.15.5.215>
- Bass, F. M., Krishnan, T. V., & Jain, D. C. (1994). Why the Bass Model Fits without Decision Variables. *Marketing Science* 13: 203–223. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mksc.13.3.203>
- Bell, A., Fairbrother, M., & Jones, K. (2019). Fixed and random effects models: making an informed choice. *Quality & Quantity* 53(2): 1051–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-018-0802-x>
- Bell, A., & Jones, K. (2015). Explaining Fixed Effects: Random Effects Modeling of Time-Series Cross-Sectional and Panel Data. *Political Science Research and Methods* 3(1): 133–153. <https://doi.org/10.1017/psrm.2014.7>
- Bengtsson, J., Ahnström, J., & Weibull, A.C., 2005. The effects of organic agriculture on biodiversity and abundance: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 42: 261-269. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2005.01005.x>
- Bjørkhaug, H., & Blekesaune, A., 2013. Development of organic farming in Norway: A statistical analysis of neighbourhood effects. *Geoforum* 45: 201–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2012.11.005>
- Blaće, A., Čuka, A., & Šiljković, Ž. (2020). How dynamic is organic? Spatial analysis of adopting new trends in Croatian agriculture. *Land Use Policy* 99: 105036. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.105036>
- Bland, J. R., & Cook, A. C. (2018). Random effects probit and logit: understanding predictions and marginal effects. *Applied Economics Letters* 26(2): 116–123. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2018.1441498>

- Bojnec, Š., & Fertő, I. (2025). Exploring the drivers of farm sustained participation in agri-environmental programmes. *Agricultural and Food Economics* 13: 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40100-025-00396-0>
- Boschiero, M., De Laurentiis, V., Caldeira, C., & Sala, S. (2023). Comparison of organic and conventional cropping systems: a systematic review of life cycle assessment studies. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review* 102: 107187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2023.107187>
- Cimino, O., Giarè, F., & Henke, R. (2025). Periurban Agriculture and Organic Farming: Investigating Synergies and Policy Implications. *Land* 14: 690. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land14040690>
- Chatzimichael, K., Genius, M., & Tzouvelekas, V. (2014). Informational cascades and technology adoption: Evidence from Greek and German organic growers. *Food Policy* 49: 186–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2014.08.001>
- Chmielinski, P., Pawlowska, A., Bocian, M., & Osuch, D. (2019). The land is what matters: factors driving family farms to organic production in Poland. *British Food Journal* 121: 1354–1367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/bfj-05-2018-0338>
- Cruz-Gonzalez, M., Fernández-Val, I., & Weidner, M. (2017). Bias corrections for probit and logit models with two-way fixed effects. *Stata Journal* 17(3): 517–545.
- Davis, F.D. (1989). Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology. *MIS Quarterly* 13 (3): 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Dessart, F.J., Barreiro-Hurlé, J., & van Bavel, R. (2019). Behavioural factors affecting the adoption of sustainable farming practices: a policy-oriented review. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 46: 417–471. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbz019>
- European Commission. (2020). Farm Accounting Data Network. An A to Z methodology. Available at: https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/befb6055-ab0c-4305-84fe-0c80c1c0553d/library/26cf03c0-c30a-4c19-8f46-bd56bfc59549?p=1&n=10&sort=modified_DESC Accessed December 15, 2025.
- European Commission. (2020). Assessing the Representativeness of FADN. Available at: <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/FarmEconomyFocus/FADNAssessment.html> Accessed December 15, 2025.
- European Parliament and Council. (2018). Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32018R0848>. Accessed December 15, 2025.
- Eurostat. (2025). *Organic crop area by agricultural production methods and crops* (Data set, code: org_cropar, last update: 12/12/2025 23:00). https://doi.org/10.2908/org_cropar Accessed December 15, 2025.
- Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity (Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft, BMLEH) (2024). 2030 Organic Strategy: National Strategy for 30% Organic Production in the Farming and Food Sector by 2030. <https://www.bmleh.de/EN/topics/farming/organic-farming/2030-organic-strategy.html>
- Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity (BMLEH). (2025). [Organic Farming and Food Production in Germany. BMLEH. Available at: <https://www.publikationen->

bundesregierung.de/pp-en/search-for-publications/organic-farming-in-germany-1891210. Accessed February 15, 2026.

Fernández-Val, I., & Weidner, M. (2016). Individual and time effects in nonlinear panel models with large N , T . *Journal of Econometrics* 192: 291–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconom.2015.12.014>

FiBL (2025). Organic retail sales. The Statistics.FiBL.org website maintained by the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland. Available at <https://statistics.fibl.org/europe/retail-sales-europe.html>. Accessed December 15, 2025.

Food and Agriculture Organization (2025). Evaluating the Potential Contribution of Organic Agriculture to Sustainability Goals. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/4/ac116e/ac116e02.htm>. Accessed December 10, 2025.

Gailhard, Ī. U., Bavorová, M., & Pirscher, F. (2015). Adoption of Agri-Environmental Measures by Organic Farmers: The Role of Interpersonal Communication. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension* 21: 127–148. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224x.2014.913985>

Giampieri, F., Mazzoni, L., Cianciosi, D., Alvarez-Suarez, J. M., Regolo, L., Sánchez-González, C., Capocasa, F., Xiao, J., Mezzetti, B., & Battino, M. (2022). Organic vs conventional plant-based foods: A review. *Food Chemistry* 383: 132352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2022.132352>

Haldar, T., & Damodaran, A. (2022). Can cooperatives influence farmer's decision to adopt organic farming? Agri-decision making under price volatility. *Environment, Development and Sustainability* 24: 5718-5742. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01679-4>

Heinze, S., & Vogel, A. (2017). Reversion from Organic to Conventional Agriculture in Germany: An Event History Analysis. *German Journal of Agricultural Economics* 66. <https://doi.org/10.30430/66.2017.1.13-25>

Hlaváčková, J., Rádlová, L., Havlíčková, B., Válková, T., Zouharová, D., & Šejnohová, H. (2025a). Statistical survey of organic farming: Basic statistical data–2024. Brno: Institute of Agricultural Economics and Information. 72 p. Available at: https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/-a82304---XZzhA1d5/statisticka-setreni-ekologickeho-zemedelstvi-2025?_linka=a682724 Accessed December 10, 2025.

Hlaváčková, J., Havlíčková, B., & Zouharová, D. (2025b). Report on the organic food market in the Czech Republic in 2023. Brno: Institute of Agricultural Economics and Information. 66 p. Available at: https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/-a71974---SUKKSoDJ/zprava-o-trhu-s-biopotravinami-v-cr-v-roce-2023?_linka=a651406 Accessed December 12, 2025.

Hrabalová, A., Dittrichová, M., & Koutná, K. (2011). Statistical survey of organic farming conducted in 2010. Brno: Institute of Agricultural Economics and Information. 47 p. Available at: https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/-a85246---7uTkLY0h/zakladni-statisticka-setreni-2010?_linka=a692534 Accessed December 13, 2025.

International Federation of Organic Agricultural Movements (2020). Principles of Organic Agriculture. Available at: <https://www.ifoam.bio/principles-organic-agriculture-brochure> Accessed December 10, 2025.

Jaime, M. M., Coria, J., & Liu, X. (2016). Interactions between CAP Agricultural and Agri-Environmental Subsidies and Their Effects on the Uptake of Organic Farming. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 98: 1114–1145. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajae/aaw015>

- Kallas, Z., Serra, T., & Gil, J.M. (2010). Farmers' objectives as determinants of organic farming adoption: the case of Catalonian vineyard production. *Agriculture Economics* 41: 409–423. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-0862.2010.00454.x>
- Kaufmann, P., Stagl, S., & Franks, D. W. (2009). Simulating the diffusion of organic farming practices in two New EU Member States. *Ecological Economics* 68: 2580–2593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2009.04.001>
- Kitano, S. (2025). The effect of social capital on organic farming and its heterogeneity. *Organic Agriculture* 15: 345–360. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-025-00501-z>
- Kremmydas, D., Ciaian, P., & Baldoni, E. (2023). Modeling conversion to organic agriculture with an EU-wide farm model. *Bio-based and Applied Economics* 12(4): 261–304. <https://doi.org/10.36253/bae-13925>
- Kuhnert, H. (2025). Current trends in the German organic sector. Available at: <https://www.thuenen.de/en/thuenen-topics/organic-farming/aktuelle-trends-der-deutschen-oekobranche> Accessed January 29, 2026.
- Kuhnert, H., & Offermann (2025). Income development of organic farms. Available at: <https://www.thuenen.de/en/thuenen-topics/organic-farming/aktuelle-trends-der-deutschen-oekobranche/einkommensentwicklung-im-oekolandbau> Accessed January 29, 2026.
- Kuminoff, N. V., & Wossink, A. (2010). Why Isn't More US Farmland Organic? *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 61: 240–258. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1477-9552.2009.00235.x>
- Lampkin, N., & Sanders, J. (2022). Policy support for organic farming in the European Union 2010-2020. Thünen Working Paper 200. <https://doi.org/10.3220/WP1663067402000>
- Latruffe, L., & Nauges, C. (2014). Technical efficiency and conversion to organic farming: the case of France. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 41: 227–253. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbt024>
- Läpple, D., & Kelley, H. (2013). Understanding the uptake of organic farming: Accounting for heterogeneities among Irish farmers. *Ecological Economics* 88: 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2012.12.025>
- Läpple, D. (2013). Comparing attitudes and characteristics of organic, former organic and conventional farmers: Evidence from Ireland. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems* 28: 329–337. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1742170512000294>
- Läpple, D., & Van Rensburg, T. (2011). Adoption of organic farming: are there differences between early and late adoption? *Ecological Economics* 70: 1406–1414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2011.03.002>
- Läpple, D. (2010). Adoption and Abandonment of Organic Farming: An Empirical Investigation of the Irish Drystock Sector. *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 61: 697–714. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1477-9552.2010.00260.x>
- Mahler, A., & Rogers, E. M. (1999). The diffusion of interactive communication innovations and the critical mass: the adoption of telecommunications services by German banks. *Telecommunications Policy* 23: 719–740. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0308-5961\(99\)00052-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0308-5961(99)00052-x)

- Malá, Z., & Malý, M. (2013). The determinants of adopting organic farming practices: a case study in the Czech Republic. *Agricultural Economics* 59(1): 19-28. [https://doi.org/ 10.17221/10/2012-AGRICECON](https://doi.org/10.17221/10/2012-AGRICECON)
- Marian, L., Chrysochou, P., Krystallis, A., & Thøgersen, J. (2014). The role of price as a product attribute in the organic food context: An exploration based on actual purchase data. *Food Quality and Preference* 37: 52–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2014.05.001>
- Massiani, J., & Gohs, A. (2015). The choice of Bass model coefficients to forecast diffusion for innovative products: An empirical investigation for new automotive technologies. *Research in Transportation Economics* 50: 17–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2015.06.003>
- Meemken, E. M., & Qaim, M. (2018). Organic agriculture, food security, and the environment. *Annual Review of Resource Economics* 10: 39-63. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-resource-100517-023252>
- Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic (2025). Statistical Surveys of Organic Farming 2006–2024. Available at: <https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/zemedelstvi/ekologicke-zemedelstvi/dokumenty-statistiky-formulare/statistika-a-pruzkumy>. Accessed December 10, 2025.
- Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic (2021). Czech Action Plan for Development of Organic Agriculture 2021–2027. Available at: https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/-q385015---gXWOgTLq/akcni-plan-cr-pro-rozvoj-ekologickeho?_linka=a293241 Accessed January 20, 2026.
- Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic (2015). Czech Action Plan for Development of Organic Agriculture 2016–2020. Available at: https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/-q385567---skLl1gXO/akcni-plan-ez-2016-2020?_linka=a293795 Accessed January 20, 2026.
- Moschitz, H., & Stolze, M. (2010). The influence of policy networks on policy output. A comparison of organic farming policy in the Czech Republic and Poland. *Food Policy* 35: 247–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2009.12.009>
- Möhring, N., Muller, A., & Schaub, S. (2024). Farmers' adoption of organic agriculture—a systematic global literature review, *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 51(4): 1012-1044. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbae025>
- Mundlak, Y. (1978). On the Pooling of Time Series and Cross Section Data. *Econometrica* 46(1): 69–85. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1913646>
- Padel, S. (2001). Conversion to Organic Farming: A Typical Example of the Diffusion of an Innovation?. *Sociologia Ruralis* 41: 40–61. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9523.00169>
- Pietola, K.S. & Lansink, A.O. (2001) Farmer response to policies promoting organic farming technologies in Finland. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 28(1): 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/28.1.1>
- Rabe-Hesketh, S., & Skrondal, A. (2013). Avoiding biased versions of Wooldridge's simple solution to the initial conditions problem. *Economics Letters* 120: 346–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2013.05.009>
- Reganold, J., & Wachter, J. (2016). Organic agriculture in the twenty-first century. *Nature Plants* 2: 15221. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nplants.2015.221>

- Rizzo, G., Migliore, G., Schifani, G., & Vecchio, R. (2024). Key factors influencing farmers' adoption of sustainable innovations: a systematic literature review and research agenda. *Organic Agriculture* 14: 57–84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-023-00440-7>
- Rogers, E. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations* (5th ed). New York: The Free Press. ISBN 9780743222099.
- Schmid, D., Renner, S., & Hoop, D. (2023). Exploring within- and between-effects of the factors influencing off-farm work decisions in Switzerland. *Agricultural Economics (Zemědělská ekonomika)* 69(10): 416–425. <https://doi.org/10.17221/233/2023-AGRICECON>
- Schmidtner, E., Lippert, Ch., Engler, B., Häring, A.M., Aurbacher, J., & Dabbert, S. (2012). Spatial distribution of organic farming in Germany: does neighbourhood matter?, *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 39(4): 661–683. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbr047>
- Shi-ming, M., & Sauerborn, J. (2006). Review of history and recent development of organic farming worldwide. *Agricultural Sciences in China* 5(3): 169–178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1671-2927\(06\)60035-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1671-2927(06)60035-7)
- Silva-Cortés, A., Villa-Enciso, E.M., & Rendón, A.M., Casdiego-Alzate, R., Tirado-Ballestas, I.P., Gallego, J.K. (2025). Assessing drivers of organic agriculture adoption among smallholder communities in Colombia: an application of the Technology acceptance model. *Organic Agriculture*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-025-00527-3>
- Simpson, J. R., Mishra, S., Talebian, A., & Golias, M. M. (2019). An estimation of the future adoption rate of autonomous trucks by freight organizations. *Research in Transportation Economics* 76: 100737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2019.100737>
- Singh, S.P., Priya, & Sajwan, K. (2023). Factors influencing the adoption of organic farming: a case of Middle Ganga River basin, India. *Organic Agriculture* 13: 193–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-022-00421-2>
- Skrondal, A., & Rabe-Hesketh, S. (2014). Handling Initial Conditions and Endogenous Covariates in Dynamic/Transition Models for Binary Data with Unobserved Heterogeneity, *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series C: Applied Statistics* 63(2): 211–237, <https://doi.org/10.1111/rssc.12023>
- Slijper, T., Mey, Y. de, Poortvliet, P. M., & Meuwissen, M. P. M. (2021). Quantifying the resilience of European farms using FADN. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 49: 121–150. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbab042>
- Smith, E., & Marsden, T. (2004). Exploring the 'limits to growth' in UK organics: beyond the statistical image. *Journal of Rural Studies* 20: 345–357. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0743-0167\(03\)00044-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0743-0167(03)00044-5)
- Sun, H. (2013). A Longitudinal Study of Herd Behavior in the Adoption and Continued Use of Technology. *MIS Quarterly* 37(4): 1013–1041. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43825780>
- Šejnohová, H., Rádlová, L., & Peterková, J. (2015). Statistical survey of organic farming: Basic statistical data–2014. Brno: Institute of Agricultural Economics and Information. 57 p. Available at: https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/-q371497---GYVBJjWa/statisticka-setreni-ekologickeho?_linka=a692634 Accessed December 12, 2025.
- Tran-Nam, Q., & Tiet, T. (2022). The role of peer influence and norms in organic farming adoption: Accounting for farmers' heterogeneity. *Journal of Environmental Management* 320: 115909. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115909>

- Urban, J. (2012). Organic Agriculture in the Czech Republic (Country Report 2011). In: Wiesinger, K. & Cais, K. (Eds.) *Angewandte Forschung und Beratung für den ökologischen Landbau in Bayern*, Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft, Freising, Schriftenreihe der Bayerischen Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft, no. 4/2012, pp. 169–178.
- Van, V. H., Heo, Y., & Doanh, N. K. (2023). ‘They convert, I also convert’: the neighborhood effects and tea farmers’ intention to convert to organic farming. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems* 38: e11. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1742170523000030>
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M., Davis, G., & Davis, F. (2003) User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. *MIS Quarterly* 27(3): 425–478. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036540>
- Verburg, R. W., Verberne, E., & Negro, S. O. (2022). Accelerating the transition towards sustainable agriculture: The case of organic dairy farming in the Netherlands. *Agricultural Systems* 198: 103368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2022.103368>
- Vona, B., & Kopáček, J. (2025). Milk: Situation and outlook report. Prague: Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic. ISBN 978-80-7434-811-2. 84 p. Available at: https://mze.gov.cz/public/portal/mze/-a77638---1ZgDKL4U/svz-mleko-2025?_linka=a666934 Accessed January 28, 2026.
- Willer, H., & Youssefi, M. (2006). Organic Agriculture in Germany and Switzerland. Country regional reports. Available at: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/8534/1/willer-youssefi-niggli-2006-ch-germany.pdf> Accessed February 20, 2026.
- Willer, H., Lampkin, N., & Reinecke, S. (2024). Germany: Organic sector factsheet – Production/market trends & policies. OrganicTargets4EU. Available at: <https://organictargets.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Germany-Digital-country-Factsheet.pdf> Accessed February 20, 2026.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2005). Simple solutions to the initial conditions problem in dynamic, nonlinear panel data models with unobserved heterogeneity. *Journal of Applied Econometrics* 20: 39–54. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.770>
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2019). Correlated random effects models with unbalanced panels. *Journal of Econometrics* 211: 137–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconom.2018.12.010>
- Xu, Q., Huet, S., Poix, C., Boisdon, I., & Deffuant, G. (2018). Why do farmers not convert to organic farming? Modeling conversion to organic farming as a major change. *Natural Resource Modeling* 31: 1–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nrm.12171>
- Zagata, L. (2010). How organic farmers view their own practice: results from the Czech Republic. *Agriculture and Human Values* 27: 277–290. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-009-9230-9>

8. APPENDIX

Table A1 Diffusion of organic farming in the Czech Republic and Germany

Year	Czechia			Germany		
	Total number of organic farms	Organic farmland [hectares]	Organic farmland as % of UAA	Total number of organic farms	Organic farmland [hectares]	Organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	3	480				
1991	132	17507	0.41			
1992	135	15371	0.36			
1993	141	15667	0.37			
1994	187	15818	0.37	5866	272139	1.6
1995	181	14982	0.35	6642	309487	1.8
1996	182	17022	0.4	7353	354171	2.1
1997	211	20239	0.47	8184	389693	2.3
1998	348	71621	1.67	9213	416518	2.4
1999	473	110756	2.58	10425	452327	2.6
2000	563	165699	3.86	12740	546023	3.2
2001	654	217869	5.09	14702	634998	3.7
2002	721	235136	5.5	15626	696978	4.1
2003	810	254995	5.97	16475	734027	4.3
2004	836	263299	6.16	16603	767891	4.5
2005	829	254982	5.98	17020	807406	4.7
2006	963	281535	6.61	17557	825538	4.9
2007	1318	312890	7.35	18703	865336	5.1
2008	1946	341632	8.04	19813	907786	5.4
2009	2689	398407	9.38	21047	947115	5.6
2010	3517	448202	10.55	21942	990702	5.9
2011	3920	482927	11.4	22506	1015626	6.1
2012	3923	488483	11.56	23032	1034355	6.2
2013	3926	493896	11.7	23271	1044955	6.3
2014	3885	493971	11.72	23398	1047633	6.3
2015	4115	494661	11.74	24736	1088838	6.5
2016	4243	506070	12.03	27132	1251320	7.5
2017	4399	520032	12.37	29395	1373157	8.2
2018	4596	538894	12.82	31713	1498027	9.0
2019	4690	540993	15.22	34110	1613834	9.7
2020	4665	543252	15.28	35396	1701895	10.3
2021	4794	558124	15.71	36307	1802231	10.9
2022	5050	575464	16.22	36862	1859560	11.2
2023	5345	595190	16.82	36680	1888999	11.4
2024	5565	604803	17.12			

Source: Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic (2025) and Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity (2025).

Table A2 Development of organic farming adoption in FADN samples

Year	Czechia							Germany						
	Conventional	Organic	Partially organic	Share of fully and partially organic farms in FADN	Share of organic farms - MA	Annual Change in FADN	Annual Change - MA	Conventional	Organic	Partially organic	Share of fully and partially organic farms in FADN	Share of organic farms - BMLEH	Annual Change in FADN	Annual Change - BMLEH
2008	1230	79	31	0.08	0.04			7477	328	36	0.05	0.05		
2009	1296	94	27	0.09	0.06	1.10	0.38	8470	383	27	0.05	0.06	1.13	1.06
2010	1248	123	58	0.13	0.08	1.50	0.31	8516	406	77	0.05	0.07	1.18	1.04
2011	1181	172	64	0.17	0.08	1.30	0.12	8397	463	62	0.06	0.08	1.09	1.03
2012	1109	205	55	0.19	0.08	1.10	0.00	8470	446	41	0.05	0.08	0.93	1.02
2013	1137	209	55	0.19	0.08	1.02	0.00	8381	492	55	0.06	0.08	1.12	1.01
2014	1099	213	51	0.19	0.08	1.00	-0.01	8310	463	50	0.06	0.08	0.94	1.01
2015	1111	224	31	0.19	0.09	0.97	0.06	8309	516	56	0.06	0.09	1.12	1.06
2016	1110	225	16	0.18	0.09	0.95	0.03	8146	548	127	0.08	0.10	1.18	1.10
2017	1089	243	11	0.19	0.09	1.05	0.04	8242	548	151	0.08	0.11	1.04	1.08
2018	1106	253	11	0.19	0.09	1.04	0.05	8100	590	194	0.09	0.12	1.12	1.08
2019	1052	220	16	0.18	0.10	0.89	0.02	7956	620	188	0.09	0.13	1.03	1.08
2020	939	196	10	0.18	0.10	0.87	-0.01	7469	632	170	0.10	0.14	0.99	1.04
2021	897	210	12	0.20	0.11	1.08	0.03	6978	175	591	0.10	0.16	0.96	1.03

Source: own processing

Table A3 Conversion to and Reversion from Organic Agriculture in FADN Samples

Year	Number of farms					
	Adoption of organic agriculture before the farm's first recorded year in FADN		Adoption of organic agriculture during the observed period		Reversion to conventional agriculture during the observed period	
	Czechia	Germany	Czechia	Germany	Czechia	Germany
2008	110	67				
2009	23	74	16	14	15	9
2010	33	90	44	31	2	10
2011	64	85	20	21	14	4
2012	61	75	0	17	3	7
2013	28	71	2	4	3	10
2014	42	68	1	15	4	11
2015	13	68	1	14	15	4
2016	20	97	2	88	14	5
2017	24	86	2	43	4	8
2018	14	108	5	48	6	5
2019	14	131	7	29	1	15
2020	20	142	0	33	0	8
2021	28	147	1	36	0	12
Total	494	1309	101	393	81	108

Source: own processing

Note: There are also 31 farms that both enter and exit organic agriculture in the Czech sample and 56 in the German sample during the observed period

Table A4 Description of Czech farms according to organic status (sample means and proportions in %)

	2008						2015						2021					
	Conventional		Partially organic		Fully organic		Conventional		Partially organic		Fully organic		Conventional		Partially organic		Fully organic	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
UAA [hectares]	552.7	761.0	780.2	749.3	329.3	408.5	616.0	865.1	612.1	749.2	207.7	310.9	682.0	920.0	271.1	300.2	242.9	319.5
Labour [AWU]	17.9	28.7	15.8	17.5	6.9	12.4	17.4	26.9	10.6	12.4	4.5	5.8	16.9	24.9	3.4	4.3	4.4	5.9
Share of rented land [%]	70.8	32.9	76.2	25.8	69.0	29.2	66.0	31.2	57.7	31.4	58.2	30.2	62.9	30.4	74.3	25.4	60.7	28.9
Unpaid labour share [%]	54.3	46.0	39.6	45.2	64.7	40.9	48.2	45.8	46.2	44.7	71.1	40.4	45.5	45.0	48.6	50.9	67.0	43.1
Output-input ratio [%]	99.2	38.2	79.8	30.6	68.7	32.0	100.1	33.9	84.0	26.2	72.7	36.0	102.2	37.3	74.6	39.3	65.6	35.0
Farm net value added [EUR/AWU]	15470.2	13955.2	18080.1	11972.0	24614.6	16680.0	20783.7	17251.8	24080.7	19269.5	17822.6	15444.9	31615.1	25145.7	37129.5	33610.3	24863.0	33091.3
Subsidies on investment [EUR/hectare]	10.6	87.8	27.3	106.8	4.6	35.0	320.8	5933.9	45.5	112.2	125.4	615.7	479.7	8414.4	79.3	199.0	166.1	1407.5
Direct payments [EUR/hectare]	201.0	55.6	202.7	59.8	226.5	37.7	277.2	454.4	237.3	39.1	258.6	84.2	285.7	476.9	264.6	87.7	271.5	179.2
Rural development payments [EUR/hectare]	83.4	210.8	147.0	125.0	290.0	110.6	55.2	97.5	165.3	113.9	287.8	176.9	1880.4	32176.7	255.2	171.1	330.9	137.3
Fixed assets [EUR/hectare]	6611.5	28250.3	5663.5	16433.1	2465.8	3743.0	14876.8	225075.3	2353.2	1428.4	3829.3	8537.7	33581.6	458280.0	4955.2	10191.3	4214.0	9028.4
Share of cereals on total arable land [%]	62.7	23.4	54.7	24.3	54.9	37.7	55.4	24.4	61.7	23.3	49.1	38.3	55.8	20.9	42.5	30.4	29.9	29.7
Share of cows on total livestock unit [%]	26.0	26.5	13.3	21.1	8.2	17.7	24.5	26.3	11.5	21.0	6.5	18.8	23.7	26.5	0.1	0.4	5.2	16.8
Altitude 300–599m a.s.l.	50.9		45.2		68.4		54.0		45.2		66.5		62.4		66.7		62.9	
Altitude ≥ 600m a.s.l.	5.9		25.8		24.1		4.1		25.8		23.7		4.8		0		28.6	
ANC_other	21.3		32.3		43.0		31.9		25.8		46.4		42.1		58.3		41.4	
ANC_mountain	9.1		45.6		22.6		8.6		38.7		36.6		9.1		16.7		41.9	
ES_3	14.6		16.2		29.1		10.8		22.6		23.2		10.5		16.7		23.3	
ES_4	18.1		12.9		24.1		14.6		16.1		20.1		16.5		25.0		25.2	
ES_5	24.1		22.6		24.1		28.9		9.7		25.9		27.5		33.3		30.0	
ES_6	30.6		38.7		5.1		41.2		45.2		6.7		41.9		5.7		16.7	
No. of farms	1,230		31		79		1,111		31		224		897		12		210	

Source: own processing

Note: ES denotes for FADN's ES6 categories: 3 represents Standard Output (SO) 25,000–<50,000 EUR; 4: 50,000–<100,000 EUR; 5: 100,000–<500,000 EUR; and 6: ≥ 500,000 EUR.

Table A5 Description of German farms according to organic status (sample means and proportions in %)

	2008						2015						2021					
	Conventional		Partially organic		Fully organic		Conventional		Partially organic		Fully organic		Conventional		Partially organic		Fully organic	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
UAA [hectares]	170.5	407.1	152.0	300.9	160.2	303.3	142.5	316.8	86.6	105.7	134.3	237.7	184.6	391.5	139.2	224.9	99.4	131.7
Labour [AWU]	4.1	9.2	3.8	5.6	3.3	5.0	3.3	7.7	2.3	2.4	2.9	3.8	3.6	8.1	2.6	4.5	2.1	2.3
Share of rented land [%]	59.0	30.8	58.8	32.4	65.7	29.4	57.4	28.9	63.7	28.0	60.7	28.5	59.9	27.6	65.6	25.6	60.4	28.3
Unpaid labour share [%]	76.4	31.7	72.2	34.3	70.9	32.4	79.5	29.4	80.2	29.4	74.0	31.3	76.8	31.4	75.0	31.2	84.4	28.0
Output-input ratio [%]	103.4	29.8	96.1	44.5	92.8	39.5	104.2	27.8	100.5	53.0	104.9	39.4	109.5	31.2	96.6	36.1	96.0	52.7
Farm net value added [EUR/AWU]	31886.9	29109.6	26945.6	32407.1	31991.8	25552.9	37724.8	35698.7	46813.8	69629.8	47488.3	33805.6	57071.5	50007.0	50277.0	43455.5	44443.7	51717.4
Subsidies on investment [EUR/hectare]	12.9	653.2	0.0	0.0	3.3	43.0	3.6	68.6	0.0	0.0	4.8	64.1	10.2	138.2	20.0	20.0	4.2	31.2
Direct payments [EUR/hectare]	321.9	944.7	297.0	163.9	270.0	94.6	309.8	200.0	307.9	121.2	309.3	119.4	328.7	311.9	301.2	301.2	338.8	243.7
Rural development payments [EUR/hectare]	37.7	72.4	202.9	227.4	256.5	133.4	36.8	78.0	261.8	188.8	327.8	163.7	51.4	85.3	358.8	358.8	271.8	207.5
Fixed assets [EUR/hectare]	28677.6	133711.4	24899.1	83953.3	10860.2	13728.7	21120.6	77609.4	13534.8	13996.0	13984.4	20404.9	16061.0	37652.6	12521.5	12521.5	14974.6	19666.9
Share of cereals on total arable land [%]	54.0	27.2	42.0	30.0	50.3	25.5	51.3	26.4	36.4	28.4	48.3	25.3	51.0	25.5	45.2	45.2	42.3	28.4
Share of cows on total livestock unit [%]	26.0	27.7	25.4	30.3	26.8	29.8	27.9	29.3	26.3	30.9	32.4	32.0	30.7	31.6	31.8	31.8	23.6	31.7
Altitude 300–599m a.s.l.	27.3		33.3		37.2		28.1		41.1		39.0		31.0		45.2		47.4	
Altitude ≥ 600m a.s.l.	3.3		22.2		9.2		3.6		8.9		12.2		3.0		12.4		7.4	
ANC_other	34.0		44.4		55.5		33.8		48.2		52.3		26.7		41.3		34.9	
ANC_mountain	1.0		11.1		4.6		1.2		7.1		7.6		5.2		16.8		10.3	
ES_4	18.4		25.0		27.7		16.0		26.8		26.4		14.4		25.4		24.0	
ES_5	59.9		50.0		47.3		61.0		48.2		51.7		57.2		52.8		44.6	
ES_6	15.4		11.1		11.6		16.1		5.4		9.9		19.0		6.8		6.3	
No. of farms	7,477		36		328		8,309		56		516		6,978		591		175	

Source: own processing

Note: ES denotes for FADN's ES6 categories: 3 represents Standard Output (SO) 25,000–<50,000 EUR; 4: 50,000–<100,000 EUR; 5: 100,000–<500,000 EUR; and 6: ≥ 500,000 EUR.

Table A6 Structure of the Czech sample for panel probit model

TF	Type	Numbers of observations													
		2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
15	CF	192	246	261	274	266	294	309	333	329	317	303	301	220	202
	OF	5	2	4	5	4	4	12	10	5	5	5	3	3	0
16	CF	80	96	114	114	105	112	107	93	115	115	115	105	72	60
	OF	0	0	6	5	6	6	10	14	7	4	5	6	2	3
20	CF	22	45	84	75	78	75	78	56	48	42	43	31	4	3
	OF	2	1	1	3	3	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
35	CF	21	26	30	31	31	39	35	36	36	34	27	21	21	20
	OF	1	2	2	4	3	5	5	6	6	5	4	5	4	4
36	CF	18	22	25	21	26	26	23	23	21	21	21	16	13	9
	OF	0	0	0	2	4	7	11	10	11	11	13	14	3	3
38	CF	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3
	OF	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
45	CF	107	106	122	125	116	126	114	112	112	100	118	118	119	101
	OF	7	10	18	25	26	23	23	19	14	18	13	15	15	12
48	CF	4	4	4	4	6	4	5	4	5	8	7	3	5	3
	OF	8	8	12	18	25	31	29	25	24	22	22	17	12	13
49	CF	53	56	60	45	51	47	47	47	56	51	57	54	40	40
	OF	37	45	71	96	120	126	116	125	138	149	156	138	113	98
50	CF	17	15	16	15	9	17	19	20	15	17	19	14	9	9
	OF	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
60	CF	11	9	12	14	15	16	9	14	13	15	10	13	9	9
	OF	0	1	2	2	1	3	4	1	2	3	1	1	0	0
70	CF	36	40	42	41	30	32	30	33	28	37	36	31	26	22
	OF	2	1	4	5	4	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	0
80	CF	255	314	319	314	303	278	266	287	293	291	281	282	244	220
	OF	17	25	40	40	40	36	34	21	16	22	22	20	13	16

Source: FADN

Note: TF denotes the type of farming: 15 = specialist cereals, oilseeds, and protein crops; 16 = general field cropping; 20 = specialist horticulture; 35 = specialist vineyards; 36 = specialist fruit and citrus fruit; 38 = permanent crops combined; 45 = specialist dairying; 48 = specialist sheep and goats; 49 = specialist cattle; 50 = specialist granivores; 60 = mixed crops; 70 = mixed livestock; 80 = mixed crops and livestock. OF denotes organic farming, including both organic statuses, i.e. full and partial adoption.

Table A7 Structure of the German sample for panel probit model

		Numbers of observations													
TF	Type	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
15	CF	605	764	828	835	993	1035	1015	1007	1028	1061	1004	971	877	793
	OF	23	21	21	25	31	27	22	28	28	42	55	61	55	48
16	CF	525	659	723	770	737	664	659	679	731	788	855	890	804	731
	OF	25	44	48	45	43	36	37	44	41	63	64	61	64	
20	CF	418	456	482	436	427	390	364	325	241	186	172	130	121	84
	OF	14	16	18	18	21	23	16	15	17	16	14	11	9	8
35	CF	367	400	419	396	401	404	405	416	392	382	393	394	366	332
	OF	9	9	17	13	15	18	27	30	34	32	33	33	32	16
36	CF	137	151	158	154	143	129	121	114	113	102	85	81	67	49
	OF	4	4	5	5	7	7	6	9	9	9	11	7	7	6
38	CF	23	22	32	26	25	26	24	29	25	28	35	31	29	20
	OF	0	0	3	3	3	2	1	3	2	3	6	1	5	1
45	CF	1402	1614	1704	1585	1594	1722	1793	1928	1951	2126	2188	2174	1913	1688
	OF	101	124	132	131	126	133	142	175	216	230	251	259	239	212
48	CF	40	44	54	53	34	67	91	93	88	83	44	49	47	38
	OF	9	11	14	16	7	19	19	19	22	24	19	22	21	20
49	CF	441	494	486	455	295	478	523	567	583	587	583	606	534	471
	OF	39	53	60	60	37	70	75	74	102	117	130	132	113	102
50	CF	900	1116	1171	1083	983	812	795	806	791	760	791	763	633	502
	OF	12	14	15	17	17	14	15	14	15	16	25	26	26	16
60	CF	94	107	138	136	152	142	140	139	124	117	144	129	104	82
	OF	2	5	8	9	6	8	12	7	7	5	6	9	3	4
70	CF	412	449	425	397	368	353	304	285	262	234	231	230	182	134
	OF	14	17	22	18	12	10	11	9	11	15	14	14	10	10
80	CF	962	1047	1086	900	1030	988	1019	1023	1013	1040	891	849	737	640
	OF	57	52	63	61	64	63	59	74	78	72	75	78	67	65

Source: FADN

Note: TF denotes the type of farming: 15 = specialist cereals, oilseeds, and protein crops; 16 = general field cropping; 20 = specialist horticulture; 35 = specialist vineyards; 36 = specialist fruit and citrus fruit; 38 = permanent crops combined; 45 = specialist dairying; 48 = specialist sheep and goats; 49 = specialist cattle; 50 = specialist granivores; 60 = mixed crops; 70 = mixed livestock; 80 = mixed crops and livestock. OF denotes organic farming, including both organic statuses, i.e. full and partial adoption.

Table A8 Descriptive statistics of selected variables (2008–2021) – the Czech Republic

Variable	Organic farms			Conventional farms		
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs
ECONOMIC_SIZE [EUR SO]	213.4	440.8	2,768	872.5	1363.6	13,801
LAND [hectares]	303.6	455.9	2,768	627.4	837.1	13,801
LABOUR [AWU]	6.3	10.2	2,768	17.7	26.2	13,801
CEREALS_ARABLE [%]	28.9	35.8	2,768	52.9	26.8	13,801
COWS_TLU [%]	7.3	18.5	2,768	17.3	24.8	13,801
RENTED_LAND [%]	61.6	29.2	2,768	66.5	31.7	13,801
RENTAL_PRICE [EUR/hectares]	77.9	566.0	2,768	178.0	3015.0	13,801
LABOUR_INTENSITY [AWU/100hectares]	4.8	26.5	2,768	20.8	181.0	13,801
FIXED_ASSETS [EUR/hectares]	3451.9	16802.9	2,768	9799.3	108103.6	13,801
DEBT_TO_ASSETS_RATIO	0.18	0.27	2,768	0.20	0.23	13,801
OTHER_ACTIVITIES_SHARE [%]	8.8	14.8	2,768	6.0	10.7	13,801
UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE [%]	65.6	43.3	2,768	47.9	45.8	13,801
TOTAL_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	567.9	171.7	2,768	1139.7	32104.7	13,801
RURAL_DEVELOPMENT_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	289.9	134.2	2,768	299.2	10638.4	13,801
ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	200.1	127.5	2,768	273.2	10638.7	13,801
INVESTMENT_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	64.0	425.9	2,768	222.6	8852.9	13,801

Source: Own processing

Table A9 Descriptive statistics of selected variables (2008–2021) – Germany

Variable	Organic farms			Conventional farms		
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs
ECONOMIC_SIZE [EUR SO]	202.2	313.2	7,133	379.4	717.4	99,164
LAND [hectares]	130.9	237.0	7,133	154.7	350.2	99,164
LABOUR [AWU]	2.7	4.1	7,133	3.5	7.9	99,164
CEREALS_ARABLE [%]	35.6	30.3	7,133	46.6	29.5	99,164
COWS_TLU [%]	24.2	30.8	7,133	19.5	27.7	99,164
RENTED_LAND [%]	61.6	28.3	7,133	58.0	29.1	99,164
RENTAL_PRICE [EUR/hectares]	328.1	2356.7	7,133	508.1	6226.9	99,164
LABOUR_INTENSITY [AWU/100hectares]	7.7	41.6	7,133	21.3	134.2	99,164
FIXED_ASSETS [EUR/hectares]	12365.5	22008.1	7,133	20673.8	93373.4	99,164
DEBT_TO_ASSETS_RATIO	0.26	0.32	7,133	0.25	0.56	99,164
OTHER_ACTIVITIES_SHARE [%]	10.9	15.3	7,133	7.6	11.2	99,164
UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE [%]	75.5	30.6	7,133	78.5	30.2	99,164
TOTAL_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	648.5	377.5	7,133	420.2	846.5	99,164
RURAL_DEVELOPMENT_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	303.5	198.9	7,133	41.4	83.2	99,164
ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	267.2	190.6	7,133	27.0	69.9	99,164
INVESTMENT_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	13.4	183.5	7,133	15.2	1502.4	99,164

Source: Own processing

Table A10 Descriptive statistics of the explanatory variables in the panel probit model – the Czech Republic

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs	Winsorised data	
						Mean	Std. Dev.
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.167	0.373	0.000	1.000	16,569	0.167	0.373
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.415	1.664	2.085	10.234	16,569	5.414	1.657
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-1.833	2.580	-6.908	0.001	16,569	-1.833	2.580
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-4.903	2.867	-6.908	0.000	16,569	-4.903	2.867
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-0.981	1.864	-6.908	0.001	16,569	-0.981	1.864
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	3.325	3.135	-6.908	12.124	16,569	3.312	3.117
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	1.207	1.170	-1.889	9.313	16,569	1.205	1.147
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	7.765	1.095	-6.908	15.683	16,569	7.767	1.010
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-2.552	1.759	-6.908	1.809	16,569	-2.555	1.754
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-4.576	2.234	-6.908	0.019	16,569	-4.578	2.230
x_ln_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-2.853	3.252	-6.908	0.001	15,569	-2.853	3.252
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.562	0.496	0.000	1.000	16,569	0.562	0.496
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.083	0.276	0.000	1.000	16,569	0.083	0.276
z_ANC_other	0.345	0.476	0.000	1.000	16,569	0.345	0.476
z_ANC_mountain	0.144	0.352	0.000	1.000	16,569	0.144	0.352
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.414	0.493	0.000	1.000	16,569	0.414	0.493
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	3.402	0.535	-6.908	4.159	15,672	3.402	0.535
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	-4.790	0.339	-5.203	-4.034	16,569	-4.790	0.339

Source: Own processing

Note: x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1) includes data from 2007.

Table A11 Descriptive statistics of the explanatory variables in the panel probit model – Germany

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs	Winsorised data	
						Mean	Std. Dev.
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.067	0.250	0.000	1.000	106,297	0.067	0.250
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.285	1.008	3.220	10.033	106,297	5.282	0.995
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-1.950	2.593	-6.908	0.001	106,297	-1.950	2.593
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-4.633	3.001	-6.908	0.001	106,297	-4.633	3.001
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-0.984	1.585	-6.908	0.001	106,297	-0.984	1.585
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	4.897	3.061	-6.908	14.229	106,297	4.890	3.051
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	1.135	1.249	-3.075	8.530	106,297	1.131	1.215
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	9.075	1.200	-6.908	15.532	106,297	9.081	1.097
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-2.376	1.760	-6.908	4.267	106,297	-2.381	1.751
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-3.587	1.647	-6.908	0.001	106,297	-3.589	1.643
x_ln_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-0.605	1.521	-8.908	0.001	106,297	-0.605	1.521
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.293	0.455	0.000	1.000	106,297	0.293	0.455
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.039	0.195	0.000	1.000	106,297	0.039	0.195
z_ANC_other	0.341	0.474	0.000	1.000	106,297	0.341	0.474
z_ANC_mountain	0.025	0.157	0.000	1.000	106,297	0.025	0.157
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.521	0.500	0.000	1.000	106,297	0.521	0.500
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	2.709	0.790	0.000	4.277	99,064	2.709	0.790
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	-3.111	0.189	-3.405	-2.688	106,297	-3.111	0.189

Source: Own processing

Note: x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1) includes data from 2007.

Table A12 Descriptive statistics of the explanatory variables in the cross-sectional probit models – the Czech Republic

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs	Winsorised data	
						Mean	Std. Dev.
2008							
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.085	0.279	0.000	1.000	1,295	0.085	0.279
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.089	1.608	2.103	8.688	1,295	5.088	1.602
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-1.425	2.327	-6.908	0.001	1,295	-1.425	2.327
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-4.601	2.955	-6.908	-0.038	1,295	-4.601	2.955
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-0.932	1.939	-6.908	0.001	1,295	-0.932	1.939
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	2.803	3.110	-6.908	10.917	1,295	2.791	3.094
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	1.168	1.046	-0.953	6.435	1,295	1.166	1.026
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	7.790	1.005	4.726	13.366	1,295	7.789	0.974
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-2.831	1.840	-6.908	0.025	1,295	-2.831	1.838
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-4.850	2.076	-6.908	-0.386	1,295	-4.851	2.072
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.510	0.500	0.000	1.000	1,295	0.510	0.500
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.076	0.265	0.000	1.000	1,295	0.076	0.265
z_ANCESTRY_other	0.236	0.425	0.000	1.000	1,295	0.236	0.425
z_ANCESTRY_mountain	0.120	0.325	0.000	1.000	1,295	0.120	0.325
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.451	0.498	0.000	1.000	1,295	0.451	0.498
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	2.665	0.363	0.001	3.367	1,255	2.665	0.363
2015							
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.187	0.390	0.000	1.000	1,366	0.187	0.390
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.479	1.682	2.151	9.472	1,366	5.478	1.674
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-2.000	2.700	-6.908	0.001	1,366	-2.000	2.700
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-5.125	2.778	-6.908	0.000	1,366	-5.125	2.778
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-1.072	1.953	-6.908	0.001	1,366	-1.072	1.953
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	3.277	3.287	-6.908	11.441	1,366	3.262	3.267
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	1.251	1.229	-1.469	9.287	1,366	1.307	1.305
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	7.461	2.075	-6.908	15.677	1,366	7.453	2.054
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-2.454	1.738	-6.908	1.072	1,366	-2.458	1.732
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-4.526	2.291	-6.908	-0.561	1,366	-4.526	2.291
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.559	0.497	0.000	1.000	1,366	0.559	0.497
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.078	0.269	0.000	1.000	1,366	0.078	0.269
z_ANCESTRY_other	0.341	0.474	0.000	1.000	1,366	0.341	0.474
z_ANCESTRY_mountain	0.139	0.346	0.000	1.000	1,366	0.139	0.346
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.419	0.494	0.000	1.000	1,366	0.419	0.494
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	3.620	0.373	2.833	4.078	1,366	3.620	0.373
2021							
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.626	0.484	0.626	0.484	1,119	0.198	0.399
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	0.092	0.289	0.092	0.289	1,119	5.510	1.662
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	0.422	0.494	0.422	0.494	1,119	-1.816	2.508
x_ln_COWS_TLU	0.154	0.361	0.154	0.361	1,119	-5.098	2.796
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.388	0.487	0.388	0.487	1,119	-1.086	1.930
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	3.472	0.510	3.472	0.510	1,119	3.659	3.384
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	0.626	0.484	0.626	0.484	1,119	1.011	0.996
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	0.092	0.289	0.092	0.289	1,119	7.487	1.733
x_ln_OA_SHARE	0.422	0.494	0.422	0.494	1,119	-2.454	1.776
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	0.154	0.361	0.154	0.361	1,119	-4.282	2.322
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.388	0.487	0.388	0.487	1,119	0.388	0.487
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	3.472	0.510	3.472	0.510	1,119	3.472	0.510
z_ANCESTRY_other	0.626	0.484	0.626	0.484	1,119	0.626	0.484
z_ANCESTRY_mountain	0.092	0.289	0.092	0.289	1,119	0.092	0.289
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.422	0.494	0.422	0.494	1,119	0.422	0.494
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	0.154	0.361	0.154	0.361	1,119	0.154	0.361

Source: Own processing

Table A13 Descriptive statistics of the explanatory variables in the cross-sectional probit models – Germany

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs	Winsorised data	
						Mean	Std. Dev.
2008							
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.046	0.210	0.000	1.000	7,838	0.046	0.210
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.309	1.031	3.231	10.033	7,838	5.307	1.018
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-1.933	2.645	-6.908	0.001	7,838	-1.933	2.645
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-4.588	2.977	-6.908	-0.016	7,838	-4.588	2.977
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-1.051	1.750	-6.908	0.001	7,838	-1.051	1.750
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	4.549	3.297	-6.908	13.579	7,838	4.543	3.289
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	1.369	1.434	-1.512	8.585	7,838	1.368	1.414
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	9.165	1.388	-6.908	15.532	7,838	9.178	1.268
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-2.270	1.693	-6.908	2.993	7,838	-2.274	1.684
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-4.103	1.710	-6.908	-0.006	7,838	-4.106	1.705
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.277	0.448	0.000	1.000	7,838	0.277	0.448
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.036	0.187	0.000	1.000	7,838	0.036	0.187
z_ANCESTRY_other	0.350	0.477	0.000	1.000	7,838	0.350	0.477
z_ANCESTRY_mountain	0.012	0.109	0.000	1.000	7,838	0.012	0.109
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.473	0.499	0.000	1.000	7,838	0.473	0.499
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	2.148	0.934	-6.908	3.178	7,838	2.148	0.934
2015							
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.064	0.245	0.000	1.000	8,878	0.064	0.245
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.333	0.990	3.262	9.530	8,878	5.330	0.977
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-1.961	2.591	-6.908	0.001	8,878	-1.961	2.591
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-4.597	3.020	-6.908	0.001	8,878	-4.597	3.020
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-0.998	1.590	-6.908	0.001	8,878	-0.998	1.590
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	4.954	3.091	-6.908	13.060	8,878	4.944	3.077
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	1.135	1.242	-2.281	8.112	8,878	1.131	1.205
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	9.118	1.127	-3.184	15.052	8,878	9.121	1.058
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-2.366	1.811	-6.908	3.416	8,878	-2.371	1.801
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-3.472	1.582	-6.908	-0.009	8,878	-3.474	1.578
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.288	0.453	0.000	1.000	8,878	0.288	0.453
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.041	0.199	0.000	1.000	8,878	0.041	0.199
z_ANCESTRY_other	0.350	0.477	0.000	1.000	8,878	0.350	0.477
z_ANCESTRY_mountain	0.016	0.127	0.000	1.000	8,878	0.016	0.127
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.547	0.498	0.000	1.000	8,878	0.547	0.498
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	2.631	1.110	-6.908	3.892	8,878	2.631	1.110
2021							
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.099	0.298	0.000	1.000	7,741	0.099	0.298
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.341	1.078	3.219	9.631	7,741	5.339	1.067
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-1.899	2.515	-6.908	0.001	7,741	-1.899	2.515
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-4.558	3.059	-6.908	0.001	7,741	-4.558	3.059
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-0.834	1.332	-6.908	0.001	7,741	-0.834	1.332
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	5.261	2.620	-6.908	11.352	7,741	5.254	2.610
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	0.886	1.020	-2.577	8.036	7,741	0.879	0.965
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	8.935	1.039	-5.454	14.379	7,741	8.940	0.974
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-2.369	1.779	-6.908	2.850	7,741	-2.373	1.773
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-3.322	1.541	-6.908	0.001	7,741	-3.324	1.537
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.325	0.468	0.000	1.000	7,741	0.325	0.468
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.038	0.192	0.000	1.000	7,741	0.038	0.192
z_ANCESTRY_other	0.280	0.449	0.000	1.000	7,741	0.280	0.449
z_ANCESTRY_mountain	0.062	0.241	0.000	1.000	7,741	0.062	0.241
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.517	0.500	0.000	1.000	7,741	0.517	0.500
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS	3.025	0.878	-6.908	4.220	7,741	3.025	0.878

Source: Own processing

Table A14 Descriptive statistics of selected variables (pooled model) – the Czech Republic

Variable	Organic farms			Conventional farms		
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs
ECONOMIC_SIZE [EUR SO]	444.8	769.5	79	737.8	1577.2	558
LAND [hectares]	542.3	793.5	79	485.7	1036.3	558
LABOUR [AWU]	13.1	22.4	79	14.4	29.1	558
CEREALS_ARABLE [%]	40.1	35.4	79	40.0	35.2	558
COWS_TLU [%]	13.8	22.8	79	8.9	20.0	558
RENTED_LAND [%]	66.1	30.8	79	54.2	39.6	558
RENTAL_PRICE [EUR/hectares]	50.0	65.9	79	339.5	5201.4	558
FERTILISERS_HA [EUR/hectares]	64.3	114.5	79	244.6	481.0	558
PESTICIDES_HA [EUR/hectares]	97.0	212.6	79	370.0	716.8	558
LIVESTOCK_DENSITY [TLU/hectares]	0.39	0.30	79	1.54	15.73	558
MFP	0.78	0.34	79	1.05	0.42	558
FIXED_ASSETS [EUR/hectares]	6254.7	17426.6	79	21665.0	51938.6	558
DEBT_TO_ASSETS_RATIO	0.20	0.23	79	0.17	0.22	558
OTHER_ACTIVITIES_SHARE [%]	6.9	11.7	79	4.9	10.8	558
LABOUR_INTENSITY [AWU/100hectares]	9.1	28.4	79	51.9	128.6	558
UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE [%]	54.3	47.0	79	60.5	43.7	558
TOTAL_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	454.4	278.1	79	309.4	440.0	558
RURAL_DEVELOPMENT_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	173.9	149.1	79	62.2	123.7	558
ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	104.8	140.8	79	46.9	113.6	558
INVESTMENT_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	350.5	1992.2	79	289.9	3576.1	558

Source: Own processing

Table A15 Descriptive statistics of selected variables (pooled model) – Germany

Variable	Organic farms			Conventional farms		
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Obs
ECONOMIC_SIZE [EUR SO]	203.0	439.3	324	367.5	697.2	2,334
LAND [hectares]	104.2	190.7	324	140.2	324.8	2,334
LABOUR [AWU]	2.3	4.8	324	3.6	7.5	2,334
CEREALS_ARABLE [%]	35.8	32.0	324	42.5	31.5	2,334
COWS_TLU [%]	20.2	28.5	324	16.1	26.3	2,334
RENTED_LAND [%]	59.3	28.4	324	57.9	32.0	2,334
RENTAL_PRICE [EUR/hectares]	672.8	6177.2	324	467.7	1988.6	2,334
FERTILISERS_HA [EUR/hectares]	64.0	93.6	324	316.5	1949.5	2,334
PESTICIDES_HA [EUR/hectares]	86.5	197.4	324	211.2	592.9	2,334
LIVESTOCK_DENSITY [TLU/hectares]	0.88	0.98	324	1.32	5.18	2,334
MFP	0.97	0.37	324	1.06	0.37	2,334
FIXED_ASSETS [EUR/hectares]	12482.0	16412.9	324	21167.9	63039.0	2,334
DEBT_TO_ASSETS_RATIO	0.26	0.40	324	0.33	0.91	2,334
OTHER_ACTIVITIES_SHARE [%]	10.1	14.4	324	8.5	13.3	2,334
LABOUR_INTENSITY [AWU/100hectares]	5.3	9.8	324	21.5	108.8	2,334
UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE [%]	83.6	26.0	324	74.5	31.7	2,334
TOTAL_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	481.6	235.7	324	395.2	315.4	2,334
RURAL_DEVELOPMENT_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	131.5	169.0	324	34.0	73.4	2,334
ENVIRONMENTAL_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	101.1	155.5	324	23.2	60.1	2,334
INVESTMENT_SUBSIDY [EUR/hectares]	0.27	4.85	324	157.6	7375.1	2,334

Source: Own processing

Table A16 Descriptive statistics of the explanatory variables in the pooled probit model – the Czech Republic

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs	Winsorised data	
						Mean	Std. Dev.
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.124	0.330	0.000	1.000	637	0.124	0.330
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.130	1.665	2.123	9.515	637	5.127	1.652
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-2.960	3.145	-6.908	0.001	637	-2.960	3.145
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-5.682	2.448	-6.908	-0.064	637	-5.682	2.448
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-1.988	2.827	-6.908	0.001	637	-1.988	2.827
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	1.467	4.842	-6.908	11.710	637	1.449	4.815
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	1.341	2.771	-6.908	6.930	637	1.340	2.768
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	7.387	4.065	-6.908	12.983	637	7.383	4.059
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-3.021	1.926	-6.908	0.315	637	-3.023	1.923
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-5.015	2.190	-6.908	-0.052	637	-5.017	2.185
x_ln_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-2.161	3.023	-6.908	0.001	637	-2.161	3.023
x_ln_PESTICIDE_HA	3.900	3.219	-6.908	8.521	637	7.275	3.575
x_ln_FERTILISER_HA	4.098	3.193	-6.908	8.675	637	6.807	3.693
x_ln_LIVESTOCK_DENSITY	-3.968	3.125	-6.908	5.481	637	-3.990	3.072
x_ln_MFP	-0.052	0.384	-1.723	1.576	637	-0.053	0.361
x_ln_ENVI_SUBSIDY_SHARE	-4.468	2.513	-6.908	-0.258	637	-4.468	2.513
x_ln_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	-4.796	4.129	-6.908	6.368	637	-4.796	4.129
x_ln_WHEAT_PRICE_PREMIUM	-5.269	3.757	-6.908	4.878	564	-5.269	3.757
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.441	0.497	0.000	1.000	637	0.441	0.497
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.044	0.205	0.000	1.000	637	0.044	0.205
z_ANC_other	0.228	0.420	0.000	1.000	637	0.228	0.420
z_ANC_mountain	0.072	0.259	0.000	1.000	637	0.072	0.259
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.482	0.500	0.000	1.000	637	0.482	0.500

Source: Own processing

Table A17 Descriptive statistics of the explanatory variables in the pooled probit model – Germany

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs	Winsorised data	
						Mean	Std. Dev.
y_ORGANIC_FARMING	0.122	0.327	0.000	1.000	2,658	0.122	0.327
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	5.193	1.063	3.221	9.510	2,658	5.189	1.051
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-2.381	2.831	-6.908	0.001	2,658	-2.381	2.831
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-4.992	2.875	-6.908	-0.023	2,658	-4.992	2.875
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	-1.122	1.824	-6.908	0.001	2,658	-1.122	1.824
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	4.566	3.544	-6.908	11.620	2,658	4.558	3.534
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	1.251	1.335	-1.980	7.401	2,658	1.249	1.305
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	9.046	1.465	-6.908	14.458	2,658	9.072	1.251
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS	-2.219	1.820	-6.908	3.628	2,658	-2.225	1.809
x_ln_OA_SHARE	-3.556	1.724	-6.908	-0.016	2,658	-3.557	1.721
x_ln_UNPAID_LABOUR_SHARE	-0.659	1.541	-6.908	0.001	2,658	-0.659	1.541
x_ln_PESTICIDE_HA	3.684	3.497	-6.908	11.045	2,658	6.849	4.265
x_ln_FERTILISER_HA	3.245	3.779	-6.908	9.656	2,658	5.856	4.407
x_ln_LIVESTOCK_DENSITY	-2.353	3.445	-6.908	5.233	2,658	-2.359	3.435
x_ln_MFP	-0.006	0.355	-2.787	1.820	2,658	-0.003	0.326
x_ln_ENVI_SUBSIDY_SHARE	-5.229	2.339	-6.908	0.001	2,658	-5.229	2.339
x_ln_EXPECTED_SUBSIDY_GAIN	-4.504	4.538	-6.908	8.188	2,658	-4.504	4.538
x_ln_WHEAT_PRICE_PREMIUM	0.413	4.683	-6.908	5.402	522	0.413	4.683
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.262	0.440	0.000	1.000	2,658	0.262	0.440
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.023	0.150	0.000	1.000	2,658	0.023	0.150
z_ANC_other	0.276	0.447	0.000	1.000	2,658	0.276	0.447
z_ANC_mountain	0.017	0.128	0.000	1.000	2,658	0.017	0.128
z_FAMILY_FARM	0.476	0.499	0.000	1.000	2,658	0.476	0.499

Source: Own processing

Table B1 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 25% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	16908	0.4	0.4
1992	15371	33858	0.4	0.8
1993	15667	50744	0.4	1.2
1994	15818	67640	0.4	1.6
1995	14982	84540	0.4	2.0
1996	17022	101415	0.4	2.4
1997	20239	118351	0.5	2.7
1998	71621	135382	1.7	3.2
1999	110756	153774	2.6	3.6
2000	165699	173002	3.9	4.0
2001	217869	193108	5.1	4.5
2002	235136	213729	5.5	5.0
2003	254995	234452	6.0	5.5
2004	263299	255251	6.2	6.0
2005	254982	276068	6.0	6.5
2006	281535	296867	6.6	7.0
2007	312890	317696	7.4	7.5
2008	341632	338459	8.0	8.0
2009	398407	359062	9.4	8.5
2010	448202	379073	10.6	8.9
2011	482927	398263	11.4	9.4
2012	488483	416712	11.6	9.9
2013	493896	435030	11.7	10.3
2014	493971	453217	11.7	10.8
2015	494661	471402	11.7	11.2
2016	506070	489570	12.0	11.6
2017	520032	507450	12.4	12.1
2018	538894	524957	12.8	12.5
2019	540993	541924	15.2	15.2
2020	543252	558829	15.3	15.7
2021	558124	575666	15.7	16.2
2022	575464	592041	16.2	16.7
2023	595190	607847	16.8	17.2
2024	604803	622964	17.1	17.6
2025		637034		18.0
2026		651684		18.4
2027		666335		18.9
2028		680986		19.3
2029		695636		19.7
2030		710287		20.1

Source: own processing

Table B2 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 30% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	18027	0.4	0.4
1992	15371	35827	0.4	0.8
1993	15667	53596	0.4	1.3
1994	15818	71370	0.4	1.7
1995	14982	89145	0.4	2.1
1996	17022	106909	0.4	2.5
1997	20239	124702	0.5	2.9
1998	71621	142541	1.7	3.3
1999	110756	161028	2.6	3.8
2000	165699	179902	3.9	4.2
2001	217869	199163	5.1	4.7
2002	235136	218625	5.5	5.1
2003	254995	238116	6.0	5.6
2004	263299	257620	6.2	6.0
2005	254982	277121	6.0	6.5
2006	281535	296625	6.6	7.0
2007	312890	316108	7.4	7.4
2008	341632	335511	8.0	7.9
2009	398407	354790	9.4	8.4
2010	448202	373676	10.6	8.8
2011	482927	392058	11.4	9.3
2012	488483	410000	11.6	9.7
2013	493896	427865	11.7	10.1
2014	493971	445653	11.7	10.6
2015	494661	463440	11.7	11.0
2016	506070	481217	12.0	11.4
2017	520032	498826	12.4	11.9
2018	538894	516217	12.8	12.3
2019	540993	533297	15.2	15.0
2020	543252	550341	15.3	15.5
2021	558124	567346	15.7	16.0
2022	575464	584086	16.2	16.5
2023	595190	600501	16.8	17.0
2024	604803	616523	17.1	17.5
2025		632095		17.9
2026		648007		18.3
2027		663920		18.8
2028		679832		19.2
2029		695745		19.7
2030		711658		20.1

Source: own processing

Table B3 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 40% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	19026	0.4	0.4
1992	15371	37622	0.4	0.9
1993	15667	56212	0.4	1.3
1994	15818	74803	0.4	1.7
1995	14982	93395	0.4	2.2
1996	17022	111984	0.4	2.6
1997	20239	130579	0.5	3.0
1998	71621	149183	1.7	3.5
1999	110756	167895	2.6	3.9
2000	165699	186650	3.9	4.3
2001	217869	205404	5.1	4.8
2002	235136	224093	5.5	5.2
2003	254995	242747	6.0	5.7
2004	263299	261352	6.2	6.1
2005	254982	279933	6.0	6.6
2006	281535	298538	6.6	7.0
2007	312890	317062	7.4	7.4
2008	341632	335472	8.0	7.9
2009	398407	353755	9.4	8.3
2010	448202	371735	10.6	8.8
2011	482927	389386	11.4	9.2
2012	488483	406775	11.6	9.6
2013	493896	424119	11.7	10.0
2014	493971	441419	11.7	10.5
2015	494661	458719	11.7	10.9
2016	506070	476012	12.0	11.3
2017	520032	493211	12.4	11.7
2018	538894	510288	12.8	12.1
2019	540993	527195	15.2	14.8
2020	543252	544083	15.3	15.3
2021	558124	560949	15.7	15.8
2022	575464	577674	16.2	16.3
2023	595190	594227	16.8	16.8
2024	604803	610576	17.1	17.3
2025		626760		17.7
2026		643120		18.2
2027		659480		18.7
2028		675839		19.1
2029		692199		19.6
2030		708558		20.1

Source: own processing

Table B4 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 50% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	19475	0.4	0.5
1992	15371	38446	0.4	0.9
1993	15667	57420	0.4	1.4
1994	15818	76394	0.4	1.8
1995	14982	95367	0.4	2.2
1996	17022	114342	0.4	2.7
1997	20239	133314	0.5	3.1
1998	71621	152280	1.7	3.6
1999	110756	171155	2.6	4.0
2000	165699	189940	3.9	4.4
2001	217869	208571	5.1	4.9
2002	235136	227028	5.5	5.3
2003	254995	245420	6.0	5.7
2004	263299	263734	6.2	6.2
2005	254982	282014	6.0	6.6
2006	281535	300328	6.6	7.1
2007	312890	318531	7.4	7.5
2008	341632	336593	8.0	7.9
2009	398407	354517	9.4	8.3
2010	448202	372142	10.6	8.8
2011	482927	389477	11.4	9.2
2012	488483	406593	11.6	9.6
2013	493896	423673	11.7	10.0
2014	493971	440717	11.7	10.5
2015	494661	457761	11.7	10.9
2016	506070	474801	12.0	11.3
2017	520032	491764	12.4	11.7
2018	538894	508633	12.8	12.1
2019	540993	525370	15.2	14.8
2020	543252	542092	15.3	15.2
2021	558124	558799	15.7	15.7
2022	575464	575398	16.2	16.2
2023	595190	591869	16.8	16.7
2024	604803	608191	17.1	17.2
2025		624412		17.7
2026		640760		18.1
2027		657107		18.6
2028		673455		19.1
2029		689802		19.5
2030		706149		20.0

Source: own processing

Table B5 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 60% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	19727	0.4	0.5
1992	15371	38914	0.4	0.9
1993	15667	58109	0.4	1.4
1994	15818	77302	0.4	1.8
1995	14982	96496	0.4	2.3
1996	17022	115692	0.4	2.7
1997	20239	134881	0.5	3.1
1998	71621	154058	1.7	3.6
1999	110756	173045	2.6	4.0
2000	165699	191877	3.9	4.5
2001	217869	210479	5.1	4.9
2002	235136	228847	5.5	5.4
2003	254995	247135	6.0	5.8
2004	263299	265328	6.2	6.2
2005	254982	283481	6.0	6.6
2006	281535	301674	6.6	7.1
2007	312890	319737	7.4	7.5
2008	341632	337643	8.0	7.9
2009	398407	355399	9.4	8.4
2010	448202	372847	10.6	8.8
2011	482927	390011	11.4	9.2
2012	488483	406968	11.6	9.6
2013	493896	423893	11.7	10.0
2014	493971	440784	11.7	10.5
2015	494661	457675	11.7	10.9
2016	506070	474562	12.0	11.3
2017	520032	491379	12.4	11.7
2018	538894	508109	12.8	12.1
2019	540993	524722	15.2	14.8
2020	543252	541321	15.3	15.2
2021	558124	557906	15.7	15.7
2022	575464	574396	16.2	16.2
2023	595190	590773	16.8	16.7
2024	604803	607022	17.1	17.2
2025		623191		17.6
2026		639469		18.1
2027		655746		18.6
2028		672023		19.0
2029		688301		19.5
2030		704578		19.9

Source: own processing

Table B6 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 70% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	19887	0.4	0.5
1992	15371	39214	0.4	0.9
1993	15667	58552	0.4	1.4
1994	15818	77888	0.4	1.8
1995	14982	97223	0.4	2.3
1996	17022	116562	0.4	2.7
1997	20239	135892	0.5	3.2
1998	71621	155206	1.7	3.6
1999	110756	174274	2.6	4.1
2000	165699	193151	3.9	4.5
2001	217869	211752	5.1	4.9
2002	235136	230083	5.5	5.4
2003	254995	248324	6.0	5.8
2004	263299	266459	6.2	6.2
2005	254982	284550	6.0	6.7
2006	281535	302686	6.6	7.1
2007	312890	320679	7.4	7.5
2008	341632	338502	8.0	8.0
2009	398407	356167	9.4	8.4
2010	448202	373513	10.6	8.8
2011	482927	390572	11.4	9.2
2012	488483	407427	11.6	9.6
2013	493896	424249	11.7	10.1
2014	493971	441040	11.7	10.5
2015	494661	457829	11.7	10.9
2016	506070	474615	12.0	11.3
2017	520032	491333	12.4	11.7
2018	538894	507967	12.8	12.1
2019	540993	524488	15.2	14.8
2020	543252	540995	15.3	15.2
2021	558124	557489	15.7	15.7
2022	575464	573893	16.2	16.2
2023	595190	590190	16.8	16.7
2024	604803	606366	17.1	17.2
2025		622472		17.6
2026		638679		18.1
2027		654885		18.5
2028		671092		19.0
2029		687298		19.5
2030		703505		19.9

Source: own processing

Table B7 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 80% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	19998	0.4	0.5
1992	15371	39423	0.4	0.9
1993	15667	58860	0.4	1.4
1994	15818	78295	0.4	1.8
1995	14982	97729	0.4	2.3
1996	17022	117168	0.4	2.8
1997	20239	136596	0.5	3.2
1998	71621	156006	1.7	3.6
1999	110756	175136	2.6	4.1
2000	165699	194051	3.9	4.5
2001	217869	212660	5.1	5.0
2002	235136	230976	5.5	5.4
2003	254995	249194	6.0	5.8
2004	263299	267300	6.2	6.3
2005	254982	285359	6.0	6.7
2006	281535	303465	6.6	7.1
2007	312890	321420	7.4	7.6
2008	341632	339196	8.0	8.0
2009	398407	356806	9.4	8.4
2010	448202	374086	10.6	8.8
2011	482927	391075	11.4	9.2
2012	488483	407859	11.6	9.7
2013	493896	424609	11.7	10.1
2014	493971	441328	11.7	10.5
2015	494661	458046	11.7	10.9
2016	506070	474761	12.0	11.3
2017	520032	491407	12.4	11.7
2018	538894	507970	12.8	12.1
2019	540993	524421	15.2	14.8
2020	543252	540859	15.3	15.2
2021	558124	557284	15.7	15.7
2022	575464	573619	16.2	16.2
2023	595190	589851	16.8	16.7
2024	604803	605963	17.1	17.2
2025		622010		17.6
2026		638154		18.1
2027		654299		18.5
2028		670444		19.0
2029		686588		19.4
2030		702733		19.9

Source: own processing

Table B8 Simulations based on Bass Model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 90% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	20078	0.4	0.5
1992	15371	39575	0.4	0.9
1993	15667	59085	0.4	1.4
1994	15818	78594	0.4	1.8
1995	14982	98101	0.4	2.3
1996	17022	117614	0.4	2.8
1997	20239	137114	0.5	3.2
1998	71621	156595	1.7	3.7
1999	110756	175773	2.6	4.1
2000	165699	194719	3.9	4.5
2001	217869	213340	5.1	5.0
2002	235136	231651	5.5	5.4
2003	254995	249859	6.0	5.8
2004	263299	267949	6.2	6.3
2005	254982	285990	6.0	6.7
2006	281535	304081	6.6	7.1
2007	312890	322013	7.4	7.6
2008	341632	339759	8.0	8.0
2009	398407	357334	9.4	8.4
2010	448202	374570	10.6	8.8
2011	482927	391509	11.4	9.2
2012	488483	408240	11.6	9.7
2013	493896	424938	11.7	10.1
2014	493971	441604	11.7	10.5
2015	494661	458269	11.7	10.9
2016	506070	474930	12.0	11.3
2017	520032	491522	12.4	11.7
2018	538894	508031	12.8	12.1
2019	540993	524427	15.2	14.8
2020	543252	540811	15.3	15.2
2021	558124	557181	15.7	15.7
2022	575464	573462	16.2	16.2
2023	595190	589639	16.8	16.7
2024	604803	605697	17.1	17.1
2025		621693		17.6
2026		637785		18.1
2027		653876		18.5
2028		669968		19.0
2029		686060		19.4
2030		702152		19.9

Source: own processing

Table B9 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990, 100% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1990	480			
1991	17507	20093	0.4	0.5
1992	15371	39605	0.4	0.9
1993	15667	59129	0.4	1.4
1994	15818	78651	0.4	1.8
1995	14982	98173	0.4	2.3
1996	17022	117699	0.4	2.8
1997	20239	137213	0.5	3.2
1998	71621	156708	1.7	3.7
1999	110756	175895	2.6	4.1
2000	165699	194848	3.9	4.5
2001	217869	213471	5.1	5.0
2002	235136	231782	5.5	5.4
2003	254995	249989	6.0	5.9
2004	263299	268077	6.2	6.3
2005	254982	286115	6.0	6.7
2006	281535	304203	6.6	7.1
2007	312890	322132	7.4	7.6
2008	341632	339873	8.0	8.0
2009	398407	357441	9.4	8.4
2010	448202	374669	10.6	8.8
2011	482927	391599	11.4	9.2
2012	488483	408320	11.6	9.7
2013	493896	425008	11.7	10.1
2014	493971	441663	11.7	10.5
2015	494661	458318	11.7	10.9
2016	506070	474968	12.0	11.3
2017	520032	491551	12.4	11.7
2018	538894	508049	12.8	12.1
2019	540993	524434	15.2	14.8
2020	543252	540807	15.3	15.2
2021	558124	557166	15.7	15.7
2022	575464	573436	16.2	16.2
2023	595190	589602	16.8	16.7
2024	604803	605649	17.1	17.1
2025		621634		17.6
2026		637715		18.1
2027		653796		18.5
2028		669877		19.0
2029		685958		19.4
2030		702039		19.9

Source: own processing

Table B10 Simulations based on Generalized Bass model with exogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1993, 100% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1993	15667	15371	0.4	0.4
1994	15818	15667	0.4	0.4
1995	14982	15818	0.4	0.4
1996	17022	14982	0.4	0.4
1997	20239	17022	0.5	0.4
1998	71621	20239	1.7	0.5
1999	110756	71621	2.6	1.7
2000	165699	110756	3.9	2.6
2001	217869	165699	5.1	3.9
2002	235136	217869	5.5	5.1
2003	254995	235136	6.0	5.5
2004	263299	254995	6.2	6.0
2005	254982	263299	6.0	6.2
2006	281535	254982	6.6	6.0
2007	312890	281535	7.4	6.7
2008	341632	312890	8.0	7.3
2009	398407	341632	9.4	8.1
2010	448202	398407	10.6	9.4
2011	482927	448202	11.4	10.6
2012	488483	482927	11.6	11.5
2013	493896	488483	11.7	11.6
2014	493971	493896	11.7	11.7
2015	494661	493971	11.7	11.7
2016	506070	494661	12.0	11.7
2017	520032	506070	12.4	12.1
2018	538894	520032	12.8	12.4
2019	540993	538894	15.2	15.1
2020	543252	540993	15.3	15.2
2021	558124	543252	15.7	15.3
2022	575464	558124	16.2	15.7
2023	595190	575464	16.8	16.2
2024	604803	596632	17.1	16.9
2025		617632		17.5
2026		638467		18.1
2027		659138		18.6
2028		679646		19.2
2029		699992		19.8
2030		720178		20.4

Source: own processing

Note: For the post-2024 period, cumulative adoption is simulated assuming that subsidy support remains at its 2024 average level.

Table B11 Bass model with endogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990)

	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	Coef.
p	0.018	0.011	0.095	-0.003	0.040
q	0.150	0.056	0.008	0.040	0.260
M	610.574	36.102	0.000	539.816	681.332
R2	0.569				
Adj.R2	0.528				
RMSE	17.571				

Source: own processing

Figure B1 Cumulative adoption of organic farming according to Bass model with endogenous M – the Czech Republic (data from 1990)

Source: own processing

Table B12 Probit model estimates based on non-winsorised data – the Czech Republic

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.656	0.308	0.033	0.053	1.259
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.139	0.332	0.676	-0.791	0.513
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.023	0.043	0.597	-0.108	0.062
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.193	0.101	0.056	-0.391	0.005
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.167	0.084	0.046	0.003	0.331
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.349	0.304	0.251	-0.945	0.247
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.606	0.297	0.041	-1.187	-0.024
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-1.558	0.266	0.000	-2.079	-1.036
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.180	0.196	0.360	-0.564	0.205
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.349	0.189	0.065	-0.022	0.719
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-2.077	0.579	0.000	-3.211	-0.942
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	1.472	0.645	0.023	0.207	2.736
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	3.158	0.965	0.001	1.268	5.049
z_TF14_16	0.944	0.596	0.113	-0.225	2.113
z_TF14_20	0.637	1.852	0.731	-2.994	4.267
z_TF14_35	-0.962	2.979	0.747	-6.802	4.877
z_TF14_36	3.473	1.258	0.006	1.006	5.939
z_TF14_45	2.577	0.837	0.002	0.937	4.216
z_TF14_48	4.332	0.998	0.000	2.377	6.288
z_TF14_49	3.694	0.770	0.000	2.185	5.202
z_TF14_50	2.756	1.156	0.017	0.490	5.023
z_TF14_60	3.442	1.163	0.003	1.163	5.721
z_TF14_70	3.151	0.963	0.001	1.264	5.039
z_TF14_80	2.586	0.735	0.000	1.145	4.027
YEAR_2009	-0.300	0.207	0.147	-0.706	0.106
YEAR_2010	1.171	0.268	0.000	0.646	1.696
YEAR_2011	1.451	0.298	0.000	0.867	2.036
YEAR_2012	1.353	0.290	0.000	0.784	1.922
YEAR_2013	1.319	0.289	0.000	0.753	1.885
YEAR_2014	1.284	0.279	0.000	0.737	1.831
YEAR_2015	0.902	0.284	0.001	0.345	1.459
YEAR_2016	0.387	0.251	0.124	-0.106	0.880
YEAR_2017	0.244	0.218	0.263	-0.183	0.670
YEAR_2018	0.188	0.205	0.358	-0.213	0.590
YEAR_2020	0.119	0.056	0.033	0.009	0.228
_const.	-5.062	3.190	0.113	-11.313	1.190
lnsig2u	3.532	0.128		3.281	3.783
sigma_u	5.847	0.374		5.159	6.628
Rho	0.972	0.004		0.964	0.978
Wald chi2(35)	137.210		0.000		
Log likelihood	-1571.239				
Wald ch2(5): Mundlak devices	46.080		0.000		
Wald chi2(2): LABOUR_INTENSITY_res, ESIZE_res	1.320		0.516		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	89.529				
Number of observations	16,569				
Number of farms	1,998				

Source: own processing

Table B13 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit model based on non-winsorised data – the Czech Republic

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.019	0.010	0.045	0.000	0.038
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.004	0.010	0.677	-0.023	0.015
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.001	0.001	0.597	-0.003	0.002
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.006	0.003	0.070	-0.012	0.000
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.005	0.003	0.069	0.000	0.010
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.010	0.009	0.269	-0.028	0.008
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.018	0.009	0.037	-0.035	-0.001
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.046	0.006	0.000	-0.058	-0.034
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.005	0.006	0.356	-0.016	0.006
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.010	0.005	0.056	0.000	0.021
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.061	0.015	0.000	-0.091	-0.032
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.041	0.019	0.030	0.004	0.078
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.105	0.034	0.002	0.038	0.172
z_TF14_16	0.025	0.015	0.108	-0.005	0.055
z_TF14_20	0.016	0.049	0.743	-0.080	0.113
z_TF14_35	-0.020	0.056	0.715	-0.130	0.089
z_TF14_36	0.107	0.042	0.011	0.024	0.189
z_TF14_45	0.075	0.025	0.003	0.026	0.125
z_TF14_48	0.140	0.036	0.000	0.070	0.209
z_TF14_49	0.115	0.026	0.000	0.063	0.167
z_TF14_50	0.081	0.037	0.027	0.009	0.153
z_TF14_60	0.106	0.040	0.009	0.027	0.184
z_TF14_70	0.095	0.030	0.002	0.036	0.155
z_TF14_80	0.076	0.021	0.000	0.034	0.117

Source: own processing

Table B14 Probit model estimates– livestock and field crops production, 2008 and 2021 – the Czech Republic

Variable	Livestock production						Field crops production					
	2008			2021			2008			2021		
	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.271	0.100	0.007	-0.290	0.073	0.000	-0.186	0.083	0.024	-0.679	0.115	0.000
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE							0.632	0.356	0.076	-0.431	0.118	0.000
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.152	0.041	0.000									
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.412	0.154	0.007							0.251	0.143	0.079
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.248	0.099	0.012	0.072	0.040	0.076						
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.627	0.189	0.001	-0.513	0.167	0.002				-0.517	0.207	0.013
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS										0.388	0.096	0.000
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.566	0.257	0.028				-0.653	0.246	0.008			
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.							0.216	0.168	0.199			
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.							0.705	0.332	0.034			
z_ANC_other	0.238	0.284	0.402	0.012	0.262	0.964						
z_ANC_mountain	0.454	0.292	0.120	0.608	0.268	0.023						
z_TF14_48/z_TF14_16				1.594	0.418	0.000				1.668	0.457	0.000
Z_TF14_49/z_TF14_60				1.351	0.262	0.000				1.742	0.651	0.007
z_TF14_80/z_TF14_80							0.414	0.188	0.028	1.965	0.437	0.000
_const.	1.453	0.905	0.108	0.420	0.630	0.505	-0.661	0.454	0.145	1.561	0.749	0.037
Wald chi2(8/7/6/8)	103.39		0.000	162.09		0.000	19.39		0.000	55.26		0.000
Log likelihood	-123.1			-139.8			-248.4		-	-78.2		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	83.86			83.66			96.18			96.22		
Number of observations	347			355			812			622		
Number of organic farms	74			168			31			33		

Source: own processing

Table B15 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit models – livestock and field crops production, 2008 and 2021 – the Czech Republic

Variable	Livestock production						Field crops production					
	2008			2021			2008			2021		
	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.053	0.020	0.007	-0.063	0.016	0.000	-0.014	0.006	0.025	-0.044	0.007	0.000
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE							0.048	0.028	0.084	-0.028	0.007	0.000
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.030	0.008	0.000									
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.081	0.030	0.007							0.016	0.009	0.078
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.049	0.019	0.011	0.016	0.009	0.074						
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.124	0.035	0.000	-0.112	0.035	0.002				-0.033	0.013	0.009
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS										0.025	0.006	0.000
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.111	0.051	0.028				-0.050	0.019	0.009			
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.							0.015	0.012	0.194			
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.							0.077	0.053	0.147			
z_ANC_other	0.043	0.050	0.389	0.003	0.061	0.964						
z_ANC_mountain	0.088	0.055	0.109	0.135	0.062	0.030						

Source: own processing

Table B16 Logit model estimates – the Czech Republic

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	1.421	0.586	0.015	0.272	2.570
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.207	0.522	0.692	-1.231	0.817
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.043	0.082	0.598	-0.204	0.117
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.335	0.168	0.046	-0.665	-0.006
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.277	0.156	0.076	-0.029	0.584
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.624	0.542	0.250	-1.686	0.438
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.906	0.244	0.000	-1.384	-0.428
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-2.013	0.128	0.000	-2.263	-1.763
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.376	0.167	0.024	-0.703	-0.050
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.484	0.220	0.028	0.053	0.915
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-2.850	0.574	0.000	-3.976	-1.725
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	2.625	1.104	0.017	0.461	4.789
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	4.874	1.264	0.000	2.396	7.351
z_TF14_16	1.769	0.752	0.019	0.295	3.243
z_TF14_36	5.915	1.762	0.001	2.463	9.368
z_TF14_45	4.485	0.905	0.000	2.711	6.260
z_TF14_48	7.558	1.523	0.000	4.574	10.542
z_TF14_49	6.434	0.911	0.000	4.648	8.221
z_TF14_50	4.550	1.392	0.001	1.822	7.278
z_TF14_60	5.802	1.026	0.000	3.791	7.812
z_TF14_70	5.467	1.029	0.000	3.450	7.483
z_TF14_80	4.471	0.748	0.000	3.004	5.937
YEAR_2009	-0.304	0.376	0.420	-1.041	0.434
YEAR_2010	2.338	0.507	0.000	1.345	3.332
YEAR_2011	2.866	0.577	0.000	1.735	3.998
YEAR_2012	2.687	0.569	0.000	1.573	3.802
YEAR_2013	2.635	0.567	0.000	1.523	3.746
YEAR_2014	2.556	0.543	0.000	1.492	3.621
YEAR_2015	1.836	0.549	0.001	0.759	2.913
YEAR_2016	0.905	0.476	0.057	-0.028	1.839
YEAR_2017	0.629	0.419	0.133	-0.192	1.450
YEAR_2018	0.504	0.395	0.202	-0.270	1.279
YEAR_2020	0.217	0.092	0.019	0.036	0.398
_const.	-6.133	4.059	0.131	-14.088	1.823
lnsig2u	4.188	0.233		3.732	4.644
sigma_u	8.119	0.945		6.463	10.198
Rho	0.952	0.011		0.927	0.969
Wald chi2(33)	643.320		0.000		
Log likelihood	-1582.177				
Wald ch2(5): Mundlak devices	169.610		0.000		
Wald chi2(2): LABOUR_INTENSITY_res, ESIZE_res	0.580		0.748		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	89.692				
Number of observations	16,569				
Number of farms	1,998				

Source: own processing

Table B17 Average partial effects (APEs) of logit model– the Czech Republic

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.030	0.012	0.015	0.006	0.054
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.004	0.011	0.692	-0.026	0.017
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.001	0.002	0.597	-0.004	0.002
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.007	0.004	0.047	-0.014	0.000
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.006	0.003	0.081	-0.001	0.012
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.013	0.011	0.250	-0.035	0.009
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.019	0.005	0.000	-0.028	-0.009
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.042	0.003	0.000	-0.048	-0.036
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.008	0.004	0.027	-0.015	-0.001
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.010	0.005	0.025	0.001	0.019
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.060	0.012	0.000	-0.083	-0.036
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.051	0.019	0.008	0.013	0.089
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.111	0.029	0.000	0.055	0.168
z_TF14_16	0.037	0.015	0.015	0.007	0.067
z_TF14_36	0.124	0.036	0.001	0.054	0.193
z_TF14_45	0.094	0.019	0.000	0.057	0.131
z_TF14_48	0.158	0.033	0.000	0.092	0.223
z_TF14_49	0.134	0.021	0.000	0.094	0.175
z_TF14_50	0.095	0.028	0.001	0.040	0.150
z_TF14_60	0.121	0.020	0.000	0.082	0.161
z_TF14_70	0.114	0.021	0.000	0.074	0.155
z_TF14_80	0.093	0.015	0.000	0.064	0.123

Source: own processing

Table B18 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 30% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1985	24940			
1986	27160	47756		
1987	33047	70680		
1988	42393	93889		
1989	54295	117549		
1990	90021	141780		
1991	158477	167709		
1992	202379	196814		
1993	246458	227903		
1994	272139	260941	1.6	1.5
1995	309487	295097	1.8	1.7
1996	354171	330851	2.1	2.0
1997	389693	368480	2.3	2.2
1998	416518	407567	2.4	2.3
1999	452327	447738	2.6	2.6
2000	546023	489332	3.2	2.9
2001	634998	534517	3.7	3.1
2002	696978	582939	4.1	3.4
2003	734027	633515	4.3	3.7
2004	767891	685339	4.5	4.0
2005	807406	738279	4.7	4.3
2006	825538	792488	4.9	4.7
2007	865336	847268	5.1	5.0
2008	907786	903279	5.4	5.4
2009	947115	960563	5.6	5.7
2010	990702	1018993	5.9	6.1
2011	1015626	1078654	6.1	6.5
2012	1034355	1139001	6.2	6.8
2013	1044955	1199854	6.3	7.2
2014	1047633	1260990	6.3	7.6
2015	1088838	1322198	6.5	7.9
2016	1251320	1384481	7.5	8.3
2017	1373157	1450652	8.2	8.7
2018	1498027	1519364	9	9.1
2019	1613834	1590351	9.7	9.6
2020	1701895	1663148	10.3	10.1
2021	1802231	1737128	10.9	10.5
2022	1859560	1812254	11.2	10.9
2023	1888999	1887938	11.4	11.4
2024		1963870		11.9
2025		2040387		12.3
2026		2117365		12.8
2027		2194681		13.2
2028		2272209		13.7
2029		2349821		14.2
2030		2427386		14.6

Source: own processing

Table B19 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 40% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1985	24940			
1986	27160	48990		
1987	33047	73135		
1988	42393	97531		
1989	54295	122324		
1990	90021	147622		
1991	158477	174422		
1992	202379	204051		
1993	246458	235460		
1994	272139	268628	1.6	1.6
1995	309487	302808	1.8	1.8
1996	354171	338445	2.1	2.0
1997	389693	375798	2.3	2.2
1998	416518	414494	2.4	2.4
1999	452327	454195	2.6	2.6
2000	546023	495219	3.2	2.9
2001	634998	539621	3.7	3.1
2002	696978	587118	4.1	3.5
2003	734027	636704	4.3	3.7
2004	767891	687514	4.5	4.0
2005	807406	739425	4.7	4.3
2006	825538	792601	4.9	4.7
2007	865336	846350	5.1	5.0
2008	907786	901340	5.4	5.4
2009	947115	957630	5.6	5.7
2010	990702	1015102	5.9	6.0
2011	1015626	1073857	6.1	6.4
2012	1034355	1133336	6.2	6.8
2013	1044955	1193351	6.3	7.2
2014	1047633	1253668	6.3	7.5
2015	1088838	1314060	6.5	7.8
2016	1251320	1375610	7.5	8.2
2017	1373157	1441487	8.2	8.6
2018	1498027	1510367	9	9.1
2019	1613834	1582107	9.7	9.5
2020	1701895	1656305	10.3	10.0
2021	1802231	1732245	10.9	10.5
2022	1859560	1810038	11.2	10.9
2023	1888999	1888826	11.4	11.4
2024		1968104		11.9
2025		2048650		12.4
2026		2130393		12.9
2027		2213258		13.4
2028		2297165		13.9
2029		2382028		14.4
2030		2467759		14.9

Source: own processing

Table B20 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 50% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1985	24940			
1986	27160	49639		
1987	33047	74426		
1988	42393	99448		
1989	54295	124839		
1990	90021	150702		
1991	158477	177968		
1992	202379	207886		
1993	246458	239480		
1994	272139	272736	1.6	1.6
1995	309487	306952	1.8	1.8
1996	354171	342550	2.1	2.0
1997	389693	379784	2.3	2.2
1998	416518	418302	2.4	2.4
1999	452327	457783	2.6	2.6
2000	546023	498537	3.2	2.9
2001	634998	542557	3.7	3.2
2002	696978	589595	4.1	3.5
2003	734027	638687	4.3	3.7
2004	767891	688988	4.5	4.0
2005	807406	740382	4.7	4.3
2006	825538	793035	4.9	4.7
2007	865336	846260	5.1	5.0
2008	907786	900731	5.4	5.4
2009	947115	956511	5.6	5.7
2010	990702	1013488	5.9	6.0
2011	1015626	1071773	6.1	6.4
2012	1034355	1130797	6.2	6.8
2013	1044955	1190372	6.3	7.2
2014	1047633	1250257	6.3	7.5
2015	1088838	1310220	6.5	7.8
2016	1251320	1371377	7.5	8.2
2017	1373157	1437070	8.2	8.6
2018	1498027	1505986	9	9.0
2019	1613834	1578044	9.7	9.5
2020	1701895	1652873	10.3	10.0
2021	1802231	1729716	10.9	10.5
2022	1859560	1808755	11.2	10.9
2023	1888999	1889003	11.4	11.4
2024		1969857		11.9
2025		2052334		12.4
2026		2136395		12.9
2027		2221998		13.4
2028		2309096		13.9
2029		2397639		14.5
2030		2487568		15.0

Source: own processing

Table B21 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 60% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1985	24940			
1986	27160	50036		
1987	33047	75217		
1988	42393	100622		
1989	54295	126380		
1990	90021	152589		
1991	158477	180143		
1992	202379	210243		
1993	246458	241957		
1994	272139	275274	1.6	1.6
1995	309487	309519	1.8	1.8
1996	354171	345102	2.1	2.0
1997	389693	382272	2.3	2.3
1998	416518	420692	2.4	2.4
1999	452327	460049	2.6	2.6
2000	546023	500647	3.2	2.9
2001	634998	544444	3.7	3.2
2002	696978	591212	4.1	3.5
2003	734027	640012	4.3	3.7
2004	767891	690010	4.5	4.0
2005	807406	741096	4.7	4.3
2006	825538	793437	4.9	4.7
2007	865336	846350	5.1	5.0
2008	907786	900509	5.4	5.4
2009	947115	955983	5.6	5.7
2010	990702	1012662	5.9	6.0
2011	1015626	1070661	6.1	6.4
2012	1034355	1129409	6.2	6.8
2013	1044955	1188716	6.3	7.2
2014	1047633	1248337	6.3	7.5
2015	1088838	1308038	6.5	7.8
2016	1251320	1368954	7.5	8.2
2017	1373157	1434526	8.2	8.6
2018	1498027	1503448	9	9.0
2019	1613834	1575676	9.7	9.5
2020	1701895	1650857	10.3	10.0
2021	1802231	1728210	10.9	10.5
2022	1859560	1807960	11.2	10.9
2023	1888999	1889044	11.4	11.4
2024		1970803		11.9
2025		2054396		12.4
2026		2139808		12.9
2027		2227021		13.4
2028		2316010		14.0
2029		2406747		14.5
2030		2499200		15.1

Source: own processing

Table B22 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 70% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1985	24940			
1986	27160	50304		
1987	33047	75749		
1988	42393	101412		
1989	54295	127418		
1990	90021	153861		
1991	158477	181609		
1992	202379	211834		
1993	246458	243631		
1994	272139	276993	1.6	1.6
1995	309487	311260	1.8	1.8
1996	354171	346838	2.1	2.1
1997	389693	383969	2.3	2.3
1998	416518	422327	2.4	2.4
1999	452327	461604	2.6	2.7
2000	546023	502102	3.2	2.9
2001	634998	545754	3.7	3.2
2002	696978	592345	4.1	3.5
2003	734027	640952	4.3	3.8
2004	767891	690752	4.5	4.0
2005	807406	741634	4.7	4.3
2006	825538	793769	4.9	4.7
2007	865336	846476	5.1	5.0
2008	907786	900429	5.4	5.4
2009	947115	955699	5.6	5.7
2010	990702	1012180	5.9	6.0
2011	1015626	1069989	6.1	6.4
2012	1034355	1128552	6.2	6.8
2013	1044955	1187679	6.3	7.2
2014	1047633	1247124	6.3	7.5
2015	1088838	1306649	6.5	7.8
2016	1251320	1367403	7.5	8.2
2017	1373157	1432890	8.2	8.6
2018	1498027	1501808	9	9.0
2019	1613834	1574140	9.7	9.5
2020	1701895	1649544	10.3	10.0
2021	1802231	1727222	10.9	10.4
2022	1859560	1807430	11.2	10.9
2023	1888999	1889051	11.4	11.4
2024		1971392		11.9
2025		2055708		12.4
2026		2142001		12.9
2027		2230266		13.5
2028		2320497		14.0
2029		2412683		14.6
2030		2506811		15.1

Source: own processing

Table B23 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 80% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1985	24940			
1986	27160	50496		
1987	33047	76131		
1988	42393	101979		
1989	54295	128163		
1990	90021	154774		
1991	158477	182662		
1992	202379	212977		
1993	246458	244835		
1994	272139	278231	1.6	1.6
1995	309487	312517	1.8	1.8
1996	354171	348092	2.1	2.1
1997	389693	385198	2.3	2.3
1998	416518	423513	2.4	2.4
1999	452327	462736	2.6	2.7
2000	546023	503165	3.2	2.9
2001	634998	546715	3.7	3.2
2002	696978	593182	4.1	3.5
2003	734027	641653	4.3	3.8
2004	767891	691313	4.5	4.1
2005	807406	742051	4.7	4.3
2006	825538	794040	4.9	4.7
2007	865336	846600	5.1	5.0
2008	907786	900407	5.4	5.4
2009	947115	955533	5.6	5.6
2010	990702	1011872	5.9	6.0
2011	1015626	1069545	6.1	6.4
2012	1034355	1127977	6.2	6.8
2013	1044955	1186975	6.3	7.2
2014	1047633	1246294	6.3	7.5
2015	1088838	1305694	6.5	7.8
2016	1251320	1366332	7.5	8.2
2017	1373157	1431755	8.2	8.5
2018	1498027	1500668	9	9.0
2019	1613834	1573070	9.7	9.5
2020	1701895	1648626	10.3	10.0
2021	1802231	1726529	10.9	10.4
2022	1859560	1807053	11.2	10.9
2023	1888999	1889049	11.4	11.4
2024		1971794		11.9
2025		2056615		12.4
2026		2143524		12.9
2027		2232529		13.5
2028		2323636		14.0
2029		2416848		14.6
2030		2512164		15.2

Source: own processing

Table B24 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 90% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1985	24940			
1986	27160	50640		
1987	33047	76419		
1988	42393	102406		
1989	54295	128723		
1990	90021	155460		
1991	158477	183454		
1992	202379	213838		
1993	246458	245743		
1994	272139	279165	1.6	1.6
1995	309487	313466	1.8	1.8
1996	354171	349040	2.1	2.1
1997	389693	386128	2.3	2.3
1998	416518	424412	2.4	2.4
1999	452327	463596	2.6	2.7
2000	546023	503975	3.2	3.0
2001	634998	547449	3.7	3.2
2002	696978	593824	4.1	3.5
2003	734027	642194	4.3	3.8
2004	767891	691750	4.5	4.1
2005	807406	742381	4.7	4.3
2006	825538	794262	4.9	4.7
2007	865336	846713	5.1	5.0
2008	907786	900410	5.4	5.4
2009	947115	955429	5.6	5.6
2010	990702	1011662	5.9	6.0
2011	1015626	1069234	6.1	6.4
2012	1034355	1127567	6.2	6.8
2013	1044955	1186470	6.3	7.2
2014	1047633	1245694	6.3	7.5
2015	1088838	1305000	6.5	7.8
2016	1251320	1365550	7.5	8.2
2017	1373157	1430925	8.2	8.5
2018	1498027	1499833	9	9.0
2019	1613834	1572283	9.7	9.5
2020	1701895	1647950	10.3	10.0
2021	1802231	1726018	10.9	10.4
2022	1859560	1806774	11.2	10.9
2023	1888999	1889044	11.4	11.4
2024		1972086		11.9
2025		2057278		12.4
2026		2144642		12.9
2027		2234195		13.5
2028		2325952		14.0
2029		2419926		14.6
2030		2516127		15.2

Source: own processing

Table B25 Simulations based on Bass model with exogenous M – Germany (data from 1985, 100% of agricultural area)

Year	Organic farmland (hectare)	Predicted organic farmland (hectare)	Observed organic farmland as % of UAA	Predicted organic farmland as % of UAA
1985	24940			
1986	27160	50752		
1987	33047	76642		
1988	42393	102738		
1989	54295	129159		
1990	90021	155995		
1991	158477	184072		
1992	202379	214510		
1993	246458	246451		
1994	272139	279894	1.6	1.6
1995	309487	314207	1.8	1.8
1996	354171	349781	2.1	2.1
1997	389693	386856	2.3	2.3
1998	416518	425117	2.4	2.4
1999	452327	464271	2.6	2.7
2000	546023	504611	3.2	3.0
2001	634998	548028	3.7	3.2
2002	696978	594332	4.1	3.5
2003	734027	642625	4.3	3.8
2004	767891	692100	4.5	4.1
2005	807406	742649	4.7	4.3
2006	825538	794446	4.9	4.7
2007	865336	846813	5.1	5.0
2008	907786	900426	5.4	5.4
2009	947115	955360	5.6	5.6
2010	990702	1011513	5.9	6.0
2011	1015626	1069006	6.1	6.4
2012	1034355	1127262	6.2	6.8
2013	1044955	1186090	6.3	7.2
2014	1047633	1245241	6.3	7.5
2015	1088838	1304474	6.5	7.8
2016	1251320	1364956	7.5	8.2
2017	1373157	1430294	8.2	8.5
2018	1498027	1499196	9	9.0
2019	1613834	1571683	9.7	9.4
2020	1701895	1647433	10.3	10.0
2021	1802231	1725626	10.9	10.4
2022	1859560	1806559	11.2	10.9
2023	1888999	1889039	11.4	11.4
2024		1972307		11.9
2025		2057785		12.4
2026		2145498		12.9
2027		2235472		13.5
2028		2327729		14.0
2029		2422291		14.6
2030		2519176		15.2

Source: own processing

Table B26 Probit model estimates based on non-winsorised data – Germany

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	1.540	0.276	0.000	0.999	2.080
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	4.034	0.571	0.000	2.915	5.153
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-1.134	0.221	0.000	-1.567	-0.700
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.043	0.026	0.101	-0.094	0.008
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.061	0.054	0.261	-0.046	0.168
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.001	0.018	0.940	-0.037	0.034
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.226	0.190	0.233	-0.599	0.146
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-2.058	0.518	0.000	-3.073	-1.043
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.439	0.119	0.000	-0.672	-0.206
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	1.439	0.433	0.001	0.590	2.289
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.620	0.192	0.001	-0.997	-0.243
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-1.305	0.436	0.003	-2.160	-0.450
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.570	0.154	0.000	-0.872	-0.268
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	1.379	0.572	0.016	0.258	2.501
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	1.335	0.704	0.058	-0.045	2.716
z_ANC_other	0.623	0.197	0.002	0.237	1.010
Z_ANC_mountain	0.466	0.324	0.151	-0.170	1.101
z_TF14_16	0.245	0.280	0.383	-0.305	0.794
z_TF14_20	4.704	1.819	0.010	1.140	8.269
z_TF14_35	2.830	1.643	0.085	-0.390	6.050
z_TF14_36	2.522	1.504	0.094	-0.426	5.469
z_TF14_38	3.273	0.754	0.000	1.795	4.751
z_TF14_45	1.207	0.512	0.018	0.203	2.211
z_TF14_48	1.501	0.495	0.002	0.531	2.471
z_TF14_49	1.464	0.399	0.000	0.681	2.247
z_TF14_50	0.806	0.693	0.245	-0.552	2.164
z_TF14_60	1.572	0.603	0.009	0.389	2.754
z_TF14_70	1.140	0.469	0.015	0.221	2.058
z_TF14_80	0.780	0.347	0.024	0.101	1.459
z_PP_2014_2020	0.076	0.088	0.390	-0.097	0.248
YEAR_2021	-0.395	0.166	0.017	-0.719	-0.070
_const.	11.202	2.977	0.000	5.368	17.036
Insig2u	3.900	0.137		3.632	4.168
sigma_u	7.030	0.481		6.148	8.038
Rho	0.980	0.003		0.974	0.985
Wald chi2(31)	175.090		0.000		
Log likelihood	-5952.230				
Wald chi2(6): Mundlak's devices	24.680		0.000		
Wald chi2(1): LABOUR_INTENSITY_res, ESIZE_res	1.370		0.503		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	87.158				
Number of observations	99,064				
Number of farms	14,028				

Source: own processing

Table B27 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit model based on non-winsorised data – Germany

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	0.028	0.004	0.000	0.019	0.036
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.073	0.017	0.000	0.040	0.106
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.020	0.005	0.000	-0.030	-0.011
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.001	0.001	0.124	-0.002	0.000
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.001	0.001	0.273	-0.001	0.003
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	0.000	0.000	0.940	-0.001	0.001
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.004	0.004	0.248	-0.011	0.003
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.037	0.005	0.000	-0.047	-0.027
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.008	0.001	0.000	-0.011	-0.005
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.026	0.005	0.000	0.016	0.036
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.011	0.002	0.000	-0.016	-0.006
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.024	0.006	0.000	-0.036	-0.012
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.010	0.004	0.005	-0.017	-0.003
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.026	0.009	0.002	0.009	0.043
z_ALTITUDE > 600 m a.s.l.	0.025	0.012	0.042	0.001	0.049
z_ANC_other	0.011	0.004	0.002	0.004	0.019
Z_ANC_mountain	0.008	0.006	0.160	-0.003	0.020
z_TF14_16	0.004	0.004	0.406	-0.005	0.012
z_TF14_20	0.103	0.051	0.045	0.002	0.203
z_TF14_35	0.053	0.032	0.096	-0.009	0.114
z_TF14_36	0.046	0.032	0.159	-0.018	0.109
z_TF14_38	0.063	0.019	0.001	0.026	0.100
z_TF14_45	0.019	0.008	0.016	0.004	0.035
z_TF14_48	0.025	0.009	0.008	0.006	0.043
z_TF14_49	0.024	0.007	0.001	0.009	0.039
z_TF14_50	0.012	0.012	0.286	-0.010	0.035
z_TF14_60	0.026	0.011	0.020	0.004	0.048
z_TF14_70	0.018	0.008	0.030	0.002	0.034
z_TF14_80	0.012	0.006	0.037	0.001	0.023

Source: own processing

Table B28 Probit model estimates with year dummies – Germany

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	1.473	0.260	0.000	0.964	1.983
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	2.812	0.447	0.000	1.935	3.688
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.880	0.202	0.000	-1.277	-0.484
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.056	0.026	0.028	-0.106	-0.006
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.042	0.054	0.436	-0.063	0.147
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	0.010	0.018	0.578	-0.025	0.045
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.139	0.190	0.464	-0.511	0.233
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-1.700	0.441	0.000	-2.564	-0.835
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.437	0.121	0.000	-0.674	-0.199
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	1.362	0.361	0.000	0.655	2.070
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.627	0.162	0.000	-0.945	-0.309
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.565	0.277	0.041	-1.108	-0.022
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.585	0.153	0.000	-0.885	-0.285
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	1.100	0.502	0.028	0.116	2.084
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	1.166	0.629	0.064	-0.067	2.398
z_TF14_36	0.708	1.231	0.565	-1.705	3.122
z_TF14_38	2.409	0.615	0.000	1.204	3.613
z_TF14_45	0.524	0.425	0.217	-0.308	1.356
z_TF14_48	0.971	0.451	0.031	0.087	1.855
z_TF14_49	0.892	0.331	0.007	0.243	1.540
z_TF14_60	0.949	0.436	0.029	0.096	1.803
z_TF14_70	0.451	0.397	0.256	-0.327	1.229
z_TF14_80	0.297	0.283	0.294	-0.257	0.851
YEAR_2010	-0.244	0.081	0.003	-0.403	-0.085
YEAR_2011	-0.315	0.103	0.002	-0.517	-0.113
YEAR_2012	-0.556	0.107	0.000	-0.766	-0.346
YEAR_2013	-0.628	0.101	0.000	-0.825	-0.430
YEAR_2014	-0.764	0.102	0.000	-0.964	-0.564
YEAR_2015	-0.487	0.093	0.000	-0.668	-0.305
YEAR_2016	0.138	0.084	0.102	-0.027	0.303
YEAR_2019	0.078	0.065	0.231	-0.049	0.204
_const.	6.422	2.564	0.012	1.397	11.446
Insig2u	3.861	0.122		3.622	4.100
sigma_u	6.892	0.420		6.116	7.766
Rho	0.979	0.002		0.974	0.984
Wald chi2(31)	179.670		0.000		
Log likelihood	-5871.452				
Wald chi2(5): Mundlak's devices	18.300		0.003		
Wald chi2(2): LABOUR_INTENSITY_res, ESIZE_res	1.200		0.549		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	87.159				
Number of observations	99,064				
Number of farms	14,028				

Source: own processing

Table B29 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit model with year dummies – Germany

Variable	APE	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS_NUTS (t-1)	0.027	0.005	0.000	0.017	0.036
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE (t-1)	0.051	0.012	0.000	0.027	0.076
Within					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.016	0.005	0.000	-0.025	-0.007
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.001	0.001	0.047	-0.002	0.000
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.001	0.001	0.441	-0.001	0.003
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	0.000	0.000	0.585	0.000	0.001
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.003	0.004	0.473	-0.009	0.004
Between					
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.031	0.005	0.000	-0.042	-0.020
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.008	0.002	0.000	-0.011	-0.005
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.025	0.005	0.000	0.016	0.034
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.011	0.002	0.000	-0.016	-0.007
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.010	0.005	0.029	-0.020	-0.001
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.011	0.004	0.003	-0.018	-0.004
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.021	0.009	0.016	0.004	0.038
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.022	0.013	0.084	-0.003	0.047
z_TF14_36	0.013	0.022	0.563	-0.031	0.057
z_TF14_38	0.044	0.013	0.001	0.019	0.069
z_TF14_45	0.010	0.008	0.211	-0.005	0.025
z_TF14_48	0.018	0.009	0.043	0.001	0.035
z_TF14_49	0.016	0.007	0.014	0.003	0.029
z_TF14_60	0.017	0.008	0.031	0.002	0.033
z_TF14_70	0.008	0.007	0.268	-0.006	0.023
z_TF14_80	0.005	0.005	0.303	-0.005	0.016

Source: own processing

Table B30 Probit model estimates – livestock and field crops production, 2008 and 2021 – German

Variable	Livestock production						Field crops production					
	2008			2021			2008			2021		
	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z	Coef.	Std.err	P> z
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.371	0.066	0.000	-0.847	0.069	0.000	-0.379	0.062	0.000	-0.342	0.042	0.000
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	-0.190	0.045	0.000				-0.118	0.041	0.004	-0.091	0.046	0.048
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE							-0.077	0.042	0.066	-0.105	0.025	0.000
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.105	0.024	0.000	-0.045	0.028	0.102						
x_ln_RENTED_LAND				0.158	0.048	0.001				0.107	0.055	0.052
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE				-0.062	0.023	0.007				-0.055	0.026	0.035
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.245	0.102	0.016	-0.399	0.077	0.000	-0.140	0.085	0.099			
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS				0.100	0.021	0.000				0.069	0.023	0.003
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.607	0.091	0.000	-0.566	0.075	0.000	-0.519	0.101	0.000	-0.503	0.086	0.000
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.099	0.092	0.279	0.228	0.074	0.002	0.282	0.097	0.004	0.303	0.073	0.000
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.302	0.184	0.101	0.612	0.125	0.000	0.116	0.372	0.756	0.091	0.293	0.755
z_ANC_other	0.354	0.096	0.000	0.155	0.073	0.034						
z_ANC_mountain	0.903	0.250	0.000	0.338	0.106	0.001						
z_TF14_48/z_TF14_16	-0.652	0.279	0.019	-0.595	0.238	0.012				0.126	0.094	0.180
z_TF14_49/z_TF14_60	-0.380	0.142	0.008	-0.553	0.170	0.001				0.127	0.203	0.530
z_TF14_80/z_TF14_80	-0.414	0.168	0.014	-0.241	0.206	0.242	0.248	0.093	0.008	0.338	0.090	0.000
_const.	2.220	0.569	0.000	4.389	0.431	0.000	1.324	0.516	0.010	1.526	0.426	0.000
Wald chi2(12/14/8/12)	166.35		0.000	327.48		0.000	54.57		0.000	139.20		0.000
Log likelihood	-606.3			-1051.8			-469.8			-785.7		
Percentage of correctly predicted values	93.50			87.43			94.47			92.06		
Number of observations	2,863			3,318			2,735			3,135		
Number of organic farms	187			60			124			248		

Source: own processing

Table B31 Average partial effects (APEs) of probit models – livestock and field crops production, 2008 and 2021 – Germany

Variable	Livestock production						Field crops production					
	2008			2021			2008			2021		
	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z	APE	Std.err	P> z
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	-0.042	0.008	0.000	-0.148	0.011	0.000	-0.034	0.006	0.000	-0.046	0.006	0.000
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	-0.021	0.005	0.000				-0.011	0.004	0.005	-0.012	0.006	0.048
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE							-0.007	0.004	0.067	-0.014	0.003	0.000
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.012	0.003	0.000	-0.008	0.005	0.102						
x_ln_RENTED_LAND				0.028	0.008	0.001				0.014	0.007	0.052
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE				-0.011	0.004	0.008				-0.007	0.003	0.035
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.028	0.012	0.016	-0.070	0.013	0.000	-0.013	0.008	0.099			
x_ln_DEBT_TO_ASSETS				0.018	0.004	0.000				0.009	0.003	0.003
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.068	0.011	0.000	-0.099	0.013	0.000	-0.047	0.009	0.000	-0.067	0.012	0.000
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.011	0.010	0.281	0.039	0.013	0.002	0.028	0.011	0.009	0.044	0.011	0.000
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.038	0.027	0.152	0.124	0.029	0.000	0.010	0.036	0.776	0.011	0.039	0.768
z_ANC_other	0.036	0.009	0.000	0.027	0.013	0.034						
z_ANC_mountain	0.136	0.054	0.012	0.063	0.021	0.003						

Source: own processing

Table C1 Discrete-time duration model estimates – the Czech Republic

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS	0.234	0.162	0.150	-0.084	0.552
x_ln_RURAL_SUBSIDY	0.263	0.067	0.000	0.131	0.394
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.105	0.052	0.046	-0.208	-0.002
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.080	0.067	0.233	-0.212	0.051
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.290	0.147	0.049	0.001	0.578
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.153	0.087	0.079	-0.323	0.018
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.435	0.208	0.036	-0.842	-0.028
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.487	0.280	0.082	-1.037	0.062
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	-0.383	0.405	0.345	-1.177	0.412
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	-0.656	0.543	0.228	-1.721	0.410
z_ANC_other	-0.137	0.350	0.696	-0.823	0.549
z_ANC_mountain	0.215	0.429	0.617	-0.626	1.056
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_3	0.214	0.404	0.597	-0.578	1.006
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.372	0.492	0.450	-1.336	0.592
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.602	0.489	0.219	-1.560	0.357
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-0.998	0.590	0.091	-2.155	0.158
z_TF14_16	0.563	0.675	0.404	-0.759	1.886
z_TF14_20	3.126	0.877	0.000	1.407	4.845
z_TF14_35	0.734	0.975	0.452	-1.177	2.645
z_TF14_36	-0.625	1.220	0.609	-3.016	1.766
z_TF14_45	0.691	0.682	0.311	-0.647	2.029
z_TF14_48	2.114	0.742	0.004	0.660	3.569
z_TF14_49	1.468	0.545	0.007	0.400	2.537
z_TF14_50	1.295	1.228	0.291	-1.111	3.702
z_TF14_60	0.668	1.224	0.585	-1.730	3.066
z_TF14_70	1.176	0.685	0.086	-0.166	2.518
z_TF14_80	1.133	0.472	0.016	0.207	2.058
z_PP_2014_2020	-1.639	0.294	0.000	-2.215	-1.062
YEAR_2021	-2.303	1.025	0.025	-4.312	-0.294
_const.	-5.260	1.004	0.000	-7.229	-3.292
Log pseudolikelihood	-458.093				
AIC	0.065				
BIC	-142321.4				
AUC	0.871	0.016		0.839	0.903
Number of observations	14,915				
Number of events	93				

Source: own processing

Note: x_ln_RURAL_SUBSIDY denotes total support for rural development per hectare (SE624/SE025), in logarithms; z_ECONOMIC_SIZE are dummies for FADN's ES6 categories: 1_2 represent Standard Output (SO) < 25,000 EUR; 3: 25,000–<50,000 EUR; 4: 50,000–<100,000 EUR; 5: 100,000–<500,000 EUR; and 6: ≥ 500,000 EUR; z_PP_2014_2021 is a dummy variable for the Common Agricultural Policy programming period 2014–2020.

Table C2 Discrete-time duration model estimates of reversion from organic to conventional agriculture in the Czech Republic

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_In_ORGANIC_FARMS	-0.241	0.298	0.418	-0.825	0.342
x_In_MARKET_SHARE	-2.156	0.914	0.018	-3.947	-0.365
x_In_DIRECT_PAYMENT	0.065	0.054	0.229	-0.041	0.172
x_In_RURAL_SUBSIDY	-0.183	0.031	0.000	-0.244	-0.123
x_In_INVESTMENT_SUBSIDY	-0.022	0.033	0.511	-0.086	0.043
x_In_ECONOMIC_SIZE	0.161	0.080	0.044	0.004	0.317
x_In_FIXED_ASSETS	0.049	0.106	0.641	-0.158	0.257
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	-0.628	0.265	0.018	-1.149	-0.108
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	-0.790	0.642	0.218	-2.047	0.468
z_ANC_other	0.179	0.279	0.520	-0.367	0.726
z_ANC_mountain	-0.420	0.591	0.478	-1.579	0.739
z_TF14_16	-1.051	0.490	0.032	-2.010	-0.091
z_TF14_20	-0.980	0.434	0.024	-1.830	-0.130
z_TF14_36	-1.455	0.851	0.087	-3.123	0.212
z_TF14_45	-2.012	0.750	0.007	-3.483	-0.541
z_TF14_48	-1.350	0.611	0.027	-2.547	-0.152
z_TF14_49	-1.825	0.439	0.000	-2.686	-0.965
z_TF14_50	-0.676	0.465	0.146	-1.588	0.236
z_TF14_60	-1.179	0.696	0.090	-2.543	0.184
z_TF14_70	-0.014	0.648	0.983	-1.285	1.257
z_TF14_80	-0.226	0.300	0.451	-0.813	0.362
c_time_from_2008	0.181	0.080	0.023	0.025	0.337
_const.	-2.009	1.154	0.082	-4.271	0.253
Log pseudolikelihood	-283.318				
AIC	0.195				
BIC	-24588.53				
Precision	0.700				
Recall	0.090				
Number of observations	3,077				
Number of events	78				

Source: own processing

Note: x_In_RURAL_SUBSIDY denotes total support for rural development per hectare (SE624/SE025) x_In_DIRECT_PAYMENT represents direct payments per hectare (SE606/SE025), x_In_INVESTMENT_SUBSIDY is subsidies for investments per hectare (SE406/SE025). All variables are expressed in logarithms.

Table C3 Discrete-time duration model estimates – Germany

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS	0.325	0.079	0.000	0.171	0.480
x_ln_RURAL_SUBSIDY	0.199	0.023	0.000	0.154	0.244
x_ln_CEREALS_ARABLE	-0.168	0.022	0.000	-0.211	-0.124
x_ln_COWS_TLU	-0.025	0.040	0.538	-0.103	0.054
x_ln_RENTED_LAND	0.090	0.074	0.223	-0.055	0.235
x_ln_RENTAL_PRICE	-0.066	0.036	0.066	-0.137	0.004
x_ln_LABOUR_INTENSITY	-0.465	0.106	0.000	-0.674	-0.257
z_FAMILY_FARM	-0.031	0.134	0.819	-0.293	0.231
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	0.199	0.134	0.138	-0.064	0.461
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	0.034	0.221	0.876	-0.398	0.467
z_ANC_other	-0.441	0.131	0.001	-0.698	-0.184
z_ANC_mountain	-0.312	0.236	0.186	-0.773	0.150
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_4	-0.428	0.166	0.010	-0.753	-0.102
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_5	-0.693	0.174	0.000	-1.035	-0.351
z_ECONOMIC_SIZE_6	-1.541	0.315	0.000	-2.158	-0.923
z_TF14_16	-0.217	0.249	0.383	-0.705	0.271
z_TF14_20	1.972	0.647	0.002	0.705	3.240
z_TF14_35	1.180	0.392	0.003	0.411	1.949
z_TF14_36	0.264	0.609	0.665	-0.930	1.458
z_TF14_38	-0.104	1.089	0.924	-2.238	2.029
z_TF14_45	0.197	0.327	0.547	-0.444	0.838
z_TF14_48	-0.090	0.355	0.800	-0.785	0.605
z_TF14_49	0.740	0.206	0.000	0.336	1.144
z_TF14_50	-0.747	0.392	0.057	-1.515	0.021
z_TF14_60	-0.163	0.554	0.769	-1.248	0.923
z_TF14_70	-0.562	0.549	0.306	-1.637	0.514
z_TF14_80	-0.492	0.269	0.068	-1.019	0.036
z_PP_2014_2020	0.856	0.136	0.000	0.589	1.123
YEAR_2021	0.689	0.216	0.001	0.265	1.112
_const.	-6.556	0.461	0.000	-7.459	-5.654
Log pseudolikelihood	-2120.706				
AIC	0.038				
BIC	-1310736				
AUC	0.8300	0.011		0.809	0.851
Number of observations	113,001				
Number of events	364				

Source: own processing

Note: x_ln_RURAL_SUBSIDY denotes total support for rural development per hectare (SE624/SE025), in logarithms; z_ECONOMIC_SIZE are dummies for FADN's ES6 categories: 1_2 represent Standard Output (SO) < 25,000 EUR; 3: 25,000–<50,000 EUR; 4: 50,000–<100,000 EUR; 5: 100,000–<500,000 EUR; and 6: ≥ 500,000 EUR; z_PP_2014_2021 is a dummy variable for the Common Agricultural Policy programming period 2014–2020.

Table C4 Discrete-time duration model estimates of reversion from organic to conventional agriculture in Germany

Variable	Coef.	Std.err.	P> z	[95% conf. int.]	
x_ln_ORGANIC_FARMS	-0.444	0.163	0.006	-0.763	-0.125
x_ln_MARKET_SHARE	-1.286	2.211	0.561	-5.619	3.047
x_ln_DIRECT_PAYMENT	0.038	0.057	0.502	-0.074	0.150
x_ln_RURAL_SUBSIDY	-0.267	0.021	0.000	-0.308	-0.225
x_ln_INVESTMENT_SUBSIDY	-0.007	0.082	0.928	-0.168	0.154
x_ln_ECONOMIC_SIZE	0.214	0.116	0.065	-0.013	0.441
x_ln_FIXED_ASSETS	0.275	0.146	0.060	-0.012	0.562
z_ALTITUDE_300-600 m a.s.l.	-0.815	0.301	0.007	-1.404	-0.225
z_ALTITUDE_> 600 m a.s.l.	-1.570	0.746	0.035	-3.031	-0.108
z_ANC_other	0.326	0.314	0.300	-0.290	0.942
z_ANC_mountain	1.424	0.704	0.043	0.045	2.804
z_TF14_16	-0.747	0.461	0.105	-1.649	0.156
z_TF14_20	-1.548	0.634	0.015	-2.790	-0.305
z_TF14_36	-2.391	0.856	0.005	-4.069	-0.713
z_TF14_45	-1.379	1.019	0.176	-3.377	0.619
z_TF14_48	-0.072	0.317	0.821	-0.692	0.549
z_TF14_49	0.023	0.692	0.974	-1.334	1.379
z_TF14_50	-0.256	0.381	0.502	-1.002	0.491
z_TF14_60	-1.039	0.790	0.189	-2.588	0.510
z_TF14_70	-0.049	0.789	0.951	-1.596	1.498
z_TF14_80	-0.019	0.684	0.978	-1.360	1.322
c_time_from_2008	-0.769	0.459	0.094	-1.668	0.130
_const.	0.084	0.116	0.469	-0.144	0.313
Log pseudolikelihood	-443.439				
AIC	0.110				
BIC	-75324.57				
Precision	0.333				
Recall	0.010				
Number of observations	8,407				
Number of events	99				

Source: own processing

Note: x_ln_RURAL_SUBSIDY denotes total support for rural development per hectare (SE624/SE025) x_ln_DIRECT_PAYMENT represents direct payments per hectare (SE606/SE025), x_ln_INVESTMENT_SUBSIDY is subsidies for investments per hectare (SE406/SE025). All variables are expressed in logarithms.

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